
Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación y Universidades.

Curriculum vitae

Name: Jesús Miguel Ibáñez Godoy

Date: 10/02/2024

INDEX

PERSONAL INFORMATION	3
SUMMARY	4
KEY WORDS	4
SCIENTIFIC HIGHLIGHTS	5
FUNDING	6
RECENTEN YEARS TRACK RECORD	8
DETAILED ACADEMIC CURRICULUM	13
MANAGEMENT AND RESPONSIBILITY POSITIONS	14
SCHOLAR AND RESEARCH STAYS IN FOREIGN CENTERS OR OUTSIDE THE UGR	14
PARTICIPATION IN INTERNATIONAL AND PRESTIGIOUS COMMITTEES AND REPRESENTATIONS	16
TEACHING ACTIVITY	18
DIRECTED THESES	22
DETAILED RESEARCH CURRICULUM	26
PARTICIPATION IN R&D PROJECTS FINANCED IN PUBLIC CALLS	26
PERSONNEL HIRED UNDER THEIR R&D PROJECTS	31
MULTIDISCIPLINARY VOLCANOLOGICAL CAMPAIGNS	34
ADVISOR TO THE RESEARCH EXECUTIVE AGENCY (REA)	39
SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS	41
PRESENTATIONS AT CONFERENCES	59
EXPERIENCE IN ORGANIZING R&D ACTIVITIES	81

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Family name (2 names): Ibáñez Godoy, Frist Name: Jesús M.

Date of birth: 23 August 1964

Nationality: Spanish

Researcher unique identifier(s):

ORCID: 0000-0002-9846-8781,

Researcher ID: G-9910-2019,

Scopus Author ID: 7101992312

Google Scholar: <https://scholar.google.es/citations?user=vH37E5MAAAAJ&hl=es&oi=ao>

ResearchGate: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Jesus-Ibanez-3>

EDUCATION

1990 PhD (Coda wave and Lg attenuation in South Spain and Italy using digital seismograms)

Science Faculty, University of Granada (UGR), Spain (Summa Cum Laude)

1987 Masters, Science Faculty, UGR, Spain (Highest rating 10/10)

1987 Degree in Physics, Science Faculty, UGR, Spain (Final score 8/10)

CURRENT POSITION

2010– Full Professor in Physics of the Earth

Department of Theoretical Physics and Cosmos, Science Faculty, and Andalusian Institute of Geophysics, UGR, Spain

PREVIOUS POSITIONS

1993–2010 Associate Professor in Physics of the Earth, UGR

1992–1993 Assistant Professor, UGR

1992 Post-doctoral researcher, National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM)

1992 Post-doctoral researcher, University of Salerno

1990–1991 Post-doctoral researcher, Harvard University

1988–1990 Pre-doctoral fellow, Instituto Andaluz de Geofísica, UGR

PERSONAL CONTACT

e-mail: jibanez@ugr.es

tlf: (+34) 625 611 818

PERSONAL ADDRESS

Calle Barranco de los Lobos, nº 64, Urbanización Santa Clara Golf. Otura. 18630 Granada, Spain

UNESCO CODE

2507. 2507.05. 2506.21

SUMMARY

KEY WORDS

Seismology; Volcano seismology; High-definition seismic tomography (velocity & attenuation, active & passive data); Automatic & real-time seismic-volcanic signal processing; Machine learning and deep learning of seismic signals; Seismic inversion, source analysis, pattern recognition, and classification; Seismo-volcanic models; Seismic antennas; Seismic and volcanic hazard.

INSTITUTIONAL RESPONSIBILITIES

2016–2017 Member of the jury of the Jaime I research prizes, "Protection of the Environment".

2009–2012 Director of the Andalusian Institute of Geophysics, UGR

1998–2009 Vice-head of the Andalusian Institute of Geophysics, UGR

REVIEWING ACTIVITIES

2008– Chair, Vice-chair & evaluator, Marie Slovoska-Curie Programme (FP7, H2020, Horizon Europe). Actions: ITN, IF, and Societal Changes in Environmental and Geosciences (69 contracts received)

1994– Grant reviewer for national and international organizations (i.e., Spain, NATO, Italy, New Zealand, The Netherlands, Luxemburg, Argentina, Mexico, France, Belgium, Ireland, Czech Republic, Switzerland, Norway, Perú, Poland, Switzerland)

1991– Invited peer reviewer and editor for regular and special volumes of various journals, including Nature, AGU, SSA, Elsevier, Pergamon journals.

SUPERVISION OF POST-GRADUATE STUDENTS AND POSTDOCTORAL FELLOWS

Current PhD students (1 Universidad Nacional de La Plata [UNLP] and 2 UGR)

Past 20 PhDs (5 on machine learning [ML] at volcanoes)/27 Masters (7 on ML)

Mostly of them have permanent or high-level contracts at academic and research institutions, including: **Javier Almendros**, Associate Professor at UGR, responsible for Antarctic Research projects, coordinator/head of Master GEOMET; **Carmen Martínez-Arévalo**, Associate Professor & Secretary of the Engineering School, Polytechnic University of Madrid; **Elisabetta Giampiccolo**, Researcher, INGV-Osservatorio Etneo; **Miguel Abril**, Technician Researcher, Andalusian Astrophysics Institute; **Daria Zandomenghi**, UK-based Independent Scientific Consultant; **Araceli García-Yeguas**, Assistant Professor, UGR; **Gabriela Badi**, Associate Professor at UNLP, responsible for seismology at the Argentinean Volcanological Observatory; **Enrique Carmona**, Researcher, Andalusian Institute of Geophysics; **Janire Prudencio**, Associate Professor at UGR, soon to be UC-Berkeley; **Ligdamis Gutiérrez**, Researcher, UGR; **Cintia Bengoa**, Researcher, Observatorio Volcanológico de los Andes del Sur; **Alejandro Díaz-Moreno**, hired in a large UK

company as a geophysicist; **Manuel Títos**, Postdoc researcher at UGR, **Guillermo Cortés**, Assitant prof. at UGR; **Angel Bueno**, Post-doctoral Researcher, Germany, **Ignacio Castro-Melgar**, Postdoctoral researcher at Germany. In addition, cosupervising a Marie Slovoska-Curie Fellow (**Dr. Luciano Zucarello**, presently a Researcher at INGV Pisa).

SCIENTIFIC HIGHLIGHTS

- Pioneer in the use of **seismic antennas** and **seismic active experiments** on active volcanoes, beginning with the first deployment in Tenerife in 1994. Subsequent locations have included Asama, Deception Island, Stromboli, Etna, Vesuvius, Colima, Copahue, Cape Verde, Tenerife, and the Azores. For many of these, I obtained the first tomographic images (velocity and attenuation).
- Pioneer in the use of **machine learning (ML)** and **deep learning (DL)** in volcano seismology, with the first paper published in 2006. I have applied ML to volcanoes that include Deception, Colima, Peteroa, Mt. Etna, Bezymianny Stromboli, Soufrière Hills, Mount St. Helens, Telica, and San Cristóbal, etc.
- Pioneer in the application of seismic signal analysis techniques (Shannon Entropy) to establish a **universally valid tool** in carrying out **early warnings of volcanic eruptions**. Currently the USGS has established it as routine volcanic monitoring for all Alaska volcanoes.
- A very high scientific productivity in velocity and attenuation seismic tomography in numerous active volcanoes using active and passive seismic data and large multidisciplinary experiments. I highlight the recent work carried out in the La Palma eruption (2021) where, for the first time in the world, a three-dimensional image of the interior of the eruptive process was made in real time, that is, during the eruption itself.
- Principal Investigator (PI) on numerous **field seismic campaigns** in Antarctica (1994–2008, including 8 expeditions from 1988–2005) and other relevant volcanoes. See next table for more details
- Invited researcher at universities in Argentina, Mexico, Portugal, Ireland, the USA, France, Italy, Japan, the UK, Chile, and Turkey, among others.
- Member of different volcanological observatories. Associated researcher of Osservatorio Etneo (INGV).

PUBLICATIONS

1990– 146 ISI publications (current H-index: 42)
256 Presentations at conferences
2 books
20 chapters in edited books (with ISBN)
10 technical reports (with ISSN or ISBN)
10 Smithsonian Institution special reports.

FUNDING

1994– PI on 24 research projects or contracts in **competitive calls** (see examples below), attracting nearly 4.8 M € of external funding to the UGR, including around 30 associated contracts for studentships, technicians, and postdoctoral researchers. In addition I was collaborator in another 45 research projects.

Acronym	Reference	Period	Funding	Contracts	Description
LEARNING	PID2022-143083NB-I00	2023–2026	287.500 €	2	Multidisciplinary Forecasting
FEMALE	PID2019-106260GB-I00	2020–2023	240.000 €	2	Forecasting (various volcanoes)
KNOWAVES	TEC2015-68752	2016–2019	245.000 €	1	DL (various volcanoes)
MED-SUV.ISES	EUROFLEETS2-SI-005	2014–2015	900.000 €	0	Etna, Aeolian Islands
MED-SUV	EU. FP7–308665-1.	2012–2014	458.000 €	4	Etna, Aeolian Islands
EPHESTOS	CGL2011-29499-C02-01	2012–2014	242.000 €	3	Cape Verde, Colima,
HISS	CGL2008-01660	2009–2011	284.713 €	2	Canary Islands, Colima
VOLUME	UE, FP6-2004-Global-3-018471	2005–2007	320.000 €	3	Colima, Deception, Etna
SIS-VOLTEDEC	CGL2005-07589-C03-02/ANT	2006–2008	92.820 €	2	Deception, Copahue
TOM-TEIDEVS	CGL2004-05744-C04-01	2004–2006	224.250 €	2	Tenerife
TOMODEC	REN2001-3833	2002–2005	346.920 €	3	Deception
e-Ruption	EU. EVR1-2001-00024	2002–2004	385.000 €	3	Canary Island, Azores
	ANT98-1111	1999–2002	188.514 €	2	Deception Island, Copahue
	ANT95-0994-C03-02	1995–1998	124.619 €	2	Deception Island, Copahue

In addition, I have secured funding for various **volcano field experiments**

Field experiment	Place	Period	Funding	People	Description
ANTARCTIC	DECEPTION	1994–2008	1.2 M €	Up to 60	Oceanographic vessels & Antarctic bases
STROMBOLI	STROMBOLI	1997	150.000 €	20	Seismic antennas
TOMOVES	VESUVIUS	1998	125.000 €	25	Multiparametric
ARRAYS-ETNA	ETNA	Sept, 2000	125.000 €	20	Double Seismic Array
E-ruption	AZORES	2003	240.000 €	35	Multiparametric
COPAHUE	COPAHUE	2004–2010	120.000 €	10	Seismic arrays
COLIMA SURVEY	COLIMA	2005–2006	90.000 €	15	Broadband and seismic antennas
TOMODEC	DECEPTION	2004–2005	320.000 €	45	Oceanographic vessels & Antarctic bases
TOMTEIDEVS	TENERIFE	2007	280.000 €	40	Multiparametric with oceanic vessel
HISS	TENERIFE	2011–2013	180.000 €	25	Broadband
EPHESTOS	CAPE VERDE	2014–2015	100.000 €	15	Broadband
TOMO-ETNA/MEDSUV	ETNA	2013–2014	1 M €	Up to 80	Oceanographic vessels & Antarctic bases

TEACHING ACTIVITIES.

1989– I teach various undergraduate (Geophysics, Physics, Geology, Biology, Civil Engineering) and Masters courses at the University of Granada. I have been an invited teacher at various universities around the world (e.g., Harvard University, University of Washington, Rice University, UN La Plata, U. Buenos Aires, Naples, UC Dublin, U. Catania, U. Colima, UNAM, U. Strasbourg, U. Izmir).

MAJOR COLLABORATIONS.

I have created and curated a strong network of collaborations (reflected in my published papers) with researchers and institutions around the world, including those in Italy, France, Germany, the UK, Ireland, the USA, Japan, Mexico, Argentina, Turkey, Perú, Costa Rica and Russia.

RECENT TEN YEARS TRACK RECORD.

Over last 10 years, first as tenured professor and now as full professor, I have devoted my time to academic research, teaching (undergraduate and postgraduate), training and mentoring young scientists, disseminating knowledge, procuring funding (regional, national, and European authorities), managing projects, and creating a multidisciplinary research group.

Teaching: I have been awarded teaching honours and received excellent evaluations (average of > 4.5/5).

Research: I always aim to develop **multidisciplinary and international teams**, and I have brought together researchers from signal processing, machine learning, geology, physics, and seismology. In the last 10 years, I have supervised 9 PhD theses (2 still on-going), of which 5 combine **machine learning (ML)** with volcano seismology. I also receive within our group researchers from different countries to carry out pre and postdoctoral training stays with us. I currently have two predoctoral researchers from Panama and Ireland for stays of more than three years. Over this period, I have successfully applied for three National Research Projects as a Principal Investigator (PI); these combined all of the above disciplines and were awarded by panels in Engineering and Geoscience. I have participated as a Partner in two European Union (EU) projects focused on volcano seismology. Recently, my research group has been granted an Innovative Training Network (ITN) project. It is indicative of the quality of our research that one of the PhD students subsequently obtained a Marie Skłodowska-Curie fellowship (hosted at the Università de Udine, Italy). Moreover, I have received another Marie Skłodowska-Curie Fellow to work in ML applied to volcano seismology. I have consolidated **an international research network** (reflected in my literature record) with researchers in Italy, Mexico, Argentina, Ireland, Germany, the USA, the UK, Japan, and other countries. This network is consolidated and is reflected in the fact that all the publications made in the last 20 years always have at least two different institutions involved, with an average of three researchers from different countries. During this period, I also coordinated one of the most complex multidisciplinary experiments performed in the field of volcanology (TOMO-ETNA); the success of this experiment demonstrated my capabilities in coordinating large research teams and producing high quality results (see below for details). Another quality indicator of my level of expertise is my appointment as **Chair** in the Environment and Geosciences Panel in the IF and PF MSC actions since 2020. In addition I act as **Vice-chair** and evaluator (starting in 2008) of the **EU Marie Skłodowska-Curie Programme** (FP7, H2020 and Horizon Europe; actions ITN, IF, and Societal Changes in different panels: 152 contracts received).

Community and service: From 2009 to 2012, I was **Director** of the Andalusian Institute of Geophysics (University of Granada) and a member of Civil Protection Services in Spain, Mexico, Italy, Argentina, and Cape Verde. In 2016 and 2017, I was a jury member for the **“Jaime I research prizes: Protection of the Environment”**, the most prestigious Spanish research prize.

Invited positions and presentations (established international conferences and/or institutions)

I have been a Visiting Professor at a number of universities (e.g., the Universidad Nacional de La Plata [UNLP], Argentina in 2018, 2020 and 2022, and the Universidad de Colima, México, in 2014, 2016, & 2018, 2020, 2021, 2022 and 2023) and research institutions (e.g., INGV in Naples [2012, 2014 and 2018] and Catania [2013, 2015, 2018]) within the framework of the VULCAMED program. Additionally, I have given invited presentations at conferences and institutions around the world (e.g., University of California at Berkeley, USGS-Menlo Park, Official College of Engineers of Guatemala, University of Colima, University of Liverpool, IGP-Perú, University of Cork, UCDublin, etc.).

Research expeditions led

TOMO-ETNA (June–November 2014) included both land-based and offshore activities; the main objective was to obtain new high-resolution seismic tomography beneath Mt. Etna, north-eastern Sicily, and the Aeolian Islands. It represents the **first experiment** covering such a wide and heterogeneous region, including two volcanic environments and five active volcanoes. We used two removable seismic networks (short period and broadband networks composed of 80 and 20 stations, respectively), 25 ocean bottom seismometers (OBS), and the permanent seismic network of INGV; in total, there were 200 seismic stations. The oceanographic research vessel (R/V) Sarmiento de Gamboa and the hydro-oceanographic vessel (H/V) Galatea were used for offshore activities, including the deployment of OBS, air-gun shots for wide angle seismic refraction (WAS), multi-channel seismic (MCS) reflection surveys, magnetic surveys, and ROV (remotely operated vehicle) dives. The R/V Aegaeo performed additional MCS surveys during November 2014. TOMO-ETNA was performed within the framework of the EC-FP7 MED-SUV and EC-FP7 EUROFLEET2 (MEDSUV.ISES) projects and involved **24 partner institutions** (from Europe and America) and more than 80 researchers and technicians. Support was also extended by the national funding agencies of Italy, Spain, and Germany. In addition, the Italian Navy and Sicily's Regional Civil Protection Department actively participated in the experiment. To date, more than 24 peer-reviewed papers have been published, including a special issue of *Annals of Geophysics*; moreover, 4 doctoral theses and at least 12 MSc theses at Spanish and Italian institutions have been presented with the obtained data. The total budget of the experiment exceeded 1.2 M €. A representative example of relevant published work is as follows:

- Díaz-Moreno, A., Barberi, G., Cocina, O., Koulakov, I., Scarfi, L., Zuccarello, L., ... & Ibáñez, J. M. (2018). New insights on Mt. Etna's crust and relationship with the regional tectonic framework from joint active and passive P-wave seismic tomography. *Surveys in geophysics*, 39, 57-97.
- Ibáñez, J. M., Castro-Melgar, I., Cocina, O., Zuccarello, L., Branca, S., Del Pezzo, E., & Prudencio, J. (2020). First 2-D intrinsic and scattering attenuation images of Mt Etna volcano and surrounding region from active seismic data. *Geophysical Journal International*, 220(1), 267-277.

- Castro-Melgar, I., Prudencio, J., Del Pezzo, E., Giampiccolo, E., & Ibanez, J. M. (2021). Shallow magma storage beneath Mt. Etna: Evidence from new attenuation tomography and existing velocity models. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 126(7), e2021JB022094.

Machine learning using seismo-volcanic signals

I am a pioneer in the application of ML to seismo-volcanic signals. For two decades, I have maintained an agreement with the UGR Signal Processing research team, a world leader in speech recognition. To date, several joint doctoral theses have been presented (e.g., Cortés-2013, Gutiérrez-2015, Titos-2018, Bueno-2021); two more are in preparation (Rey-Devesa at UGR, Martínez at UNLP). More than 45 conference papers have been presented and more than 28 international peer-reviewed papers have been published. One of my PhD student was a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Fellow at the Università de Udine (Italy) and I was co-supervising a new Marie Skłodowska-Curie Fellow at UGR. My work has advanced the use of recurrent and Bayesian neural networks for automatic P and S-waves picking, signal segmentation and labelling, dimensional reduction algorithms, and more. Recently, via frequency analysis of seismic signals using Bayesian neural networks, we discovered a shift in the frequency index (i.e., the ratio of energy in low [1–5 Hz] and high [6–10 Hz] frequency windows) before and after an eruptive process at Mount St. Helens, providing new insight into the physical properties of the sources and medium. This research network has subsequently welcomed new researchers from around the world, including De Angelis (UK), Lesage (France), Carniel (Italy), Chouet and Dawson (USA), Del Pezzo (Italy), Bean (Ireland), De Hope (USA), Koulakov (Russia); Arambula (México), etc. As a consequence of this collaboration we are world leaders in this field, with an average of 8 peer-reviewed papers produced every year. Recently, I have been invited by the journal **Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences** to prepare a special review paper on the topic of ML on volcano seismology. In addition other relevant works are:

- Titos, M., Gutiérrez, L., Benítez, C., Rey Devesa, P., Koulakov, I., & Ibáñez, J. M. (2023). Multi-station volcano tectonic earthquake monitoring based on transfer learning. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 11, 1204832.
- Bueno-Rodríguez, Á., Balestrieri, R., De Angelis, S., Benítez, M. C., Zuccarello, L., Baraniuk, R., ... & de Hoop, M. V. (2021). Recurrent Scattering Network detects metastable behavior in polyphonic seismo-volcanic signals for volcano eruption forecasting. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 60, 1-23.
- Bueno, A., Titos, M., Benítez, C., & Ibáñez, J. M. (2021). Continuous active learning for seismo-volcanic monitoring. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, 19, 1-5.
- Bueno-Rodríguez, A., Benítez, C., Zuccarello, L., De Angelis, S., & Ibáñez, J. M. (2021). Bayesian monitoring of seismo-volcanic dynamics. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 60, 1-14.

- Titos, M., Bueno, A., García, L., Benítez, M. C., & Ibañez, J. (2018). Detection and classification of continuous volcano-seismic signals with recurrent neural networks. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 57(4), 1936-1948.

Understanding Physical processes of Volcanic Eruptions.

I worked to expand the knowledge of the physics of eruptive processes through different methods: seismic tomography in velocity and attenuation, analysis of the entropy of energy, or the relationship between eruptions and large earthquakes, among others. I highlight the recent work carried out in the La Palma eruption (2021) where, for the first time in the world, a three-dimensional image of the interior of the eruptive process was made in real time, that is, during the eruption itself. These tools have been applied to other eruptive scenarios such as Etna or El Hierro and to potential future scenarios such as Tenerife. Recent relevant works:

- Cabrera-Pérez, I., D'Auria, L., Soubestre, J., Przeor, M., Barrancos, J., García-Hernández, R., ... & Pérez, N. (2023). Spatio-temporal velocity variations observed during the pre-eruptive episode of La Palma 2021 eruption inferred from ambient noise interferometry. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 12039.
- Koulakov, I., D'Auria, L., Prudencio, J., Cabrera-Pérez, I., Barrancos, J., Padilla, G. D., ... & Ibañez, J. M. (2023). Local earthquake seismic tomography reveals the link between crustal structure and volcanism in Tenerife (Canary Islands). *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 128(3), e2022JB025798.
- Zuccarello, L., De Angelis, S., Minio, V., Saccorotti, G., Bean, C. J., Paratore, M., & Ibanez, J. M. (2022). Volcanic Tremor Tracks Changes in Multi-Vent Activity at Mt. Etna, Italy: Evidence From Analyses of Seismic Array Data. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 49(22), e2022GL100056.
- D'Auria, L., Koulakov, I., Prudencio, J., Cabrera-Pérez, I., Ibañez, J. M., Barrancos, J., ... & Peréz, N. M. (2022). Rapid magma ascent beneath La Palma revealed by seismic tomography. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1), 17654.
- Bretón, M., Ibañez, J. M., Leon, Z., Plascencia, I., Campos, A., Santiago, H., ... & De Angelis, S. (2022). Historical and morphological evidence for multi-stage growth of El Volcancito, Volcán de Colima. *Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, 421, 107447.

Forecasting volcanic eruptions.

Pioneer in the application of seismic signal analysis techniques (Shannon Entropy) to establish a universally valid tool in carrying out early warnings of volcanic eruptions. Currently the procedure is established in the Alaska Volcano Observatory as routine volcanic monitoring for all Alaska volcanoes (https://apps.avo.alaska.edu/volcano_seismology/). I propose the use of the Second Law of Thermodynamics and entropy, H, as an indicator of the equilibrium state of a volcanic active region (a seismic system). In this sense, I demonstrate the exportability of first principles (e.g., thermodynamics laws) to different scenarios suggesting that the relationship between increasing H and the occurrence of volcanic eruptions reflects the irreversible transition of a system. In the case of the use of the Shannon

Entropy (SE), I conclude that SE could be used as a complementary tool in seismic volcano monitoring, showing its successful behaviour prior to energetic eruptions, giving time enough to alert the population and prepare for the consequences of an imminent and well predicted moment of the eruption. Some relevant scientific works are:

- Rey-Devesa, P., Prudencio, J., Benítez, C., Bretón, M., Plasencia, I., León, Z., ... & Ibáñez, J. M. (2023). Tracking volcanic explosions using Shannon entropy at Volcán de Colima. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 9807.
- Rey-Devesa, P., Benítez, C., Prudencio, J., Gutiérrez, L., Cortés-Moreno, G., Titos, M., ... & Ibáñez, J. M. (2023). Volcanic Early Warning Using Shannon Entropy: Multiple Cases of Study. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, e2023JB026684.
- Posadas, A., Morales, J., Ibáñez, J. M., & Posadas-Garzon, A. (2021). Shaking earth: Non-linear seismic processes and the second law of thermodynamics: A case study from Canterbury (New Zealand) earthquakes. *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, 151, 111243.

Multidisciplinary research, international networking, and data sharing in volcanology

As leader of a multidisciplinary and international research team, I have worked on several volcanic scenarios involving various disciplines and approaches, and with researchers from multiple institutions and countries. In my published papers, the **number of authors is broadly reflective of the number of collaborating institutions**. I strongly believe in data sharing (raw and processed products). Example publications that highlight these endeavours are as follows:

Data Sharing

- Ibáñez, J.M., et al. (2017). Database of multi-parametric geophysical data from the TOMO-DEC experiment on Deception Island, Antarctica. *Nat. Sci. Data* 4, 170128, doi:10.1038/sdata.2017.128.

Seismic attenuation

- Castro-Melgar, I., et al. (2021). Shallow magma storage beneath Mt. Etna: Evidence from new attenuation tomography and existing velocity models. *J. Geophys. Res.* 10.1029/2021JB022094.

Source mechanisms

- Díaz-Moreno, A., et al. (2015). Seismic hydraulic fracture migration originated by successive deep magma pulses: The 2011–2013 seismic series associated to the volcanic activity of El Hierro Island. *J. Geophys. Res.* 120(11), 7749–7770. doi:10.1002/2015JB012249.

In addition I have published multidisciplinary articles, as the first author, or as a collaborator in works such as: Statistical analysis of volcanic seismicity and volcanic source models.

DETAILED ACADEMIC CURRICULUM

ACADEMIC POSITIONS.

- Subdirector del Instituto Andaluz de Geofísica de la Universidad de Granada, desde 13/05/1994 a 09/06/2000.
- Secretario del Instituto Andaluz de Geofísica de la Universidad de Granada, 10/06/2000 a 27/06/2008.
- Director del Instituto Andaluz de Geofísica de la Universidad de Granada, 28 de Junio de 2008 hasta 24 junio 2011.

SCHOLARSHIPS AND AID RECEIVED.

- Collaborating student scholarship (Ministry of Education and Science, INAPE) at the Cartuja University Observatory, in the years 1985-86, 1986-87.
- Scholarship holder of the Sectoral Scholarship Program for Teacher and Research Staff Training in Spain. National Geological Resources Plan. Realization, Department of Theoretical and Cosmos Physics, University of Granada. Years 1988, 1989, 1990.
- Aid for stays abroad for scholarship recipients of the Sectoral Scholarship Program for Training of Teachers and Research Personnel in Spain. Date: April-June, 1989. Place: Istituto Di Scienze della Terra. University of Catania. Italy.
- Aid for stays abroad for scholarship recipients of the Sectoral Scholarship Program for Training of Teachers and Research Personnel in Spain. Date: August-October, 1990. Place: Department of Earth and Planetary Sciences. HarvardUniversity. USA.
- Help from the Department of Education and Science. General Directorate of Universities and Research. Date: June-July, 1991. Place: Department of Earth and Planetary Sciences. HarvardUniversity. USA.

ACADEMIC POSITIONS AT THE UNIVERSITY OF GRANADA

Puesto	Institución	Fechas
BECARIO FPI	UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA	1988-1990
Profesor Titular Interino de Universidad en el área de conocimiento de Física de la Tierra, Astronomía y Astrofísica, en el Departamento de Física Teórica y del Cosmos.	UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA	1- Octubre 1990 – 30-Julio 1993.
Profesor Titular de Universidad. Area de conocimiento de Física de la Tierra	UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA	31 de Julio de 1993 – 27 de Julio de 2010

Catedrático de Universidad. Área de conocimiento de Física de la Tierra	UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA	28 de Julio 2010 – actualidad
---	------------------------	-------------------------------------

SEXENIOS Y QUINQUENIOS

Número de sexenos de investigación: 5. Último concedido 2020. Nueva fecha de solicitud Diciembre de 2025.

Número de quinquenios: 6 (Máximo posible). Último concedido 2018.

Tramos de Excelencia de la Junta de Andalucía: 5. Los máximos.

LANGUAGES

(R = fair, B = good, C = correctly)

Spanish. Mother tongue.

English, Speak (C), Read (C), Write (C)

Italian, Speak (C), Read (C), Write (C)

French, Speak (R), Read (B), Write (R)

Basic Portuguese

MANAGEMENT AND RESPONSIBILITY POSITIONS

- Responsible for the Teaching Area of the Andalusian Institute of Geophysics and Prevention of Seismic Disasters 1992-2000.

- Member of the Doctoral Commission of the University of Messina. Italy, 2000.

- Member of the Board of Directors of the Department of Theoretical Physics and Cosmos. University of Granada. 10/11/1995 to 07/20/2000, and 10/03/2005 to 06/16/2008

- Deputy director of the Andalusian Institute of Geophysics of the University of Granada, from 05/13/1994 to 06/09/2000.

- Secretary of the Andalusian Institute of Geophysics of the University of Granada, 06/10/2000 to 06/27/2008.

- Director of the Andalusian Institute of Geophysics of the University of Granada, June 28, 2008 until June 24, 2012.

- Honorary Associate Member of the Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanología, Italy, from June 2012 to the present.

SCHOLAR AND RESEARCH STAYS IN FOREIGN CENTERS OR OUTSIDE THE UGR (continuous stays longer than one month)

1- Base antártica argentina de Decepción, Antártida, Campaña antártica 1987-88. Enero - Marzo de 1988.

2- Istituto di Scienze della Terra. Universidad de Catania, Italia, Abril - Junio de 1989.

3- Istituto di Scienze della Terra. Universidad de Catania, Italia, 30 Octubre - Diciembre de 1989.

4- Department of Earth and Planetary Sciences. Harvard University, Cambridge,

Mass, USA. Agosto - Octubre de 1990.

5- Dipartimento di Fisica. Università di Salerno. Salerno, Italia. Enero - Febrero de 1991.

6- Department of Earth and Planetary Sciences. Harvard University, Cambridge, Mass, USA. Julio - Septiembre 1991.

7- Dipartimento di Fisica. Università di Salerno. Salerno, Italia. Octubre - Diciembre de 1991.

8- Instituto de Geofísica. Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México. México. Enero - Marzo, 1992.

9- Tokio Institute of Technology. Japón, Marzo de 1992.

10- Dipartimento di Física. Università di Salerno. Salerno, Italia. Octubre-Noviembre de 1992.

11- Dipartimento di Física. Università di Salerno. Salerno, Italia. Octubre-Noviembre de 1993.

12- Geophysical Engineering Department. Dokuz Eylul Universitesi. Izmir, Turquía, Febrero-Marzo 1994.

13- Refugio español Gabriel de Castilla (E.T.), Isla Decepción, Antártida. Diciembre 1994 - Marzo 1995.

14- Base Antártica Española Gabriel de Castilla (E.T.), Isla Decepción, Antártida. Diciembre 1996 - Enero 1997.

15- Base Antártica Española Gabriel de Castilla (E.T.), Isla Decepción, Antártida. Diciembre 1998 - Marzo 1999.

16- Observatorio vulcanológico. Universidad de Colima. Colima. México. Julio de 2000

17- Department of Geology. University College of Dublin. Irlanda. Agosto 2000.

18- Base Antártica Española Gabriel de Castilla (E.T.), Isla Decepción, Antártida. Diciembre 2001 - Febrero 2002.

20- Base Antártica Española Gabriel de Castilla (E.T.), Isla Decepción, Antártida. Diciembre 2002 - Enero 2003.

21- Universidad de Colima. Facultad de Ingeniería Civil. Colima. México. Enero de 2004.

22- Universidad de Colima. Facultad de Ingeniería Civil. Colima. México. Septiembre de 2005.

23- Buque Hespérides, campaña 2004-2005. Enero 2005.

24- Universidad de Colima. Facultad de Ingeniería Civil. Colima. México. Diciembre de 2006.

25- Universidad de Colima. Facultad de Ingeniería Civil. Colima. México. Marzo de 2008.

26- Geological Department. University College of Dublin, July-August, 2008.

27- Universidad de Colima. Facultad de Ingeniería Civil. Colima. México. Febrero de 2009.

28- Universidad Nacional de La Plata, Argentina, Profesor Visitante invitado. Junio 2011.

29- Profesor invitado por el INGV, Italia, Catania, Junio de 2013.

30- Profesor invitado por el INGV, Italia, Napoles, Diciembre de 2013.

31- Universidad Nacional de La Plata, Argentina. Profesor Visitante invitado. Junio 2018.

- 32- Geological Department, University of Cork, Ireland, July-August, 2019
 2022 33- Departamento de Química y Física, Universidad de Almeria, Almeria, Spain, Julio
 2023 34- Departamento de Química y Física, Universidad de Almeria, Almeria, Spain, Julio

(Less than 1 month, listing)

- Dipartimento de Física, Università di Salerno, Italia.
 Osservatorio Vesuviano, Napoli, Italia.
 Dipartimento di Geologia, Università di Catania, Italia.
 Osservatorio sismologico, Università di Messina, Italia.
 Dipartimento di Fisica, Università di Salerno, Italia.
 Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica, Roma, Italia.
 Observatorio de la Universidad Nacional de La Plata, Argentina.
 Base Antártica Española Gabriel de Castilla (E.T.), Isla Decepción, Antártida.
 Universidad de Bergen, Noruega.
 Universidad de Dublín, Irlanda.
 Universidad de Strasbourg, Francia
 Universidad de Washington, Seattle, USA.
 Universidad do Acores, Portugal.
 USGS, Menlo Park, USA.
 Berkeley University, USA.
 Instituto de Geofísica de Perú. Arequipa, Perú.
 Centro de Estudios Volcanológicos, Universidad de Colima, México
 Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia, Pisa, Italy
 School of Environmental Sciences, University of Liverpool, Liverpool, UK
 Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies, Dublin, Ireland
 Department of Computational and Applied Mathematics, Rice University, Houston,
 USA.

PARTICIPATION IN INTERNATIONAL AND PRESTIGIOUS COMMITTEES AND REPRESENTATIONS.

- Reviewer of professional journals:
 Geophysical Journal International, Terra Antarctica, Annali di Geofisica, Journal of Geophysical Research, Bulletin of the Seismological American Society, Geophysical Res. Letters, Journal Volcanology and Geothermal Research, Bulletin of Volcanology, Physic. EarthPlanet. Int., PAGEOPHS, Phys. Earth. Planet. Sciences, Godwana Research, Surveys in Geophysics, Geophy. Journal. Int.
- Editor of a special volume in Pageophs, 1995.
- Editor of the Annals of Geophysics Magazine. From 2009 to 2014.
- Guest editor of Geosciences Magazine 2016 to the present.
- Member of the Jury of the King Jaime I Award for Environmental Protection 2016,
 2017.
- Project reviewer for the Grupo Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia (Italy).
- Project reviewer for The New Zealand Antarctic Institute (New Zealand).

- Project evaluator for the Scientific and Technological Promotion Agency. Calls for the years 2005, 2006, 2007, 2008, 2009, 2011.
- ANEP project evaluator. Years 2005, 2006, 2009, 2010, 2011, 2014, 2015.
- Project evaluator at the Universiteit Gent in Belgium, year 1997.
- Irish Government project evaluator. Year 2006.
- NATO project evaluator, “Advanced Study Institutes Programme”, year 1997.
- EU Project Evaluator, 7FP, Research European Agency, Marie Curie Actions, ITN, IEF, IOF, IIF, IAAP, CIG. Year 2010, 2011, 2012, 2013.
- ViceChair in the EU Marie Curie programs, 7FP, year 2013.
- EU Evaluator, H2020 program, ITN programs, Individual Fellowships, MSC actions. 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017.
- EU ViceChair, H2020/Horizon Europe programme, ITN/DN programme, MSC actions. 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2021.
- EU Evaluator, H2020 program, Individual Fellowships, MSC actions. 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023.
- EU ViceChair, H2020 programme, Individual Fellowships, MSC actions. 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2023.
- EU Chair, H2020/Horizon Europe programme, Individual Fellowships, MSC actions. 2020, 2021, 2022,
- Vice Chair and Quality Checker Vice Chair in other Horizon Europe programs such as Steal and Aoal Staff Exange, Widera, 2022, 2023.
- Project evaluator of the Agence Nationale de la Recherche of France, year 2012.
- Project evaluator for the Research Promotion Foundation of Cyprus, 2013.
- Project evaluator of the Fonds National de la Recherche Luxemburg, year 2016, 2017.
- Project evaluator of the Netherlands Organization for Scientific Research, year 2016.
- External evaluator of the Athena Swan Bronze Awards, University of Liverpool, year, 2016.
- External evaluator of U.S. contracts. Geological Survey, year 2013.
- Member of the American Geophysical Union.
- Member of the American Seismological Society.
- Member of the Spanish Geophysical Instrumentation Group.
- Member of the Geophysical Research Group in Andalusia.
- Member of the Royal Spanish Society of Physics.
- Member of the International ANTEC group (Antarctic neotectonics). Scientific Cometees on Antarctic Research.
- Member of the National Commission of Volcanology (National Commission of Geodesy and Geophysics) from May 1, 1999 to September 2010.
- Member of the Plenary of the Spanish Commission of Geodesy and Geophysics.
- Secretary of the Spanish Volcanological Association.
- Member of the advisory group of the Deception volcanic Observatory. South Shetland Islands, Antarctica. 1993-present.
- Advisor to the Civil Protection Service of the Junta de Andalucía. From January 1, 2000 to the present.
- Scientific advisor to the Granada Science Park. From January 1, 2000 to the present.
- Member of the Scientific Advisory Committee for the Colima Fire Volcano of Civil Protection. States of Jalisco and Colima. November 2004- Present.
- Scientific collaborator of ITER. Tenerife. Spain. From 2006 to 2011.

- Evaluator of the Grieg research program of the Polish government, NATIONAL SCIENCE CENTRE. 2020.
- Evaluator of the Czech Academic of Science, 2020, 2021. Czech Government.
- Evaluator, Chair, the Polish government's Evaluation Panel National Science Center, Poland program, NATIONAL SCIENCE CENTRE. 2021.
- Member (March 10, 2021) of the Volcanology Section of the Spanish Commission of Geodesy and Geophysics.

TEACHING ACTIVITY

REGULATED TEACHINGS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF GRANADA.

- Prácticas de laboratorio de Física General para 1) de E.T.S. en la Facultad de Ciencias de la Universidad de Granada. Curso 1988-89. 2 horas semanales.
- Laboratorio de Física General para ingenieros de Caminos Canales y Puertos de la Universidad de Granada. Curso 1989-90. 4 horas semanales.
- Laboratorio de Física General para Biólogos. Facultad de Ciencias. Universidad de Granada Curso 1990-91. 8 horas semanales.
- Laboratorio de Física General para Biólogos. Facultad de Ciencias. Universidad de Granada Curso 1991-92. 8 horas semanales.
- Curso de doctorado "Atenuación de ondas sísmicas", programa "sismología", Departamento de Física Teórica y del Cosmos, bienios 1991-92 y 1992-93, 3 créditos.
- Laboratorio de Física General para Biólogos. Facultad de Ciencias. Universidad de Granada Curso 1992-93. 8 horas semanales.
- Física para ingenieros de Caminos, Canales y Puertos. Universidad de Granada. Año 1993. 8 horas semanales.
- Laboratorio de Física General para Biólogos. Facultad de Ciencias. Universidad de Granada Curso 1993-94. 8 horas semanales.
- Física para Biólogos. Curso 1994-95, 1995-96, 1996-97.
- ATENUACION SISMICA. SISMOLOGIA E INGENIERIA SISMICA (Doctorado). 1995-96.
- SISMICIDAD. SISMOLOGIA E INGENIERIA SISMICA (Doctorado). 1995-96.
- Geofísica para Geólogos. Curso 1997-98, 1998-99.
- ANALISIS NUMERICO. GEOFISICA, ASTROFISICA Y PARTICULAS (Doctorado). 1998-99.
- ATENUACION SISMICA. GEOFISICA, ASTROFISICA Y PARTICULAS (Doctorado). 1998-99.
- SISMICIDAD VOLCANICA. GEOFISICA, ASTROFISICA Y PARTICULAS (Doctorado). 1999-00.
- Geofísica. Licenciatura de Geológicas, plan nuevo. Cursos 1998-99, 1999-2000, 2000-2001, 2001-2002.
- Laboratorio de Física General para Geólogos. Facultad de Ciencias. Universidad de Granada Curso 1997-98.
- Sismología. Libre configuración. Curso 1998-99, 1999-2000, 2000-2001, 2001-2002
- Física II. Licenciatura de Geológicas. Curso 1999-2000.
- Física. Licenciatura de Geológicas. Curso 2000-2001, 2001-2002, 2002-2003, 2003-2004, 2004-2005, 2005-2006, 2006-2007, 2007-2008, 2008-2009, 2009-2010.
- Física de Volcanes, Libre configuración. Cursos 2003-2004, 2004-2005. 2005-2006,

2006-2007, 2007-2008, 2008-2009, 2009-2010, 2010-2011, 2011-2012, 2012-2013.

- Vigilancia de volcanes activos. Curso de doctorado de Ciencias de la Tierra, Universidad de Granada. Curso 2005-2006, 2006-2007, 2007-2008, 2008-2009.

- Sismicidad volcánica. Curso de doctorado de Geofísica y Meteorología, Universidad de Granada. Curso 2005-2006.

- Geofísica volcánica y flujo geotérmico. Master de Calidad Geofísica y Meteorología. Universidad de Granada. Curso 2006-2007, 2007-2008, 2008-2009, 2009-2010.

- Riesgos sísmicos, climáticos y volcánicos. Master de Calidad Ciencias de la Tierra. Universidad de Granada. Curso 2007-2008.

- Riesgo Sísmico. Master de Calidad Geología, Universidad de Granada. Curso 2008-2009.

- Física. Grado en Ciencias Ambientales. Curso 2010-2011,

- Geofísica volcánica y flujo geotérmico. Master GEOMET, Desde curso 2009 hasta la actualidad.

- Riesgos sísmicos, climáticos y volcánicos. Master GEOMET, Desde curso 2009 hasta la actualidad.

- Riesgos sísmicos, climáticos y volcánicos. Máster Universitario en Profesorado de Enseñanza Secundaria Obligatoria y Bachillerato, Formación Profesional y Enseñanzas de Idiomas (Doctorado). Curso 2016-2017, 2017-2018, 2018-2019.

- Recursos Geotérmicos. Master GEOREC, desde 2011 hasta la actualidad.

- Geofísica. Licenciado en Física. Curso 2012-2013, 2013-2014.

- Física. Graduado en Ingeniería Civil. Curso 2014-2015, 2015-2016.

- Geofísica. Graduado en Física, Curso 2016-2017, 2017-2018, 2018-2019, 2019-2020, 2020-2021, 2021-2022, 2022-2023, 2023-2024.

NON-REGULATED TEACHINGS OR FROM OTHER UNIVERSITIES.

- Profesor invitado del Curso de sismología de la Licenciatura de geología y de la de Física de la Facultad de Ciencias de la Universidad de Catania, Italia, durante el mes de Noviembre de 1989. 2 horas diarias.

- Sismicidad del Sud Della Spaga. Università di Catania. Istituto di Scienze della Terra. Catania. Italia. 4-6 Mayo 1989.

- Attenuazione ed onde di coda. Università di Catania. Istituto di Scienze della Terra. Catania. Italia. 25-27 Mayo 1989.

- Sismicidad del Sud della Spagna. Università degli Studi di Salerno. Dipartimento de Fisica. Salerno, Italia. 6-7 Junio 1989.

- Calcolo del Fattore di Qualità. Università degli Studi di Salerno. Dipartimento de Fisica. Salerno, Italia. 6-7 Junio 1989.

- Profesor de prácticas del Seminario "Ondas Coda", organizado por el Instituto Andaluz de Geofísica y el Departamento de Física Teórica y del Cosmos, del 23 al 27 de Octubre de 1989.

- Attenuazione delle onde Lg nel Bacino di Granada. Università degli Studi di Salerno. Dipartimento de Fisica. Salerno, Italia. 16-20 Noviembre 1989.

- Attenuazione dell onde Lg nel bacino di Granada. Università di Catania. Istituto di Scienze della Terra. Catania. Italia. 21 de Noviembre de 1989.

- Seismicity, seismic attenuation and response of Southern Spain. Universitetet i Bergen. Institute of Solid Earth Physics. Bergen. Noruega. 1-3 Junio de 1991.

- Eventi sismici profondi anomali. Università degli Studi di Salerno. Dipartimento de Fisica. Salerno, Italia. 31 de Enero de 1991.
- Struttura del Mantello terreste. Università degli Studi di Salerno. Dipartimento de Fisica. Salerno, Italia. 4 de Febrero de 1991.
- Eterogenità del mantello e flusso convettivo terrestre. Università degli Studi di Salerno. Dipartimento de Fisica. Salerno, Italia. 5 de Febrero de 1991.
- Sismicidad, atenuación y efectos de sitio en Granada, España. Centro Nacional de Prevención de Desastres. México D.F., México. 13 de Febrero de 1992.
- Terremotos profundos localizados fuera de las zonas de subducción. Instituto de Geofísica. UNAM. México D.F., México. 20 de Febrero de 1992.
- Atenuación y efectos de sitio en la Depresión de Granada. Instituto de Geofísica. UNAM. México D.F., México. 28 de Febrero de 1992.
- Attenuazione ed onde di coda. Università degli Studi di Salerno. Dipartimento de Fisica. Salerno, Italia. 10-14 de Noviembre de 1992.
- Profesor en los "Programas de Postgrado y Doctorado en Ingeniería Sísmica y Dinámica Estructural" del Departamento de Ingeniería del Terreno y Cartográfica de la Universidad Politécnica de Cataluña. Noviembre de 1991, Julio de 1992 y Septiembre de 1992.
- Profesor del curso "Prevención Sísmica", organizado por el Centro de Enseñanzas Propias de la Universidad de Granada y el Instituto Andaluz de Geofísica. Enero de 1993.
- Sismicidad volcánica. Università degli Studi di Salerno. Dipartimento de Fisica. Salerno, Italia. 6-10 Octubre 1993.
- Attenuazione sismica. Università degli Studi di Salerno. Dipartimento de Fisica. Salerno, Italia. 14-16 Octubre 1993.
- Profesor en la VIII edición del **Curso Internacional de volcanología y Geofísica Volcánica**. Con los seminarios "Sismicidad volcánica I", Sismicidad Volcánica II" e "Instrumentación sísmica". Lanzarote Octubre-Noviembre 1995.
- Wave attenuation in the Mediterranean. Ecole et Observatoire de Physique du Globe. Université Pasteur. Strasbourg. Francia. 18 de Enero de 1996.
- Profesor en la IX edición del **Curso Internacional de volcanología y Geofísica Volcánica**. Con los seminarios "Sismicidad volcánica I", Sismicidad Volcánica II" e "Instrumentación sísmica". Lanzarote Octubre-Noviembre 1996.
- Presentación y análisis preliminar de los datos de campañas antárticas. Departamento de Física Aplicada. Universidad de Almería. Almería. España. 18-21 de Abril de 1997.
- Profesor en la X edición del **Curso Internacional de volcanología y Geofísica Volcánica**. Con los seminarios "Sismicidad volcánica I", Sismicidad Volcánica II" e "Instrumentación sísmica". Lanzarote Octubre-Noviembre 1997.
- Profesor en la XI edición del **Curso Internacional de volcanología y Geofísica Volcánica**. Con los seminarios "Sismicidad volcánica I", Sismicidad Volcánica II" e "Instrumentación sísmica". Lanzarote Octubre-Noviembre 1998.
- Profesor en la XII edición del **Curso Internacional de volcanología y Geofísica Volcánica**. Con los seminarios "Sismicidad volcánica I", Sismicidad Volcánica II" e "Instrumentación sísmica". Lanzarote Octubre-Noviembre 1999.
- Atenuación sísmica en ambientes volcánicos. Observatorio vulcanológico. Universidad de Colima. Colima. México. 4-6 Julio de 2000.
- Profesor en la XIII edición del **Curso Internacional de volcanología y Geofísica Volcánica**. Con los seminarios "Sismicidad volcánica I", Sismicidad Volcánica II" e "Instrumentación sísmica". Lanzarote Octubre-Noviembre 2000.

- Profesor invitado del Master de Física de la Tierra y Astronomía. Universidad de La Plata. La Plata. Argentina. Cursos académico 1999-2000.
- Profesor del “Mestrado de Vulcanología e Riscos Geológicos da Universidade Dos Açores”, en la disciplinas de “Monitorización sísmica y sismología volcánica”, Marzo, 2001.
- Antenas sísmicas y su aplicación a la sismología volcánica. Observatorio vulcanológico. Universidad de Colima. Colima. México. 20 Junio de 2001.
- Profesor en la XIV edición del **Curso Internacional de vulcanología y Geofísica Volcánica**. Con los seminarios "Sismicidad volcánica I", Sismicidad Volcánica II" e "Instrumentación sísmica". Lanzarote Octubre-Noviembre 2001.
- Profesor del “Mestrado de Vulcanología e Riscos Geológicos da Universidade Dos Açores”, en la disciplinas de “Monitorización sísmica y sismología volcánica”, Mayo, 2002.
- Profesor en la XV edición del **Curso Internacional de vulcanología y Geofísica Volcánica**. Con los seminarios "Sismicidad volcánica I", Sismicidad Volcánica II" e "Instrumentación sísmica". Lanzarote Octubre-Noviembre 2002.
- Profesor invitado en la Maestría de Ciencias de la Tierra. Asignatura “Sismología Volcánica”. Postgrado oficial de la Universidad de Colima. Facultad de Ingeniería Civil. Colima. México. Enero de 2004.
- Sismicidad volcánica. Departamento de Ciencias Geológicas. Facultad de Ciencias Exactas y Naturales. Universidad de Buenos Aires. Buenos Aires. Argentina. 15-16 de Noviembre de 2004.
- Profesor invitado en la Maestría de Ciencias de la Tierra. Asignatura “Riesgo Volcánico”. Postgrado oficial de la Universidad de Colima. Facultad de Ingeniería Civil. Colima. México. Septiembre de 2005.
- Profesor invitado del Master de Física de la Tierra y Astronomía. Universidad de La Plata. La Plata. Argentina. Cursos académico 2005-2006.
- Tendencias actuales de la Sismología Volcánica. X Reunión Internacional del Volcán de Colima. Observatorio Vulcanológico. Universidad de Colima. Colima. México. 16 de Febrero de 2006.
- Profesor invitado en la Maestría de Ciencias de la Tierra. Asignatura “Fundamentos y usos de las antenas sísmicas en vulcanología”. Postgrado oficial de la Universidad de Colima. Facultad de Ingeniería Civil. Colima. México. Diciembre de 2006.
- Vulcanismo y sismicidad en la Antártida. Fundación UCEIF. Universidad de Cantabria. Santander. España. 26 de Abril de 2007.
- Vulcanismo y sismicidad en la isla Decepción. Fundación Ciudad de las Artes y las Ciencias. Ciudad de las Artes y las Ciencias. Valencia. España. 15 de Mayo de 2007.
- Profesor del 8º curso de actualidad científica “En Torno al Titanic” con el curso “Explorando la Antártida”. Parque de las Ciencias. 24 de Octubre de 2007.
- Profesor invitado en la Maestría de Ciencias de la Tierra. Asignatura “Nuevas tendencias de la sismología volcánica”. Postgrado oficial de la Universidad de Colima. Facultad de Ingeniería Civil. Colima. México. Marzo de 2008.
- Profesor de las “Jornadas sobre espacio europeo de educación superior e innovación docente” con el trabajo “Evaluación de la comprensión lectora en estudiantes universitarios de Ciencias Experimentales”. Universidad de Jaén. 4-5 de Junio de 2008.
- Profesor invitado en la Maestría de Ciencias de la Tierra. Asignatura “Análisis de array para el seguimiento de señales volcánicas”. Postgrado oficial de la Universidad de Colima. Facultad de Ingeniería Civil. Colima. México. Febrero de 2009.
- Tomography of active volcanoes. XI Reunión Internacional del Volcán de Colima. Observatorio Vulcanológico. Universidad de Colima. Colima. México. 2 de Febrero de 2009.

- Profesor curso “La homologación de las asignaturas de Geofísica Volcánica en diferentes universidades y niveles de grado y post-grado”. Departamento de Ciencias Geológicas. Universidad de Buenos Aires. Buenos Aires. Argentina. 3-4 de Marzo de 2009.
- Volcanismo y sismicidad en la Antártida. Parque de las Ciencias. Granada. España. 31 de marzo de 2009.
- High definition seismic tomography of active volcanic island using active and passive experiments. Keynote lecture. Cities on Volcanoes 6. IAVCEI. Puerto de la Cruz. Tenerife, 31 Mayo-4 Junio 2010.
- Atenuación Sísmica. Curso de Postgrado en el Doctorado en Geofísica. Universidad Nacional de La Plata, Argentina. Profesor Visitante invitado. Junio 2011.
- Profesor invitado por el INGV, Italia, en el curso VULCAMED de postgrado. Asignatura “Elementos de Sismología”. 30 horas. Catania, 12-18 de Junio de 2013.
- Profesor invitado por el INGV, Italia, en el curso VULCAMED de postgrado. Asignatura “Sismología volcánica”, “Tomografía Sísmica de Volcanes activos”. 40 horas. Napoles, 12-20 de Diciembre de 2013.
- Nuevos avances y Técnicas de Estudio en Sismología Volcánica. Curso de Postgrado en el Doctorado en Geofísica. Universidad Nacional de La Plata, Argentina. Profesor Visitante invitado. Junio 2018.

DIRECTED THESES

- “Seismic attenuation at the Irno Valley, Salerno, Italy”. Alessandro Sorgente. Tesi sperimentale in Fisica. Università degli studi di Salerno. Salerno. Italia. 1991.
- “Studio della risposta di sito in due differenti contesti geologici: il vulcano Etna e il Bacino di Granada”. Elisabetta Giampiccolo. Tesi Sperimentale in Geologia. Correlatore. 1993
- “Análisis de señales sismo-volcánicas mediante técnicas de array”. Francisco Javier Almendros González. Tesis doctoral. Universidad de Granada. 22 De Enero de 1999. Sobresaliente Cum Laude. Co-director.
- “Contribuição para a monitorização sísmica de um sistema vulcânico activo- sete cidades, Sao Miguel, Açores”. Ulisses Barata. Tesis. Universidade dos Açores. Portugal. 3 – Octubre 2003.
- “Estructura superficial de atenuación para ondas sísmicas directas, P y S, en ambientes volcánicos. Aplicación al volcán Isla Decepción (Antártida) y volcán Etna (Italia). Carmen Martínez Arévalo. 22 de Junio de 2005. Sobresaliente Cum Laude por unanimidad.
- “Contribuição para o estudo da geometria da fonte sísmica nos Açores. Aplicação a crise do Faial de 1998”. Eva Góngora González. Tesis. Universidade dos Açores. Portugal. Septiembre 2005
- “Evolución, diseño y desarrollo de antenas sísmicas. Las antenas del Gran Sasso, del Vesubio y las nuevas antenas sísmicas portátiles del Instituto Andaluz de Geofísica. Aplicación a zonas tectónicas y volcánicas”. Miguel Abril Martí. Sobresaliente cum laude por

Unanimidad. 4 Julio 2007

“Passive and active seismic tomography of volcanic islands: Sao Miguel (Portugal and Deception (Antarctica). Daria Zandomenghi. Sobresaliente cum laude por Unanimidad. 20 Julio 2007

“Estudo de senais sísmicos associados a sistemas vulcânicos activos na região dos Açores”. Tesis. Dina Silveira. Universidade dos Açores. Portugal. Sobresaliente. 21 de Noviembre de 2008.

“Análisis de señales sísmicas de explosión del Volcán de Colima, registradas en el periodo octubre 2005 a Abril de 2006, utilizando técnicas de arrays sísmicos y de polarización”. Mara Cisneros. Tesis en Ciencias de la Tierra, especialidad en vulcanología. Sobresaliente. Universidad de Colima, México. Enero de 2009.

“Resultados inicial del estudio de la atenuación sísmica de ondas P para la isla de Tenerife”. Janire Prudencio Sónora. Máster en Geofísica y Meteorología, Universidad de Granada, Granada, España. Directores Jesús M. Ibáñez y Araceli García-Yeguas. Febrero 2009. Sobresaliente.

“Análisis de las propiedades del campo de onda de las explosiones volcánicas del Volcán de Colima, México.” Justo Orozco Rojas. Geofísica y Meteorología, Universidad de Granada, Granada, España. Director Jesús M. Ibáñez. Febrero 2009. Sobresaliente.

“Caracterización de sistemas de fractura mediante la localización relativa de terremotos tectónicos y volcánicos usando métodos clásicos y técnicas de array”. Enrique Carmona Rodríguez. Sobrealiente Cum Laude por unanimidad. Octubre 2009.

“Estudio de heterogeneidades laterales de volcanes activos: Tomografía sísmica de alta resolución de la isla de Tenerife, anomalías de propagación de ondas sísmicas de la isla Decepción y otros efectos.” M^a Araceli García Yeguas, 28 de Septiembre de 2010. Sobresaliente cum laude por Unanimidad.

“Atenuación sísmica en la región de Nuevo Cuyo”. Gabriela Alejanda Badi. Universidad Nacional de La Plata. Argentina. 12 de Julio de 2011. Sobresaliente cum laude por Unanimidad.

“From 2D to 3D attenuation tomography in volcanoes. The study of Tenerife (Canary Islands) and Deception Island (Antarctica)”. Janire Prudencio Sónora. 13 de Septiembre de 2013. Universidad de Granada. Doctorado en Ciencias de la Tierra. Apto cum laude. Doctorado internacional.

“Sistema de detección y clasificación de señales sísmico-volcánicas utilizando modelos ocultos de Markov (HMMs): Aplicación a volcanes activos de Nicaragua e Italia.” Ligdamis Gutiérrez Espinoza. 20 de Septiembre de 2013. Universidad de Granada. Doctorado en Ciencias de la Tierra. Apto cum laude.

“Reconocimiento de señales sismo-volcánicas mediante canales específicos basados en modelos ocultos de Markov”. Guillermo Cortés Moreno. 18 de Diciembre de 2015. Universidad de Granada. Doctorado en Ciencias de la Tierra. Apto cum laude.

“Estudio de la sismicidad volcano-tectónica del volcán Copahue, Cordillera Neuquina-Argentina, 2003-2010. Evidencias de reactivación del sistema.” Cintia Lorena Bengoa. Mayo 2016. Universidad de Buenos Aires. Área de Ciencias Geológicas, Buenos Aires. Argentina.

“Joint active and passive seismic tomography in active volcanoes: The case of study of Mt. Etna, and further implications in active volcanic regions”. Alejandro Díaz Moreno, 21 de Octubre de 2016. Universidad de Granada. Doctorado en Ciencias de la Tierra. Sobresaliente cum laude.

Bayesian transfer learning for continuous monitoring of active volcanoes. Bueno Rodríguez, Á. (17 septiembre de 2021). Universidad de Granada. Apto cum laude. Directores: Carmen Benítez y Jesús M. Ibáñez.

Castro Melgar, Ignacio. Directores Jesús M. Ibáñez y Janire Prudencio. Título: MODELOS ESTRUCTURALES DE VELOCIDAD Y ATENUACIÓN SÍSMICA EN ZONAS VOLCÁNICAS ACTIVAS Programa de Doctorado en Ciencias de la Tierra, Universidad de Granada. 08/07/2022 Sobresaliente y Mención de Doctorado Internacional

In preparation

Verónica Martínez. Directores Gabriela Badi y Jesús M. Ibáñez. Universidad Nacional de La Plata. Argentina.

Ricardo Centeno Quirico. Director Jesús M. Ibáñez. Instituto Geofísico de Perú. Universidad de Arequipa/Universidad de Granada.

TEACHING INNOVATION PROJECTS

- 1.- Red Temática AECI “Vigilando Volcanes Activos”. Coordinador. Participantes Universidad de La Laguna, Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Universidad de Colima, Universidad de Buenos Aires, Universidad de Costa Rica. 01/01/2003 – 31/12/2005. Investigador Responsable.
- 2.- “Evaluación de la comprensión lectora en Ciencias Experimentales”. Universidad de Granada. Coordinador Dr. Antonio Segura Carretero. 2009.
- 3.- “Desarrollo de un sistema integrado de adquisición y procesamiento de datos sísmicos para su aplicación a la enseñanza de la Geofísica”. Universidad de Granada. Coordinadora Dra. Inmaculada Serrano Bermejo. 2009-2010
- 4.- UGR-ID12-47: Virtual platform for Seismic hazard assessment (PI: Inmaculada Serrano)
- 5.- UGR-ID15-47: Adquisición y tratamiento de datos de los satélites Goce y Grace: aplicación en la docencia de la Geofísica (PI: Inmaculada Serrano)

DETAILED RESEARCH CURRICULUM

PARTICIPATION IN R&D PROJECTS FINANCED IN PUBLIC CALLS.

AS PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR.

1. - "Investigación en geofísica básica en la Base Antártica Española Juan Carlos I: sismología y geodinámica en las Shetland del Sur", CICYT, ANT94-0854-C02-02. **Investigador Principal. 1994-1995. 89.000,00 €**

2.- "Volcanismo, sismicidad, magnetismo y geodinámica de las Shetland del Sur: Estaciones sísmicas en la BAE (Livingston)", CICYT, ANT95-0994-C03-02. **Investigador Principal. 1995-1998. 124.619,90 €**

3.- "Sismicidad volcánica, local y regional del área de las Shetland del Sur y Estrecho de Bransfield (Antártida). ANT98-1111. **Investigador Principal. 1998-2001. 188.513,50 €**

4.- "Study and constraints on intermediate storage, magma uprise and conduits through modelling of strain fields, velocity and attenuation tomography at Mt. Etna". GNV Italia, 2000-2002. **Investigador responsable unidad 7. 35.000 €.**

5.- "e-Ruption. A satellite telecommunication and Internet-bases seismic monitoring system for volcanic eruption forecasting and risk management.". EU. EVR1-2001-00024. **Investigador responsable. 2002-2005. 305.716,00 €**

6.- "Creación de una base de datos sísmicos de la Isla Decepción (Antártida). REN2000-2908-E. Acción Especial. 2000-2001. **35.000,00 € Investigador responsable.**

5.- "DEC-SISM2001. Estudios sísmicos, magnéticos y de flujo de CO₂ en la Isla Decepción (Antártida), campaña 2001-2002.", REN2000-2897, **2011-2003. 45.000 €. Acción especial. Investigador responsable.**

6.- "TOMODEC. Tomografía sísmica de alta resolución de la Isla Decepción (Antártida) y modelización de la fuentes sismo-volcánica.", REN2001-3833. **Investigador responsable. 2001-2005. 346.919,80 €**

7.- Red Temática AECI "Vigilando volcanes activos", n 00481; C/1019/03. **2003-2005. 20.000 €**

8.- "E-ruption. Solicitud de dotación adicional para campañas sísmicas de campo en el Teide, Azores y la Isla Reunión", REN2002-10640-E/RIES. **35.000 €. Investigador Principal.**

9.- "Sismicidad volcánica del Teide: Tomografía de alta resolución usando datos sísmicos activos y pasivos. TOM-TEIDEVS", CGL2004-05744-C04-01. **Investigador principal. 2004-2007. 224.250,00 €**

10.- "Actuación de urgencia ante la reactivación sísmica del Teide: estaciones sísmicas y magnéticas", CGL2004-2001-E. **Investigador principal. 2005. 21.000 €**

11.- "AYU-TOMODEC: Solicitud de dotación adicional al proyecto TOMODEC para la realización de una campaña antártica". CGL2004-2002-E. **Investigador principal. 2005. 25.000 €**

12.-"SIS-VOLTEDEC: Monitorización sismo-volcánica, estructura superficial y modelo cortical de la isla Decepción (Antártida)". CGL2005-07589-C03-02/ANT. **Investigador principal. 2005-2008. 92.820,00 €**

13.-"Volcanoes: Understanding subsurface mass movement; VOLUME". UE, FP6-2004-Global-3-018471. **Investigador principal. 2005-2009. 245.000,00 €**

14.-"Modelos Sísmicos De Alta Resolución De Volúmenes Sismogénéticos De Volcanes Activos, Islas De Tenerife Y Decepción, Y Su Impacto En La Valoración Del

Peligro Volcánico. HISS”. CGL2008-01660. **Investigador Principal. 2009-2011. 284.713,00 €**

15.- “Desarrollo De Modelos De Propagacion De Ondas Sismicas En Medios Altamente Heterogeneos Y Sus Efectos: Aplicacion A Regiones Volcanicas Activas” EPHESTOS. CGL2011-29499-C02-01, Investigador Principal. 2012-2014. **242.000,00 €**.

16.- MEDiterranean SUPersite Volcanoes. MED-SUV. EU. FP7 – 308665-1.COC-DI-2011-08. **Investigador Principal. 2013-2016. 458.200,00 €**

17.- “MEDiterranean SUPersite Volcanoes. Integration of on-shore and off-shore passive and active Seismic Experiments in South Italy”, EUROFLEETS2-SI-005_MED-SUV.ISES. **Investigador principal junto al Dr. Giuseppe Puglisi. 2014-2015 Uso BIO “Sarmiento de Gamboa” y Buque “Aegean”. Valor estimado 500.000 €. Duración: 11/2010-10/2014 Organismo financiador: EUROFLEETS2, EU VII Framework Programm.**

18.- “Extraccion del conocimiento del estado de volcanes activos y su aplicacion en el modelado del pronostico de erupciones mediante el analisis avanzado de la señal sísmica”, KNOWAVES. TEC2015-68752-R. **Investigador principal junto a la Profesora Carmen Benítez Ortúzar. 2016-2020. 244.299,00 €**

19.- “Forecasting Volcanic Eruptions Using Signal Procesing and Machine Learning Techniques on Seismic Signals. FEMALE”. PID2019-106260GB-I00. **Investigador principal junto a la Profesora Carmen Benítez Ortúzar. 2020-2023. 229.900,00 €**

20.- “Prueba de concepto del uso del aprendizaje profundo para pronosticar erupciones volcanicas. Proof-Forever”. EUR2022-134044. **Investigador Principal. Diciembre de 2023- Diciembre 2024. 89.646,15 €**

21.- What can we learn from seismic signals to successfully forecast volcanic eruptions? (LEARNING). PID2022-143083NB-I00, **Investigador principal junto a la Profesora Carmen Benítez Ortúzar. 2023-2026. 287.500,00 €**

RESEARCH CONTRACTS.

22.- “Progettazione e realizzazione di 8 sub-arrays sismici”. Contrato de investigación entre Osservatorio Vesuviano de Nápoles y el Instituto Andaluz de Geofísica a través de la Fundación Empresa-Universidad de Granada. 1999-2001. **Investigador responsable de la parte española.**

23.- Contrato nº C-3609-00 suscrito con la empresa Agencia de Medio Ambiente y Agua de Andalucía, proyecto denominado "Servicio de mantenimiento y control de la Red de Acelógrafos de las Presas de Béznar y Rules correspondientes al Distrito Hidrográfico Mediterráneo, Provincia de Granada (NET730283)", junto con el prof. D. Fernando Delgado Ramos. La vigencia del proyecto se extendió desde el 17 de octubre de 2011 al 31 de diciembre de 2013 y cuyo importe ascendió a 16.800€, más el correspondiente IVA.

24.- Contrato nº C-3698-00 suscrito con la empresa Delegación de Gobierno de la Junta de Andalucía en Granada, proyecto denominado "Actuaciones ante riesgo sísmico y acceso a sistemas de información sísmica para gestión de emergencias", cuya vigencia se extendió desde el 25 de mayo de 2012 al 31 de diciembre de 2012 y cuyo importe ascendió a 17.700€ más el correspondiente IVA.

25.- Contrato nº 4178-00, suscrito entre la empresa Agencia de Medio Ambiente y Agua de Andalucía, siendo el Investigador Responsable el Prof. D. Fernando Delgado Ramos, proyecto titulado "Servicio de mantenimiento y control ordinario de la red de acelerógrafos de las presas de Béznar y Rules. Período 01/08/2015 - 31/07/2016". Esta Fundación actuó como entidad encargada de la gestión económico-administrativa del mismo. La duración de la colaboración se extiende desde el 9 de Septiembre de 2015 hasta el 8 de Septiembre de 2016.

AS COLLABORATOR

1. - "Sismicidad y Neotectónica de la Depresión de Granada y las Alpujarras". Financiación de CAICYT. 3184-83 C04-01. Periodo 1984-86. Investigador Principal Fernando de Miguel Martínez, Universidad de Granada.

2.- "Estudios geofísicos de zonas activas de España". Financiación CICYT. Periodo 1988-1990. PB86-0431-C05-04. Investigador Principal: Fernando de Miguel Martínez, Universidad de Granada.

3.- "Mapas de Riesgos Geológicos de la Provincia de Málaga y trabajos complementarios.", Financiación: Instituto Tecnológico y Geominero de España. 1988.

4.- "Mapas de Riesgos Geológicos de la Provincia de Granada", Financiación: Instituto Tecnológico y Geominero de España. 1989.

5.- "Microsismicidad, atenuación y respuesta local de las cuencas de Almería y Cerdeña (España) y Valle del Irno (Italia). 1991-1993. Financiación DGICYT. GEO90-1017. Investigador principal: Fernando de Miguel Martínez, Universidad de Granada.

6.- "European Laboratory Volcanoes: Teide. Definition of the fine structures and the plumbing system aimed at eruption prediction, hazard assesment and eruptive mechanism understanding". Programa EVOP (EV5V-CT93-0283), C.E.E. Proponente principal de microsismicidad: María José Blanco, IGN Canarias. **Investigador.**

7.- "Convenios de Colaboración para el desarrollo de Estudios Sísmicos", Junta de Andalucía - Universidad de Granada. III, IV y V Convenios específicos, años 1986, 1987 y 1988, **Becario.** VI, VII y VIII Convenios específicos, años 1989, 1990 y 1991, **Investigador.**

8-- "Acción Integrada hispano-italiana sobre Atenuación y Dispersión de Ondas Sísmicas", Financiada por la DGICYT, HI-121, año 1993. **Investigador.**

9.- "Spanish-Japanese joint project on seismic ground motion in sedimentary basins", Financiada por la Kajima Corporation, Japan, 1993-94. **Investigador.**

10- Modello di velocita e di attenuazione al vulcano Stromboli, 1997: CNR-GNV (Italia) 96.00856.PF62. **Investigador.**

11- Studio dell'attenuazione sismica all'Etna mediante arrays di sismometri a corto periodo. 1998. CNR-GNV (Italia) **Investigador.**

12.-"Simulación de movimientos fuertes del terreno e inversión de la fuente sísmica de terremotos del sureste de España" CICYT AMB99-0795-C02-01. **Investigador.**

13.-"Centenario del Observatorio Geofísico de Cartuja (Granada): Cien años de Sismología". REN 2001-4608-E. Investigador.

14.-"Integración de sistemas de adquisición de datos de la Red Sísmica de Andalucía." REN2000-2903-E Acción especial. **Investigador.**

15.-"Proyecto de monitoreo de volcanes activos de los Andes Centrales del Sur para la mitigacion del riesgo volcanico y mejorar la seguridad de la aeronavegacion en la región", Investigador responsable, Prof. J.G. Viramonte

16.-"Campo d'onda sismico associato alla dinamica del vulcanismo attivo", Ministero

dell'Istruzione, dell'Università e della Ricerca, RBAU01772S, Investigador principal, Prof. Edoardo Del Pezzo., 2002-2005.

17.- "High-Resolution Seismic Tomography and Earthquake Monitoring at Deception Island Volcano, Antarctica". USA-NSF Award# 0230094, William Wilcock (Principal Investigator) .UNIVERSITY OF WASHINGTON. Amount \$316,845.00

18.-"Control y vigilancia de la actividad sismo-volcánica en la isla Decepción". REN2002-12536-E. Investigador principal Javier Almendros.

19.-"Técnicas geofísicas y geodésicas para el estudio de la zona volcánica activa del Teide". CGL2004-21643. Investigador principal: Alicia García.

20.- "Control de la contaminación química en aguas de la Antártica". CGL2006-27105-E. Investigador Principal, Antonio Segura.

21.- "Catálogo de riesgos en el estado de Colima. Zonificación y análisis de las principales amenazas naturales y antropogénicas y estudio de la vulnerabilidad de edificaciones esenciales". CONACYT-Gobierno del Estado de Colima (México). Colima 2005-C01-14. Investigador principal, Mauricio Bretón González.

22.- "Zonificación y análisis de los principales peligros en el Volcán de Fuego de Colima y estudio de la vulnerabilidad de las poblaciones más cercanas al edificio volcánico". Fondo Ramón Alvarez Buylla de Aldana, 411/06. Universidad de Colima, México. Investigador principal Mauricio Bretón González.

23.- "Estructura Cortical Del Área De Las Shetland Del Sur Mediante El Análisis De Funciones Receptoras En Estaciones Sísmicas Permanentes De Banda Ancha. Corshet." POL2006-08663, Investigador principal, Fco. Javier Almendros González.

24.- "Towards improved imaging of Magma Chambers", Science Foundation of Ireland, 08/RFP/GEO1486. Investigador principal Chris Bean y Francesca Martini

25.- Seguimiento De La Actividad Sismovolcánica En Isla Decepción (Islas Shetland Del Sur, Antártida). CTM2008-03062-E. Investigador principal Daniel Stich.

26.- Natural Risk Prevention in Mediterranean Countries. European Union. N070401/2008/507838/SUB/A3. Investigador principal Francisco Vidal Sánchez.

27.- Seguimiento de la actividad volcánica de la isla Decepción (Islas Shetland del sur, Antártida) (sísmica). CGL2007-28855-E/ANT. Investigador principal Inmaculada Serrano Bermejo.

28.- "Estudio volcanológico de la Isla Decepción, Antártida". Gobierno argentino, 01/01/2004-31/12/2007. P.I.C.T.-O-07-11557. Investigador principal Alberto Caselli.

29.- "Estudio y seguimiento de volcanes activos: Volcán Copahue, Provincia de Neuquén". Gobierno argentino y Universidad de Buenos Aires.01/01/2004-31/12/2007. UBACyT X018. Investigador principal Alberto Caselli.

30.- "Estudio y seguimiento de volcanes activos: Isla Decepción, Antártida". Gobierno Argentino, 01/01/2008-31/12/2010. PICT-O-36051. Investigador principal Alberto Caselli.

31.- "Estudio y seguimiento de volcanes activos andinos de la zona volcánica sur (33° - 46° LS) y Antártida. Gobierno Argentino y Universidad de Buenos Aires. 01/01/2008-31/12/2010. UBACyT X040. Investigador principal Alberto Caselli.

32.- Fortalecimiento de las capacidades de I+D+I para contribuir a la reducción del Riesgo Volcánico en la Macaronesia (MAC/3/C161). UE. MAKAVOL. Investigador principal Nemesio Pérez (ITER).

33.- ESTRUCTURA 3D DEL ARCO DE GIBRALTAR Y MODELADO NUMERICO DE LA PROPAGACION DE ONDAS SÍSMICAS DE TERREMOTOS EN LA

ZONA DE CONTACTO DE PLACA NUBIA-EURASIA. P09-RNM-5100. Junta de Andalucía. José Morales Soto. 2010-2014

34.- Visualización De Modelos Sísmicos Temporales Generados A Partir De La Integración De Los Tiempos De Viaje De Los Terremotos Registrados En Andalucía. P20_00694, Junta de Andalucía. IP Inmaculada Serrano Bermejo. 04/10/2021 hasta 04/10/2023.

35.- ETIQUETADO COLABORATIVO DE EVENTOS VOLCANO-SÍSMICOS BASADO EN LA COMPARTICIÓN DE CONOCIMIENTO EXPERTO Y TÉCNICAS AVANZADAS DE MACHINE LEARNING. (CROWDLABELLING). A-TIC-215-UGR18. Junta de Andalucía. Luz María García Martínez. 2020-2022. 60.000 €

36.- Una infraestructura digital para la previsión de erupciones volcánicas en Canarias. PLEC2022.009271- DIGIVOLCAN (MINECO Líneas estratégicas). IP Carmen Benítez Ortúzar.

37.- Imaging active volcanic regions: an improvement of volcanic risk models (ALARM). C-EXP-022-UGR23. Universidad de Granada. IP Janire Prudencio Sónora.

38.- Observatorio argentino de vigilancia volcánica. SEGEMAR, Sec. de Minería, Min. Producción, Argentina. Financiación: BAPIN: 73103. Argentina. 2017-2022. U\$S 8.520.466.

39.- Nuevas tecnologías para el procesamiento de señales geofísicas. Monitoreo y resultados en Sudamérica. PROYECTOS I+D UNLP. Acreditación: UNLP. Código: UNLP G156. Argentina. Gabriel Badi. 2018-2021.

40.- Manifestación del Impacto Ambiental. Modalidad Particular y Estudio de Riesgo Nivel 2. Korean Gas, Mitsui, Samsung. Colima, Mexico. Mauricio Bretón González. 2019-2012. 90.000 €.

41.- State of unrest of active VOLCANOes through advanced seismic WAVES analysis - An application to eruption forecast modelling. EU. MSCA-IF-EF-ST. Proposal number: 798480. Luciano Zuccarello. 2019-2021. 170.000 €.

42.- Volcanic emissions analysis through SeiSmic and Infrasonic Advanced monitoring. VOSSIA. European Network of Observatories and Research Infrastructures for Volcanology – EUROVOLC. Luciano Zuccarello. 2018-2021. 4,997,292 €.

43.- ICE-VOLC (Multiparametric Experiment at antarctica VOLCANoes: data from volcano and cryosphere-ocean-atmosphere dynamics). Programma Nazionale di Ricerche in Antartide (PNRA). Italy. 2018-2021. 189.000 €.

44.- Fine-scale Seismicity Structure and Apparent Stress Distribution in Subducting Slabs at Intermediate Depths. Principal Investigator: Professor A Rietbrock, University of Liverpool, Earth Surface Dynamics. NERC Reference : NE/C000315/1. Period of Award: 1 Sep 2005 - 31 Oct 2009. Value: £182,406

45.- Assessing the strength of volcanic eruptions using acoustic infrasound measurements. Principal Investigator: Dr S. De Angelis, University of Liverpool, Earth, Ocean and Ecological Sciences. NERC Reference: NE/P00105X/1. Period of Award: 1 Jan 2017 - 31 Dec 2019. Value: £373,842

46.- TOMO-ETNA. Geophysical Instrument Pool Potsdam, GFZ, Germany. Grant: GIPP201407. Principal Investigator: Lühr, Birger; Ibanez, Jesus M.; Dahm, Torsten. <https://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de/doi/network/1T/2014>

Personnel hired under their R&D projects, transfer contracts, research groups and other calls for training or hiring of technical or research personnel.

1.- PRUDENCIO SOÑORA, JANIRE 01/11/2018 31/10/2020 PLAN NACIONAL De INVESTIGACIÓN CONTRATOS DE INCORPORACIÓN DE DOCTORES JUAN DE LA CIERVA INCORPORACION

2.- DÍAZ MORENO, ALEJANDRO 01/12/2016 31/05/2017 UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA PLAN PROPIO CONTRATO PUENTE

3.- DÍAZ MORENO, ALEJANDRO 01/12/2014 30/11/2016 PLAN NACIONAL DE INVESTIGACIÓN BECAS F.P.I. (PROYECTOS) PERIODO DE CONTRATO PREDOCTORAL CGL2011-29499-C02-01

4.- PRUDENCIO SOÑORA, JANIRE 01/04/2014 31/03/2015 UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA PROYECTOS INTERNACIONALES CONTRATO DE INVESTIGACIÓN 308665

5.- DÍAZ MORENO, ALEJANDRO 01/12/2012 30/11/2016 PLAN NACIONAL DE INVESTIGACIÓN BECAS F.P.I. (PROYECTOS) FASE DE BECA CGL2011-29499-C02-01

6.- PRUDENCIO SOÑORA, JANIRE 18/07/2012 31/12/2013 OTRAS INSTITUCIONES OTRAS INSTITUCIONES CONTRATOS. Basque Government researcher training program BFI09.277.

7.- GARCÍA JEREZ, ANTONIO 01/04/2012 31/03/2015 PLAN NACIONAL DE INVESTIGACIÓN CONTRATOS DE INCORPORACIÓN DE DOCTORES PROGRAMA JUAN DE LA CIERVA CGL2008-01660

8.- MARTÍN LEÓN, ROSA MARÍA 01/01/2012 31/12/2014 PLAN NACIONAL DE INVESTIGACIÓN PERSONAL TÉCNICO DE APOYO MOD. INFRAESTRUCTURAS CIENTIFICAS

9.- PRUDENCIO SOÑORA, JANIRE 01/01/2012 31/12/2012 OTRAS INSTITUCIONES OTRAS INSTITUCIONES CONTRATOS. Basque Government researcher training program BFI09.277.

10.- GARCÍA YEGUAS, MARÍA ARACELI 01/01/2011 31/12/2011 UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA PLAN PROPIO CONTRATO PUENTE

11.- PRUDENCIO SOÑORA, JANIRE 01/01/2010 31/12/2011 OTRAS INSTITUCIONES OTRAS INSTITUCIONES BECAS. Basque Government researcher training program BFI09.277.

- 12.- GONZÁLEZ MARÍN, ENRIQUE 01/09/2009 31/08/2013 PLAN NACIONAL DE INVESTIGACIÓN BECAS F.P.I. (PROYECTOS) FASE DE BECA
- 13.- CORTÉS MORENO, GUILLERMO 01/05/2009 30/04/2011 UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA PROYECTOS DE INVESTIGACIÓN CONTRATOS DE APOYO TÉCNICO
- 14.- GARCÍA YEGUAS, MARÍA ARACELI 01/10/2008 30/09/2010 PLAN NACIONAL DE INVESTIGACIÓN BECAS F.P.I. (PROYECTOS) PERIODO DE CONTRATO PREDOCTORAL
- 15.- CORTÉS MORENO, GUILLERMO 01/07/2008 30/09/2008 UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA PROYECTOS INTERNACIONALES CONTRATO DE INVESTIGACIÓN
- 16.- GARCÍA YEGUAS, MARÍA ARACELI 01/10/2006 30/09/2010 PLAN NACIONAL DE INVESTIGACIÓN BECAS F.P.I. (PROYECTOS) FASE DE BECA
- 17.- ZANDOMENEGHI, DARIA 01/12/2005 30/09/2007 UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA PROYECTOS INTERNACIONALES CONTRATO DE INVESTIGACIÓN
- 18.- MARTÍNEZ ARÉVALO, CARMEN 08/11/2004 31/03/2005 UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA PROYECTOS INTERNACIONALES CONTRATO DE INVESTIGACIÓN
- 19.- CARMONA RODRÍGUEZ, ENRIQUE 01/01/2004 31/08/2005 UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA PROYECTOS DE INVESTIGACIÓN CONTRATO DE INVESTIGACIÓN
- 20.- MARTÍNEZ ARÉVALO, CARMEN 01/01/2003 30/06/2003 UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA PLAN PROPIO AYUDAS PUENTE
- 21.- CARMONA RODRÍGUEZ, ENRIQUE 10/11/2002 09/11/2003 UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA PROYECTOS DE INVESTIGACIÓN CONTRATO DE INVESTIGACIÓN
- 22.- ABRIL MARTÍ, MIGUEL 01/11/2002 31/10/2004 UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA PROYECTOS INTERNACIONALES CONTRATO DE INVESTIGACIÓN
- 23.- ZANDOMENEGHI, DARIA 01/07/2002 31/03/2005 UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA PROYECTOS INTERNACIONALES CONTRATO DE INVESTIGACIÓN
- 24.- MARTÍNEZ ARÉVALO, CARMEN 08/11/2004 31/03/2005 UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA PROYECTOS INTERNACIONALES CONTRATO DE INVESTIGACIÓN
- 25.- CARMONA RODRÍGUEZ, ENRIQUE 01/01/2004 31/08/2005 UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA PROYECTOS DE INVESTIGACIÓN CONTRATO DE INVESTIGACIÓN
- 26.- MARTÍNEZ ARÉVALO, CARMEN 01/01/2003 30/06/2003 UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA PLAN PROPIO AYUDAS PUENTE
- 27.- CARMONA RODRÍGUEZ, ENRIQUE 10/11/2002 09/11/2003 UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA PROYECTOS DE INVESTIGACIÓN CONTRATO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

- 28.- ABRIL MARTÍ, MIGUEL 01/11/2002 31/10/2004 UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA
PROYECTOS INTERNACIONALES CONTRATO DE INVESTIGACIÓN
- 29.- ZANDOMENEGHI, DARIA 01/07/2002 31/03/2005 UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA
PROYECTOS INTERNACIONALES CONTRATO DE INVESTIGACIÓN
- 30.- ABRIL MARTÍ, MIGUEL 01/06/2002 31/10/2004 UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA
PROYECTOS INTERNACIONALES CONTRATO DE INVESTIGACIÓN
- 31.- CARMONA RODRÍGUEZ, ENRIQUE 01/11/2001 31/10/2002 UNIVERSIDAD DE
GRANADA CONTRATOS Y CONVENIOS (OTRI)
- 32.- MARTÍNEZ ARÉVALO, CARMEN 01/01/1999 31/12/2002 M.E.C.D. BECAS F.P.I.
(PROYECTOS) PLAN NACIONAL (P.N.)
- 33.- GUTIÉRREZ ESPINOZA, LIGDAMIS ANAXIS 15/04/2021 31/12/202
UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA PROYECTOS DE INVESTIGACIÓN CONTRATO DE
INVESTIGACIÓN PID2019-106260GB-I00
- 34.- TITOS LUZÓN, MANUEL MARCELINO 25/02/2019 06/10/2019 UNIVERSIDAD DE
GRANADA PLAN PROPIO CONTRATO PUENTE TEC2015-68752-R
- 35.- PRUDENCIO SOÑORA, JANIRE 01/11/2018 27/04/2021 PLAN NACIONAL
DE INVESTIGACIÓN CONTRATOS DE INCORPORACIÓN DE DOCTORES JUAN DE
LA CIERVA INCORPORACION
- 36.- TITOS LUZÓN, MANUEL MARCELINO 15/08/2018 14/02/2019
UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA PROYECTOS DE INVESTIGACIÓN CONTRATO DE
INVESTIGACIÓN TEC2015-68752-R
- 37.- GUTIÉRREZ ESPINOZA, LIGDAMIS ANAXIS 21/02/2023 31/12/2023
UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA PROYECTOS DE INVESTIGACIÓN C.
INVESTIGACION INDEFINIDO LEY CIENCIA EUR2022-134044
- 38.- CORTÉS MORENO, GUILLERMO 01/01/2022 31/12/2024 PLAN NACIONAL
DE INVESTIGACIÓN CONTRATOS DE INCORPORACIÓN DE DOCTORES JUAN DE
LA CIERVA INCORPORACION
- 39.- REY DEvesa, PABLO 01/07/2021 30/06/2025 PLAN NACIONAL DE
INVESTIGACIÓN BECAS F.P.I. (PROYECTOS) CONTRATO PREDOCTORAL
LEY 14/2011 PID2019-106260GB-I00

LARGE MULTIDISCIPLINARY VOLCANOLOGICAL CAMPAIGNS AS A RESPONSIBLE/CO-RESPONSIBLE RESEARCHER.

1.- A double seismic antenna experiment at Teide volcano (1994). Role, Responsible.

This experiment was carried out during a 40 days in Teide Volcano (Canary Islands, Spain) with two short-period small-aperture dense seismic antennas in 1994. The objective of this experiment was to detect, analyze and locate the local seismicity. We analyzed also the background seismic noise to investigate the possible presence of volcanic tremor. From a set of 76 events, we selected 21 of them in base of their good signal-to-noise ratio and their possibility to locate their seismic source by using the seismic antennas. A visual classification based on the S–P time and seismogram shape has permitted to establish three groups of events: local seismicity (S–P time between 3 and 5s), very local earthquakes (S–P time smaller than 3s) and artificial explosions. This experiment was partially supporter by the project “European Laboratory volcanoes: Teide. Definition of the fine structures and the plumbing system aimed at eruption prediction, hazard assessment and eruptive mechanism understanding”, EVOV-CT93-0283 CEE and by the project ANT98-1111.

2.- Twin digital short period seismic Array Experiment at Stromboli Volcano (June-July 1997). Role, Co-responsible

Two small arrays composed by short period (1 Hz) digital seismic stations, with an aperture of approximately 400 meters, were set up at Stromboli volcano (one at semaforo Labronzo, the other at Ginostra, Timpone del Fuoco) in June-July 1997, with the purpose of the spatial location of the high frequency source of the explosion quakes. About 75 explosion-quakes were recorded at both arrays, and constitute the available data base. We have planned to apply the zero-lag cross-correlation technique to the whole data set in order to obtain back-azimuth and apparent slowness of the coherent seismic phases. A preliminary analysis for both arrays shows that the predominant back-azimuth for the first phase is oriented in the direction of, but not strictly coincident to, the crater area. Moreover some back-scattered arrivals are quite evident in the seismogram. Participant institutions: Dipartimento di Fisica, Università di Salerno, Dipartimento di Geofisica e Vulcanologia, Univ. Federico II – Napoli, Istituto Andaluz de Geofisica - Univ. de Granada, Spain, CSIC. Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales de Madrid – Spain, Osservatorio Vesuviano – Italy.

3.- A seismic array on Mt Vesuvius (November, 1997). Role, Co-responsible.

In November 1997 a seismic antenna (array) of short period seismometers was installed on the south-western flank of Mt. Vesuvius; aim of the experiment was to test the use of non-conventional devices for the seismic monitoring of this volcano. In 7 months local seismicity, regional earthquakes and samples of seismic noise were recorded by the array and organised in a data base. Local earthquakes and seismic noise have been analysed with array techniques to investigate the spectral, kinematic and polarization properties of the wavefield. Preliminary results show that the backazimuth of local earthquakes is oriented in the direction of the crater area. For some events, the source location has been constrained using a simplified back propagation in a 2-D velocity structure. The noise wavefield is characterized by the predominance of a sustained low frequency component (< 1Hz) whose source is located S-SE of the array. This low frequency signal has been interpreted as associated to the sea-loading in the gulf of Naples. Participant institutions: Osservatorio Vesuviano – Italy, Dipartimento di Fisica, Università di Salerno, Istituto Andaluz de Geofisica - Univ. de Granada, Spain.

4.- Seismic Survey Of Deception Island, Antarctica. 1993-2007. Role, Responsible

During 14 Antarctic campaigns, from 1993 to 2007, I have been the principal investigator of different Spanish public calls for the study of the Decepción Island volcano and adjacent areas. These volcanic monitoring campaigns have had multidisciplinary aspects, using different scientific platforms (Antarctic Bases and scientific research vessels). The total budget used for this work exceeds 1.5 million euros, more than 10 researchers, numerous doctoral theses and impact publications in international journals have been hired. The participation has been multi-institutional and multinational, highlighting in Spain the collaboration with the CSIC-National Museum of Natural Sciences, and the Universities of Almería, Jaén or Cádiz, among others. Internationally, it is important to highlight the collaboration with institutions from Italy, Argentina, Mexico, the USA and Ireland, among many others. In general each seismic survey is divided in two phases. The first one consists in the deployment of the seismic network and in a rapid evaluation of the level of the seismic activity in Deception volcano in order to establish the activity level before the opening of the Spanish Antarctic Base “Gabriel de Castilla”. In the second phase, all scientific instrumentation is deployed, a quasi-real-time evaluation routine of volcanic dynamics is established, and multiparametric data are acquired.

5.- A Double Seismic Array Experiment on Mt. Etna (1999). Role, Co-Responsible.

On September 1999 two seismic antennas (array) and a profile of 3-D stations equipped with short period seismometers were installed on Mt. Etna; Aims of the experiment were to investigate the structure and the polarisation parameters of the volcanic tremor wavefield radiated in eruptive conditions, and to measure the seismic velocities and attenuation in the shallow structure beneath the arrays. The first array was installed close to Pizzi Deneri Volcanological Observatory, East of the crater area; the second array was located close to Torre del Filosofo site, south of the crater area. The profile was set up close to the Pizzi Deneri array. It had a length of 600 meters and consisted of 16 short period 3-component stations. In addition, a circular array of 8 short period seismometers was set up around the main crater area. Participant institutons: Osservatorio Vesuviano, INGV-Naples, Italy, Progetto POSEIDON – INGV, Catania, Italy, Istituto Andaluz de Geofisica - Univ. de Granada, Spain.

6.- Seismic campaing at Sao Miguel, Azores (2003).

Between April 4 and July 15, 2003, a temporary network including 14 short-period and broad-band instruments, as well as three small-aperture seismic antennas, was deployed in São Miguel to expand and complete the permanent network operated by “Sistema de Vigilancia Sismologica dos Açores” (SIVISA). In the framework of the EU project ‘e-Ruption’, a joint Italy-Portugal-Spain team carried out a seismicity study at the Fogo-Furnas volcanoes and adjacent areas on Sao Miguel Island, Azores. These instruments recorded continuously from April 1 to July 15, 2003. The aim of the experiment was to collect high-quality data in order to characterize the present-day level of activity of these volcanoes. More than one thousand earthquakes were detected by our systems. Most of this seismicity is associated to an intense swarm on April 26, 2003, when about 300 micro-earthquakes ($M_d < 2$) occurred over a period of a few hours. This activity is concentrated in a small volume located NE of the summit Fogo crater, at depths ranging between 1 and 6 km bsl. The seismic survey was funded by the European Union project e-Ruption (EVR1-CT-2001-40021). Partial support also came from the projects ANT2001-3833, CLG2004-05744-C04-01, and CGL2005-05789-C03-02/ANT of

the Spanish Ministry of Education, and from the European Union project VOLUME (FPG2004-GLOBAL-3-018471).

7.- Array analyses of volcanic earthquakes and tremor recorded at Las Cañadas caldera (Tenerife Island, Spain) during the 2004 seismic activation of Teide volcano. Role, Responsible.

We deployed three seismic antennas at Las Cañadas caldera in early May 2004. They were in operation during the period May–July 2004. We selected three locations near Teide volcano: Cañada de Diego Hernández (DH), Sanatorio Plateau (SA) and the southern slopes of Pico Viejo volcano (PV). Each antenna was composed of 10 short-period seismometers (nine vertical-component and one three-component). All receivers were Mark L28 instruments, with response electronically extended to 1 Hz. The acquisition system sampled these 12 channels at 100 sps with a 24-bit A/D converter in continuous mode. Data was stored into an external, 30 Gb hard disk. Absolute timing was obtained using a GPS receiver. The DH, SA, and PV antennas had apertures of 550, 430, and 350 m, respectively.

8.- Volcanic tremor and local earthquakes at Copahue volcanic complex, Southern Andes, Argentina (2003-2005). Role, Responsible.

The experiment was envisaged to deploy a seismic antenna in the vicinity of Caviahue Village, in a flat area equidistant from the crater and the geothermal field of Copahue volcano, Argentina. The array was in operation from November 8th, 2003 to May 10th, 2004, and from November 10th, 2004, to April 8th, 2005, with the exception of March 2005. It was composed of 5 vertical and one 3-D seismometers. All of them were Mark L-25 sensors with responses electronically extended to 1 Hz. Recording was performed by an eight-channel, PC-based digital data acquisition system with a dynamic range of 16 bits, sampling at 200 samples/second/channel. Involved Institutions: University of Granada, Spain, University of Buenos Aires, Argentina, Osservatorio Vesuviano, Naples, Italy, Universidad Nacional de la Plata, Argentina. This experiment was partially supported by the research projects VOLUME, UE, FP6-2004-Global-3-018471, SISVOLTEDEC CGL2005-05789-C03-02/ANT, FIRB — Italy's Ministry of Education for base research, and DPC-INGV (Italy's Civil Protection and INGV funds for volcano monitoring) V3_4 Project.

9.- TOMODEC Experiment (2005). Role, Responsible.

The seismic data were collected using the R/V Hesperides in January 2005 as part of an international experiment led by the University of Granada, Spain. The experiment was designed to obtain a high-resolution three-dimensional image of a volume extending up to ~ 20 km from the center of the caldera and down to at least ~ 3 km depth, and also included a 90-km-long profile for deeper imaging of the crust beneath the island. Data were recorded on three-component seismometers at 36 land stations and by 9 compact arrays which typically comprised about ten vertical seismometers arranged around one of the three-component seismometer sites. In total 122 onland seismometers were used. Fourteen 1-Hz ocean bottom seismometers (OBS) from the US OBS Instrument Pool were also available for each round of shooting and were deployed at a total of 26 seafloor sites within the caldera and around the island. This seismometer network was used to record more than 6600 air gun shots that were located both inside Port Foster and around the island from the R/V Hesperides during a 2-week period. Approximately 580 km of air gun shot lines were completed. The experiment used the R/V Hespérides and R/V Las Palmas, with the support of the personnel of the Gabriel de Castilla base, and the members of the TOMODEC Working Group. This work

was supported by the Spanish Education and Research Ministry grants REN 2001-3833, CGL2005-05789-C02-02/ANT, POL2006-08663, and CGL2008-01660 and the U.S. National Science Foundation grant ANT-0230094. The ocean bottom seismometers were provided by the U.S National Oceanographic Instrument Pool. Several working groups and teams were involved in the TOMO-DEC experiment, such as the Andalusian Institute of Geophysics and Earthquake Disaster Prevention (IAGPDS), Lamont Doherty Earth Observatory, Columbia University (United States), INGV-Vesuvius Observatory (Italy), INGV-Catania (Italy), CENAPRED (Mexico), University of Cadiz (Andalusia), University of Colima (Mexico), University College Dublin (Ireland), Complutense University of Madrid (Spain), National University of La Plata (Argentina), University of Washington (United States) and USGS Volcanic Hazard Team (United States).

10.- Seismic Survey Of Colima Volcano (Mexico) November 2005–May 2006. Role, Co-Responsible.

In the framework of the FIRB project# 2-13-3-46-23 aimed to study high risk explosive volcanoes, a seismic survey on Colima volcano was carried out by the Osservatorio Vesuviano–INGV, the Observatorio Vulcanologico of Colima University and the Instituto Andaluz de Geofísica–Universidad de Granada, from October 2005 to May 2006. The aim of the experiment was the detailed study of the elastic wavefield associated with the eruptive dynamics of Colima volcano. During the seismic survey four Lennartz MARSlite stations were installed on the Colima volcano flank. The stations were equipped with four Lennartz LE-3D/20s sensors, that were buried in approximately 30 cm deep holes. The 3-D sensors were deployed with the horizontal components oriented in the N-S and E-W directions. In addition we deployed a 12-channel seismic antenna at the Cofradía de Tonila site in October 2005. This antenna was composed of 10 short-period seismometers (nine vertical-component and one three-component). Several working groups and teams were involved in these experiment, such as the Andalusian Institute of Geophysics and Earthquake Disaster Prevention (IAGPDS), INGV-Vesuvius Observatory (Italy), and University of Colima (Mexico).

11.- TEIDE-VS Experiment (2007). Role, Responsible.

An active seismic experiment to study the internal structure of Teide volcano was being carried out on Tenerife, a volcanic island in Spain's Canary Islands archipelago. The main objective of the Tomography at Teide Volcano Spain (TOM- TEIDEVS) experiment, begun in January 2007, is to obtain a three-dimensional (3-D) structural image of Teide volcano using seismic tomography and seismic reflection/refraction imaging techniques. The multinational experiment—involving institutes from Spain, the United Kingdom, Italy, Ireland, and Mexico—generated a unique high resolution structural image of the active volcano edifice and will further our understanding of volcanic processes. The experiment consisted of the deployment of a dense seismic network on Tenerife Island and the shooting of air guns around the island. The Spanish oceanographic vessel R/V Hespérides fired shots using a 12 m long array consisting of six BOLT 1500LL with a total volume of 3520 cu.in. (57.68 L). The air guns were shot every two minutes (6459 shots were fired in total), which corresponds to a shot separation of around 300 m. A total of 125 seismometers provided by various institutions from the UK, Italy and Spain were deployed on Tenerife Island. The majority of instruments were 100 Guralp CMG-6TD provided by the University of Liverpool, UK. This work has been partially funded by projects CGL2004-05744-C04-01 and CGL2005-07589-C03-02/ANT of the Spanish Ministry of Science, FP6-2004-Global-3-018471 of the

European Union, and by the Geophysics Research Group (RNM104) of the Junta de Andalucía, Spain. The seismic instruments and data management facilities were provided under loan 812 by SEIS-UK at the University of Leicester to the University of Liverpool. Data collected will be available through the IRIS Data Management Center. The facilities of SEIS-UK are supported by the Natural Environment Research Council under Agreement R8/H10/64

12.- TOMOETNA Experiment (2014-2015). Role, Responsible.

The TOMO-ETNA experiment was devised to image of the crust underlying the volcanic edifice and, possibly, its plumbing system by using passive and active refraction/reflection seismic methods. This experiment included activities both on-land and offshore with the main objective of obtaining a new high-resolution seismic tomography to improve the knowledge of the crustal structures existing beneath the Etna volcano and northeast Sicily up to Aeolian Islands. The TOMO-ETNA experiment was divided in two phases. The first phase started on June 15, 2014 and finalized on July 24, 2014, with the withdrawal of two removable seismic networks (a short period network and a broadband network composed by 80 and 20 stations respectively) deployed at Etna volcano and surrounding areas. During this first phase the oceanographic research vessel (R/V) “Sarmiento de Gamboa” and the hydro-oceanographic vessel (H/V) “Galatea” performed the offshore activities, which includes the deployment of ocean bottom seismometers (OBS), air-gun shooting for wide angle seismic refraction (WAS), multi-channel seismic (MCS) reflection surveys, magnetic surveys and ROV (remotely operated vehicle) dives. This phase finished with the recovery of the short period seismic network. In the second phase the broadband seismic network remained operative until October 28, 2014, and the R/V “Aegaeo” performed additional MCS surveys during November 19-27, 2014. Overall, the information deriving from TOMO-ETNA experiment could provide the answer to many uncertainties that have arisen while exploiting the large amount of data provided by the cutting-edge monitoring systems of Etna volcano and surrounding areas. This experiment has a high number of innovative elements, of which I want to highlight:

- Seismic data were recorded by a very large number of seismic stations, that range from ocean bottom seismometers, hydrophones, seismic antennas and permanent and portable seismic stations.
- It represents the first experiment covering such a wide and heterogeneous region, including two volcanic environments and five active volcanoes.
- The seismic tomography integrates, and for the first time in Mt. Etna and surrounding region, passive sources (earthquakes and LP events) and marine active air-gun shootings. This approach provided a 3D image inverting simultaneously P-waves travel times for both seismic sources.
- The expected images in the investigated area are probably the deepest ever obtained in previous research works.
- The final tomographic images are the product of the integration of seismic data with other geophysical surveys performed both in terrestrial and marine environments as magnetic, gravimetric and magnetotelluric measurements among others.

This experiment was partially funded by the following research projects: the European project MED-SUV funded by the European Union’s Seventh Framework Program for research, technological development and demonstration under grant agreement No. 308665; the Spanish COCSABO project (COC-DI 2011-08); the European project EUROFLEETS2 (Seventh Framework Programme, grant agreement No. 312762) through transnational access

to the research vessels “Sarmiento de Gamboa” operated by CSIC (Spain) and “Aegaeo” by HCMR (Greece); the Geophysical Instrument Pool Potsdam (GIPP) from GFZ (Potsdam) with the project (Seismic TOMOgraphy of ETNA volcano and Eolian Islands, Italy, using active and passive seismic data). In addition I had the following supporting institutions: Dipartimento Regionale della Protezione Civile, Regione Siciliana; Dipartimento Azienda Regionale Foreste Demaniali, Ufficio Provinciale di Catania; Ente Parco dell’Etna; Unidad de Tecnología Marina - CSIC in Barcelona (Spain); Stato Maggiore Marina (Italian Navy General Staff), CINCPNAV (Command in Chief of the Fleet) and Marisicilia (Navy Command of Sicily); Coastal Guard of Messina and Riposto; to obtain support and navigation permissions for the oceanographic cruises: Spanish Foreign Office and Italian Foreign Office. In addition the experiment was partially supported by the Spanish projects TEC2015-68752-R (MINECO/FEDER), KNOWAVES and CGL2015-67130-C2-2. I thank all private and public owners of the sites selected to deploy seismic stations for their kind and unselfish disposal to use their properties.

SPECIFIC CONTRACTS AS SCIENTIFIC ADVISOR TO THE RESEARCH EXECUTIVE AGENCY (REA) AND THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION.

- REA HORIZON-MSCA-2023-DN-01 – EVALUATORS, CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-164
- REA HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-02 - Twinning - Vice-Chairs, CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-163
- REA Evaluation – Call RFCS-2023 - Vice-Chairs, CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-162
- HORIZON -MSCA-PF-2023, Vice-Chair, CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-160
- REA RFCS-2023-CSP Big tickets VCs, CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-159
- HORIZON-MSCA-2022-SE-01-01- Evaluators/Rapporteurs/, Vice-Chair, CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-157
- REA HORIZON-MSCA-2022-DN-01 – EVALUATORS, CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-156
- REA RFCS-2023-CSP, VCs, CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-155
- HORIZON EUROPE MSCA-PF-2022, Chair, CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-154
- REA HORIZON-MSCA-2021-DN-01-01 – EVALUATORS, CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-153
- HORIZON EUROPE MSCA-PF-2021, Chair. CONTRACT NUMBER CT-EX2006C159051-152
- H2020-MSCA-IF-2020, Chair. CONTRACT NUMBER CT-EX2006C159051-151.
- REA/A/01 H2020-MSCA-ITN-2020, ViceChair. CONTRACTS NUMBER CT-EX2006C159051-145. CT-EX2006C159051-148. EX2006C159051-150.
- H2020-MSCA-IF-2019, ViceChair. CONTRACT NUMBER CT-EX2006C159051-144.
- Call ID: H2020-SFS-2019-2_First Stage Topic reference: SFS-35-2019-2020. ViceChair. February-April, 2019. CT-EX2006C159051-143.
- H2020-MSCA-ITN-2019, ViceChair. CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-140. January-April 2019. CT-EX2006C159051-141. CT-EX2006C159051-142

- H2020-MSCA-IF-2018, ViceChair. CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-139 y CT-EX2006C159051-138. September-December 2018.
- Expert, Final evaluation, project - FP7-ITN-GA-2013-608001-ABYSSYS. CT-EX2006C159051-137. July-August 2018.
- H2020-MSCA-ITN-2018, ViceChair. CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-134 y CT-EX2006C159051-136. January-March 2018.
- H2020-MSCA-IF-2017, ViceChair. CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-128 y CT-EX2006C159051-129. September-December 2017
- H2020-MSCA-ITN-2017, ViceChair. CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-125 y CT-EX2006C159051-126. January-March 2017.
- Expert, Final evaluation, project - FP7-ITN-GA-2013-290040-MINSC. CT-EX2006C159051-124. July-August 2016.
- H2020-MSCA-IF-2016, ViceChair. CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-121 y CT-EX2006C159051-122. September-December 2016.
- H2020-MSCA-ITN-2016, ViceChair. CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-120 y CT-EX2006C159051-119. January-March 2016.
- Expert, Final evaluation, project - FP7-ITN-GA-2013-289976-NEMOH. CT-EX2006C159051-118. March 2016.
- Expert, Final evaluation, project - FP7-ITN-GA-2013-291509-INTERFACES CT-EX2006C159051-117. July-August 2016.
- H2020-MSCA-IF-2015, ViceChair. CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-116. September-December 2015.
- H2020-MSCA-ITN-2015, ViceChair. CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-115. January-March 2015.
- H2020-MSCA-IF-2014, ViceChair. CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-114. September-December 2014.
- H2020-MSCA-ITN-2014, ViceChair. CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-113. January-March 2014.
- Expert, Final evaluation, project - FP7-ITN-GA-2013-288843-ITARS. CT-EX2006C159051-97. July-August 2014.
- Expert, Middle term evaluation, project - FP7-ITN-GA-2013-290040-MINSC. CT-EX2006C159051-95. February 2014.
- Expert, Final evaluation, project - FP7-ITN-GA-2013-289958-BIOBONES. CT-EX2006C159051-93. July-August 2013.
- FP7-MCA-IF-2013, Expert. CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-112. September-December 2013.
- FP7-MCA-ITN-2013, Expert. CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-110. January-March 2013
- FP7-MCA-IF-2012, Expert. CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-108. September-December 2012.
- FP7-MCA-ITN-2012, Expert. CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-106. January-March 2012
- FP7-MCA-IF-2011, Expert. CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-105. September-December 2011.
- FP7-MCA-ITN-2011, Expert. CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-104. January-March 2011
- FP7-MCA-IF-2010, Expert. CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-101. September-December 2010.

- FPT-MCA-ITN-2010, Expert. CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-100. January-March 2010
- FP7-MCA-IAPP-2010, Expert. CONTRACT NUMBER - CT-EX2006C159051-98. January-March 2010
- ERASMUS MUNDUS Call EACEA/41/10, May-June 2011.

SCIENTIFIC-TECHNICAL DOCUMENTS BOOKS AND SCIENTIFIC REPORTS

1990:

- 1.- Del Pezzo, E., & Ibáñez, J.M., (1990). Ondas coda. Teorías y resultados. Monografías del Instituto Andaluz de Geofísica y PDS. Servicio de publicaciones de la Universidad de Granada. ISBN 84-338-1250-5, 148 pp.
- 2.- Ibáñez, J.M., (1990). Atenuación de ondas coda y Lg en el Sur de España y de Italia a partir de sismogramas digitales. Servicio de Publicaciones de la Universidad de Granada. ISBN 84-338-1160-6, 306 pp.

1992:

- 3.- Patané, D., & Ibáñez, J.M. (1992). Procedure di calcolo in linguaggio Basic per la stima del fattore di qualita: QLIN e QNLIN. Open File Report, CNR, I.I.V., 4/91, 13 pp.
- 4.- Patané, D., De Miguel, F. & Ibáñez, J.M. (1992). Un programma in Basic basato sul metodo di Wadati per il calcolo della profondita focale dei terremoti e delle velocita delle onde P e S: Applicazione all'area Etnea. Open File Report, CNR, I.I.V., 3/91, 23 pp.

1997:

- 5.- Ibáñez, J.M. (1997). "Apuntes de Sismología Volcánica". Ed. Por la Casa de los Volcanes. Cabildo de Lanzarote. 92 pp. ISBN 84-87021-74.3.

1998:

- 6.- Del Pezzo, E., La Rocca, M., Petrosino, S., Grozea, B., Maritato, L., Saccorotti, G., Simii, M., Ibáñez, J.M., Alguacil, G., Carmona, E., Abril, M., Almendros, J., Ortiz, R., García, A., Pingue, F. & Esposito, T. (1998). Twin digital short period seismic array experiment at Stromboli volcano (September 1997). Open File Report. Osservatorio Vesuviano, 1998, n° 1.
- 7.- Del Pezzo, E., Bianco, F., Castellano, M., Petrosino, S., Pingue, F., Capello, M., Esposito, T., Augusti, V., Saccorotti, G., La Rocca, M., Maresca, R., Galluzo, D., Cirillo, A., Grozea, B., Ibáñez, J.M., Carmona, E. & Alguacil G. (1998). A seismic array on Mt. Vesuvius. Open File Report. Osservatorio Vesuviano, 1998, n° 3.

1999:

- 8.- Ibáñez, J.M. & Del Pezzo, E. (1999). Seismic survey of Deception Island, December 1990-March 2000. Open File Report. Osservatorio Vesuviano, 1999, n° 4.
- 9.- Saccorotti, G., Almendros, J., Carmona, E., Ibáñez, J.M. & Del Pezzo, E. (1999). Seismic arrays at Deception Island 1998-99 survey – 1st phase. Open File Report. Osservatorio Vesuviano, 1999, n° 1.
- 10.- Del Pezzo, E.; Bianco, F.; Castellano, M.; Petrosino, S.; Pingue, F.; Capello, M.; Esposito, T.; Augusti, V.; Saccorotti, G.; La Rocca, M.; Maresca, R.; Galluzo, D.; Cirillo, A.;

Grozea, B.; Ibáñez, J. M.; Carmona, E.; Alguacil, G. (1999). *A seismic array on Mt. Vesuvius*. Open file del Osservatorio Vesuviano, 3/1999. www.osve.unina.it.

2000:

11.- Del Pezzo, E.; Castellano, M.; Capello, M.; Giudicepietro, F.; La Rocca, M.; Martini, M.; Petrosino, S.; Saccorotti, G.; Ibáñez, J. M.; Abril, M.; Almendros, J.; Carmona, E.; Martínez, C.; Vílchez, J.; Privitera, E.; Alparone, S.; Di Grazia, G.; Gresta, S. (2000). *A Double Seismic Array Experiment on Mt. Etna*. Open file del Osservatorio Vesuviano, 1/2000. www.osve.unina.it.

2007:

12.- Del Pezzo, E.; Bianco, F.; Saccorotti, G.; La Rocca, M.; Galluzzo, D.; Nisii, V.; Petrosino, S.; Cusano, P.; Zaccarelli, L.; Damiano, N.; Tramelli, A.; de Astis, G.; Bretón, M.; Orozco-Rojas, J.; Navarro, C.; Ibáñez, J. M.; Ocaña, E.; García, A. (2007). *Seismic survey of Colima Volcano (México). November 2005-May 2006*. Open file del Osservatorio Vesuviano, 7/2007. www.osve.unina.it.

CHAPTERS OF BOOKS

1991:

1.- De Miguel, F., Ibáñez, J.M., Morales, J. Peña, J.A., & Romacho, M.D. (1991). "Escalas de magnitud para redes sísmicas locales". En *Instrumentación y Proceso de Datos en Ciencias de la Tierra*. Ed. Alicia García. Serie Casa de los Volcanes, Cabildo Insular de Lanzarote, 1, 91-100. ISBN 84-87021-13.3.

2.- Ibáñez, J.M., De Miguel, F., Alguacil, G., Morales, J. & Posadas, A.M. (1991). "Un programa de cálculo de parámetros de coda para PC's". En *Instrumentación y Proceso de Datos en Ciencias de la Tierra*. Ed. Alicia García. Serie Casa de los Volcanes, Cabildo Insular de Lanzarote, 1, 101-122. ISBN 84-87021-13.3.

3.- Peña, J.A., Alguacil, G., Vidal, F., Ibáñez, J.M. De Miguel, F., Morales, J. & Posadas, A.M. (1991). "EQBASE-1". En *Instrumentación y Proceso de Datos en Ciencias de la Tierra*. Ed. Alicia García. Serie Casa de los Volcanes, Cabildo Insular de Lanzarote, 1, 123-133. ISBN 84-87021-13.3.

4.- Posadas, A.M., Vidal, F., De Miguel, F., Alguacil, G., Peña, J.A., Morales, J., Ibáñez, J.M. & Romacho, M.D. (1991). "Caracterización de sistemas de fracturas sísmicamente activas y su evolución temporal mediante el programa ACP". En *Instrumentación y Proceso de Datos en Ciencias de la Tierra*. Ed. Alicia García. Serie Casa de los Volcanes, Cabildo Insular de Lanzarote, 1, 135-150. ISBN 84-87021-13.3.

1996:

5.- Del Pezzo, E., Simini, M. & Ibáñez, J.M. (1996). Separation of intrinsic and scattering Q for volcanic areas: a comparison between Etna and Campi Flegrei. En *Libro Homenaje en honor al profesor Fernando de Miguel Martínez*. F. Vidal y M. Espinar editores. Servicio de Publicaciones de la Universidad de Granada.: 579-588.

6.- Ibáñez, J.M, Del Pezzo, E. & Akinci A. (1996). Separación de la Atenuación intrínseca y de scattering en el Sur de España. En *Libro Homenaje en honor al profesor Fernando de Miguel Martínez*. F. Vidal y M. Espinar editores. Servicio de Publicaciones de la Universidad de Granada.: 263-286.

7.- Kagawa, T., Vidal F., Alguacil G., Ibáñez J.M., Morales J., Martín J.B., Almendros

J., Navarro M., Seo K., Horike, M., Samano T., Iwata T., Tsurugi M., Kurita K. & K. Hatayama (1996). Microtremor array observation in the Granada basin, Southern Spain. Libro Homenaje en honor al profesor Fernando de Miguel Martínez. F. Vidal y M. Espinar editores. Servicio de Publicaciones de la Universidad de Granada.: 287-304.

2000.

8.- Abril, M. & J.M. Ibáñez (2000). Uso de antenas sísmicas en ambientes volcánicos. En Curso internacional de volcanología y geofísica volcánica. Ed. Mar Astiz y Alicia García. Serie Casa de los Volcanes, Cabildo Insular de Lanzarote, 7, 283-296. ISBN 84-87021-74.3.

9.- Ibáñez, J.M. & E. Carmona (2000). Sismicidad volcánica. En Curso internacional de volcanología y geofísica volcánica. Ed. Mar Astiz y Alicia García. Serie Casa de los Volcanes, Cabildo Insular de Lanzarote, 7, 269-282. ISBN 84-87021-74.3.

2008.

10.- Góngora, E., Wallenstein, N., Ibáñez, J.M., Carmona, E. and Posadas, A. Utilização da análise das componentes principais (ACP) no estudo da geometria da fonte na crise sísmica do Faial, entre 1998 e 2002. Ed. Sousa Oliveira, Aníbal Costa and Joao C. Nunes. En Sismo 1998-Açores. Uma Década Depois, pp. 111-118. ISBN 978-989-20-1223-0. Editorial SPRHI, S.A.

2009.

11.- Benítez, M.C., Ibáñez, J.M., García, L., Gutiérrez, L., Cortés, G. & Álvarez, I. Analysis of volcanic seismicity at Deception Island, Stromboli and Mt. Etna volcanoes using an automatic CHMM-based recognition method. Ed. Bean, Braidon, Lockmer, Martini and O'Brien. The VOLUME project. VOLcanoes: Understanding subsurface mass movement. Printed by jaycee. ISBN: 978-1-905254-39-2, pp 140-149.

12.- Benítez, M.C., Lesage, P., Cortés, G., Segura, J.C., Ibáñez, J.M., & de la Torre, A., Automatic recognition of volcano-seismic events based on Continuous Hidden Markov Models. Ed. Bean, Braidon, Lockmer, Martini and O'Brien. The VOLUME project. VOLcanoes: Understanding subsurface mass movement. Printed by jaycee. ISBN: 978-1-905254-39-2, pp 130-139.

13.- Caselli, A., Vélez, M.L., Agosto, M.R., Bengoa, C.L. Euillades, P.A. & Ibáñez, J.M. (2009), Copahue volcano (Argentina): A relationship between ground deformation, seismic activity and geochemical changes. Ed. Bean, Braidon, Lockmer, Martini and O'Brien. The VOLUME project. VOLcanoes: Understanding subsurface mass movement. Printed by jaycee. ISBN: 978-1-905254-39-2, pp 309-318.

14.- Cortés, G., Arámbula, R., Alvarez, I., Benítez, C., Ibáñez, J.M., Lesage, P., González-Amézcuca, M. & Reyes-Dávila, G. Analysis of Colima, Popocatepetl and Arenal volcanic seismicity using an automatic Continuous Hidden Markov Model-based recognition system. Ed. Bean, Braidon, Lockmer, Martini and O'Brien. The VOLUME project. VOLcanoes: Understanding subsurface mass movement. Printed by jaycee. 207-216, pp 150-159.

15.- Ibáñez, J.M., Orozco-Rojas, J., Cisneros, M., Bretón, M., Caselli, A., Bengoa, C., Palo, M., Almendros, J., García-Yeguas, A., Carrión, F. & Alguacil, G. The use of seismic arrays to track seismo-volcanic activity, examples from Colima and Copahue volcanoes. Ed. Bean, Braidon, Lockmer, Martini and O'Brien. The VOLUME project. VOLcanoes: Understanding subsurface mass movement. Printed by jaycee. ISBN: 978-1-905254-39-2, pp 227-236.

16.- Ibáñez, J.M., Saccorotti, G., La Rocca, M., Del Pezzo, E., Zuccarello, L. & Alguacil, G., The use of seismic arrays to study the seismo-volcanic source. The example of Mt. Etna and Stromboli volcano. Ed. Bean, Braiden, Lockmer, Martini and O'Brien. The VOLUME project. VOLcanoes: Understanding subsurface mass movement. Printed by jaycee. ISBN: 978-1-905254-39-2, pp 217-226.

17.- Wallenstein, N., Silva, R., Riedel, C., Lopez, C., Ibáñez, J.M., Silveira, D. & Montalvo, A., Recent developments in seismic studies in the Fogo-Congro área, São Miguel Island, Azores. Ed. Bean, Braiden, Lockmer, Martini and O'Brien. The VOLUME project. VOLcanoes: Understanding subsurface mass movement. Printed by jaycee. ISBN: 978-1-905254-39-2, pp 207-216.

2011

18.- Gutiérrez, L., Ramírez, J., Ibáñez, J.M. and Benítez, C. (2011). "Volcano-seismic signal detection and classification processing using Hidden Markov Models. Application to San Cristóbal and Telica volcanoes, Nicaragua". In "Hidden Markov Models, Theory and Applications. Ed. By INTECH Open access publisher. Pp 187-206. ISBN 978-953-307-208-1.

2012.

20.- Carmona, E., Almendros, J., Martín, R., Cortés, G., Alguacil, G., Moreno, J., Martín, B., Martos, A., Serrano, I., Stich, D., Ibáñez, J. M., Recent advances in seismic monitoring at Deception Island volcano (Antarctica). Springer book series.

2014.

21.- Vilchez-González, J.M., Prudencio, J., Urbano-Rodríguez, L., Ibáñez, J.M. and Castillo Rosúa, F.J., (2014). El conocimiento sobre volcanes en educación primaria. In book: Vivencias innovadoras en las aulas de primaria, Edition: 1, Publisher: Editum, Editors: Javier J. Maquillón Sánchez, Andrés Escarbajal Frutos, Rosa Nortes Martínez-Artero, pp.464-477

2024.

22.- Bretón, M. and Ibáñez, J.M. Is the Tonga Eruption (2022) a New Climate Change Threat for the Pacific Basin?. in Transition to a Safe Anthropocene in the Asia-Pacific: Sustainability, Climate Action, and Green Technology ed. Dra. Antonina Ivanova Boncheva and Dr. José Ernesto Rangel Delgado. Springer.

ARTICLES IN SPECIALIZED JOURNALS.

1987:

1.- Ibáñez, J.M., De Miguel, F. & Vidal F., (1987). Métodos para la estimación fiable de la profundidad focal de sismos locales. Aplicación a Terremotos registrados por la Red Sísmica de la Universidad de Granada. Publicación del Observatorio de Cartuja. Report 1/1987, pp. 24.

1989:

2.- Del Pezzo, E., De Martino, S., Grozea, B., De Miguel, F., Ibáñez, J.M. & Sorgente, A. (1989). Caratteristiche dell'attenuazione sismica in due aree tettonicamente attive del Sud Europa. Atti del 8° convegno annuale Gruppo Nazionale di Geofisica della Terra Solida. Roma. CNR

3.- Del Pezzo, E., Neri G., Patané D., Privitera, E., Cocina, O. & Ibáñez, J.M. (1989). Studio del fattore de qualita in aree volcaniche della Sicilia. Atti Conv. Gruppo Nazionale Vulcanologia, Vol. 1, 199-207.

4.- Patané, D., Del Pezzo, E., & Ibáñez J.M. (1989). Studio dell'attenuazione sismica all'Etna mediante parametrizzazione non lineare. Atti del 8° convegno annuale Gruppo Nazionale di Geofisica della Terra Solida. Roma. CNR

1990:

5.- Ekström, G., Dziewonski, A.M. & Ibáñez, J.M. (1990). Deep earthquakes outside slabs. EmsTrans, EOS, 71, 1462. (Abstract).

6.- Ibáñez, J.M., Del Pezzo, E., De Miguel, F., Herraiz, M., Alguacil, G. & Morales, J., (1990). Depth dependence seismic attenuation in Granada zone (South Spain). Bull. Seism. Soc. Am., 80, 1232-1244.

7.- Morales, J., Vidal, F., De Miguel, F., Alguacil, G., Posadas, A.M., Ibáñez, J.M., Guzmán, A., Guirao, J.M., (1990). Basement structure of the Granada basin. Betic Cordilleras. (Southern Spain). TECTONOPHYSIC, 177, 337-348

1991:

8.- Canas, J.A., Pujades, LL., Badal, J.I., Payo, G., De Miguel, F., Vidal, F., Alguacil, G., Ibáñez, J.M. & Morales, J., (1991). Lateral variation and frequency dependence of coda-Q in the Southern part of Iberia. Geophys. J. Int. Vol. 107, 57-66.

9.- Carreño, E., Sanchez-Venero, M., García, C., Herráiz, M., Udías, A., Ibáñez, J.M., Morales, J., López-Casado, C. & Sanz De Galdeano, C. (1991). Microsismicidad de la región Granada-Málaga, Sur de España. Revista de Geofísica, Vol. 47, 93-102.

10.- Del Pezzo, E., De Martino, S., De Miguel, F., Ibáñez, J.M. & Sorgente, S., (1991). Characteristics of the seismic attenuation in two tectonically active zones of the Southern Europe. Pure and Appl. Geophy. 135, 1-16.

11.- Ibáñez, J.M., De Miguel, F., Alguacil, G., Morales, J., Del Pezzo, E., Vidal, F. & Posadas, A.M. (1991). Análisis de Q-coda en las Béticas Centrales con datos digitales. Revista de Geofísica, Vol. 47., 59-74.

12.- Ibáñez, J.M., De Miguel, F., Del Pezzo, E., Patane, D. & Morales, J. (1991). Estudio de la Atenuación sísmica mediante parametrización no lineal. Anales de Física, 87, 263-270.

13.- Ibáñez, J.M., Morales, J., De Miguel, F., Vidal, F., Alguacil, G., & Posadas A., (1991). Effect of a sedimentary basin on estimations of Q_c and Q_{Lg} . Phys. Earth Planet. Inter.

66, 244-252.

14.- Morales, J., Vidal, F., Peña, J., Alguacil, G. & Ibáñez, J.M. (1991). Microtremor study in the sediment filled basin of Zafarraya, Granada (Southern Spain). *Bull. Soc. Seism. Am.*, 81, 687-693.

15.- Morales, J., Ibáñez, J.M., Vidal, F., De Miguel, F., Alguacil, G. & A.M. Posadas (1991). Q_c site dependence in the Granada Basin (Southern Spain). *Bull. Soc. Seism. Am.*, Vol. 81, 2486-2492.

16.- Morales, J., Seo, K., Samano, T., Peña, J.A., Ibáñez, J.M. & Vidal, F. (1991). Site effect on seismic motion in Granada Basin, Southern Spain, based on microtremors measurement and site-dependence Q_c value. *Earthquake seismology. Earthquake engineering*. 38, 15-44.

1992:

17.- Del Pezzo, E., De Martino, S., De Miguel, F., Ibáñez, J.M. & Sabbarese, C., (1992). Misura del coefficiente di attenuazione geometrica in sismologia. *Atti dell 111 - C.N.G.N.Geof.T.S.*, Roma 9-11 Dicembre 1992, 405-419.

18.- De Miguel, F., Ibáñez, J.M., Alguacil, G., Canas, J.A., Vidal, F., Morales, J., Peña, J.A., Posadas, A.M., & Luzón, F. (1992). 1 to 18 Hz Lg attenuation in Granada Basin (Southern Spain). *Geophys. J. Int.* 111, 270-280.

19.- Ibáñez, J.M., Ekström, G. & Dziewonski, A.M. (1992). Los modelos de subducción y su relación con la dinámica terrestre. *Rev. de Geofísica*, 48, 179-197.

1993:

20.- Ibáñez, J.M., E. Del Pezzo, M. Martini, D. Patane, F., De Miguel, F., Vidal & J. Morales (1993). Estimates of coda-Q using a non-linear regression. *Journ. Phys. Earth*, 41, 203-219.

21.- Ibáñez, J.M., Del Pezzo, E., Alguacil, G., De Miguel, F., Morales, J., De Martino, S., Sabbarese, C & Posadas, A.M. (1993). Geometrical spreading function for short period S and coda waves recorded in Southern Spain. *Phys. Earth Planet. Inter.* 80, 25-36.

22.- Morales, J., Seo, K., Samano, T., Peña, J.A., Ibáñez, J.M. & Vidal, F. (1993). The response on seismic motion in the Granada Basin (Southern Spain) based on microtremor measurements. *Jour. Phys. Earth*. 41, 219-240.

23.- Peña, J.A., Vidal, F., Posadas, A.M., Morales, J., Alguacil, G. De Miguel, F., Ibáñez, J.M., Romacho, M.D., López-Linares, A. Space clustering properties of the Betic Alboran earthquakes in the period 1962-1989. *Tectonophysics*, 221, 125-134.

24.- Posadas, A.M., Vidal, F., De Miguel, F., Peña, J., Alguacil, G., Ibáñez, J.M. & Morales, J. (1993). Spatial-temporal analysis of a seismic swarm using the principal component analysis. The Antequera swarm (Spain), 1989. *Journ. Geophys. Res.*, 98, 1923-1932.

25.- Posadas, A.M., Vidal, F., Morales, J., Peña, J.A., Ibáñez, J.M. & Luzón, F. (1993). Spatial and temporal analysis of a seismic series using a new version of three point method. Application to Antequera (Spain) 1989 earthquakes. *Phys. Earth Planet. Inter.* 80, 159-168.

1995.

26.- Akinci, A., Del Pezzo, E. & Ibáñez J.M. (1995). Separation of scattering and intrinsic attenuation in Southern Spain and Western Anatolia (Turkey). *Geophys. J. Int.*, 121, 337-353.

27.- Akinci A., Ibáñez, J.M., Del Pezzo, E. & Morales J. (1995). Geometrical spreading and attenuation of Lg waves: a comparison between Western Anatolia (Turkey) and Southern Spain. *Tectonophysics*, 250, 47-50.

28.- Del Pezzo, E., Ibáñez, J.M., Morales, J. Akinci, A. & Maresca R. (1995). Measurements of intrinsic and scattering seismic attenuation in the crust. *Bull. Seism. Soc. Am.*, 85, 1373-1380.

1996.

29.- Del Pezzo, E., Simini, M. & Ibáñez J.M. (1996). Separation of intrinsic and scattering Q for volcanic areas: a comparison between Etna and Campi Flegrei. *Jour. Vol. Geoth. Res.*, 70, 213-219.

1997.

30.- Almendros, J., Ibáñez, J.M., Alguacil, G., Del Pezzo, E. & Ortiz, R. (1997). Array tracking of the volcanic tremor source at Deception Island, Antarctica. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 24, 3069-3072.

31.- Del Pezzo, E., La Rocca, M. & Ibáñez, J.M. (1997). Observation of high frequency scattered waves using dense arrays at Teide Volcano. *Bull. Seism. Soc. Am.*, 87, 1637-1647.

32.- García, A., Blanco, I., Torta, J.M., Astiz, M.M., Ibáñez, J.M. and Ortiz, T. (1997). A search for the volcanomagnetic signal at Deception Volcano (South Shetland I., Antarctica). *Annali di Geofisica*, XL, 319-327.

33.- Ibáñez, J.M., Morales, J., Alguacil, G., Almendros, J., Ortiz, R. and Del Pezzo, e. (1997). Intermediate-focus earthquakes under South Shetland Islands (Antarctica). *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 24, 531-534.

34.- Ibáñez, J.M., Morales, J., Alguacil, G., Almendros, J., Ortiz, R., Del Pezzo, E., Posadas, A. & Luzón, F. (1997). Actividad sísmica regional alrededor de las Islas Livingston y Decepción entre 1992 y 1996: terremotos superficiales y profundos. *Boletín de la RSEHN*, 93, 93-101.

35.- Ibáñez, J.M, Almendros, J., Alguacil, G., Morales, J., Del Pezzo, E., Ortiz, R. (1997). Eventos sísmicos de largo periodo en la isla Decepción: evidencias de una zona volcánica activa. *Boletín de la RSEHN*, 93, 103-110.

36.- Ortiz, R., García, A., Aparicio, A., Blanco, I., Felpeto, A., Del Rey, R., Villegas, M., Ibáñez, J.M., Morales, J., Del Pezzo, E., Olmedillas, J.C., Astiz, M., Vila, J., Ramos, M., Viramonte, J.G., Risso, C. & Caselli A. (1997). Monitoring of the volcanic activity of Deception Island, South Shetland Islands, Antarctica (1986-1995). *Terra Antarctica*, Special issue The Antarctic region: Geological evolution and Processes. 1071-1076.

1999.

37.- Alguacil, G., Almendros, J., Del Pezzo, E., García, A., Ibáñez, J.M., La Rocca, M., Morales, J. & Ortiz, R., (1999). Observations of volcanic earthquakes and tremor at Deception island – Antarctica. *Annali di Geofisica*, 42, 417-436.

38.- Almendros, J., Ibáñez, J.M., Alguacil, G. & Del Pezzo, E., (1999). Array analysis using circular wave-front geometry: an application to locate the nearby seismo-volcanic source. *Geophys. J. Int.*, 135, 159-172.

39.- Bianco, F., Castellano, M., Del Pezzo, E. & Ibáñez, J.M., (1999). Attenuation of the short period seismic waves at Mt. Vesuvius, Italy. *Geophys. J. Int.*, 138, 67-76

2000.

40.- Almendros, J., Ibáñez, J.M., Alguacil, G., Morales, J., Del Pezzo, E., La Rocca, M., Ortiz, R., Araña, V. & Blanco M.J. (2000). A double seismic antenna experiment at Teide Volcano: existence of local seismicity and evidence for the non existence of volcanic tremor. *Jour. Vol. Geoth. Res.*, 103, 439-462.

41.- Ibáñez, J.M., Del Pezzo, E., Almendros, J., La Rocca, M., Alguacil, G., Ortiz, R. & García A. (2000). Seismo volcanic signals at Deception Island volcano (Antarctica): wavefield analysis and source modeling. *Journ. Geophys. Res.* 105, nº 6, 13905-13931.

42.- La Rocca, M., Petrosino, S., Saccorotti, G., Simini, M., Ibáñez, J.M., Almendros, J. & Del Pezzo, E. (2000). Location of the source and shallow velocity model deduced by the explosion quakes recorded by two seismic antennas at Stromboli volcano. *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth*, 25, 731-736.

2001

43.- Ibáñez, JM, C Bottari, JA Esquivel, J Morales, G Alguacil Magnitude-intensity relations for instrumental and historical (IX-XIX century) earthquakes in south Spain. Tectonical and seismic hazard implications. *Bull. Seism. Soc. Am*, 2001

44.- Saccorotti, G., Almendros, J., Carmona, E., Ibáñez, J.M., & Del Pezzo, E. (2001). Slowness anomalies from two dense seismic arrays at Deception Island, Antarctica. *Bull. Seism. Soc. Am.* 91, 561-571.

2002

45.- Bianco, F., Del Pezzo, E., Castellano, M., Ibáñez, J.M., Di Luccio, F. (2002) Separation of intrinsic and scattering seismic attenuation in the Southern Apennine zone, Italy. *Geophys. Journal. Int.*, 150, 10-22.

46.- Muñoz, D., Cisternas, A., Udías, A., Mezcua, J., Sanz de Galdeano, C., Morales, J., Sánchez-Venero, M., Haessler, H., Ibáñez, J.M., Buforn, E., Pascual, G., Rivera, L., (2002). Micriseismicity and tectonics in the Granada Basin (Spain). *Tectonophysics*, 356, 233-252.

47.- Saccorotti, G., Carmona, E., Ibáñez, J.M. & Del Pezzo, E. (2002). Spatial characterization of the Agron, southern Spain, 1988-1989 seismic series. *Phys. Earth Planet. Int.*, 129, 13-29.

2003.

48.- Havskov, J., Peña, J.A., Ibáñez, J.M., Ottemöller, L. Martínez-Arévalo, C. (2003). Magnitude scales for very local earthquakes. Application for Deception Island volcano (Antarctica). *Journ. Vol. Geo. Res.* , 128, 115-133.

49.- Ibáñez, J.M., Carmona, E., Almendros, J., Saccorotti, G., Del Pezzo, E., Abril, M., Ortiz, R. (2003). The 1998-1999 seismic series at Deception Island volcano, Antarctica. *Journ. Vol. Geo. Res.* , 128, 65-88.

50.- Ibáñez, J.M., Almendros, J., Carmona, E., Martínez-Arévalo, C, Abril, M. (2003). The recent seismo-volcanic activity at Deception Island volcano. *Deep-Sea Research, Part II. In a special vol. ERUPT: Ecosystem studies of an enclosed bay within Deception Island, Antarctica*, ed. K. Smith. 50, 1611-1629 (2003).

51.- Martínez-Arévalo, C, Bianco, F., Ibáñez, J.M., Del Pezzo, E., (2003). Shallow seismic attenuation and shear waves splitting in the short period range of Deception Island volcano (Antarctica). *Journ. Vol. Geo. Res.* , 128, 89-113.

2004.

52.- Almendros, J., Carmona, E., Ibáñez, J. M., 2004. Precise determination of the relative wave propagation parameters of similar events using a small-aperture seismic array, *Journ. Geophys. Res.* , 109, 11308-11324.

53.- La Rocca, M., Saccorotti, G., Del Pezzo, E., Ibáñez, J. (2004). Probabilistic source location of Explosion Quakes at Stromboli volcano estimated with double array data. *Journ. Vol. Geo. Res.* 131, 123-142.

54.- Saccorotti, G., Zuccarello, L., Del Pezzo, E., Ibáñez, J.M, and Gresta, S. (2004). Quantitative analysis of the tremor wavefield at Etna volcano, Italy. *Journ. Vol. Geo. Res.* , 136, 223-245.

55.- Saccorotti, G., Wallenstein, N., Ibáñez, J., Bonagura, M. T., Damiano, N., La Rocca, M., ... & Zandomenighi, D. (2004). A seismic field survey at Fogo Furnas volcanoes, São Miguel island, Azores. In *Geophysical Research Abstracts* (Vol. 6, p. 04493).

2005.

56.- Fernández-Ibáñez, F., Pérez-López, R., Martínez-Díaz, J.J., Paredes, C., Giner-Robles, J.L., Caselli, A.T., Ibáñez, J.M. (2005). Costa Recta beach of Deception Island: is it a retreated scarp of a submarine fault? (Occidental Antarctica). *Antarctic Science*. [Volume 17, Issue 03](#), septiembre 2005, pp 418-426.

57.- Martínez-Arevalo C., Patané D., Rietbock A., Ibáñez J.M. (2005). The intrusive process leading to the Mt. Etna 2011 flank eruption: Constrain from 3-D attenuation tomography. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 32, 21309-21313.

58.- Tuvé, T., Teramo, A., Ibáñez, J.M., Bottari, C., Termini, D. (2005) Macroseismic intensity modelling of earthquakes in Southern Spain: attenuation and tectonic implications. *PAGEOPHS*, 162, 747-760.

2006.

59.- Benítez, C., J. Ramírez, J. C. Segura, A. Rubio, J. M. Ibáñez, J. Almendros, A. García Yeguas (2006). Continuous HMM-Based Volcano Monitoring At Deception Island, Antarctica. *IEEE International Conference on Acoustics Speech and Signal Processing*, May. [Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing, 2006. ICASSP 2006 Proceedings. 2006 IEEE International Conference on](#) Volume: 5, On page(s): V-VISSN: 1520-6149 ISBN: 1-4244-0469-X INSPEC Accession Number: 9174974 Digital Object Identifier: 10.1109/ICASSP.2006.1661384

60.- Gutiérrez, L., Ramírez, J., Benítez, C., Ibáñez, J., Almendros, J., & García-Yeguas, A. (2006). HMM-based classification of seismic events recorded at Stromboli and Etna volcanoes. In *2006 IEEE International Symposium on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* (pp. 2765-2768). IEEE.

61.- Tuvé, T., Bianco, F., Ibáñez, J.M., Patané, D., Del Pezzo, E., and Bottari, A. (2006). Attenuation study in the Straits of Messina area (Southern Italy). *Tectonophysics*, 421, 173-185

2007.

62.- Almendros J., Ibáñez, J.M., Carmona, E., and Zandomenighi, D. (2007). Array analyses of volcanic earthquakes and tremor recorded at Las Cañadas caldera (Tenerife Island, Spain), during the May 2004 seismic activation of Teide volcano. *Journ. Vol. Geoth. Res.*, 160, 285-299.

63.- Badi, G., Ibáñez, J.M. and Sabbione, N. (2007). Atenuación sísmica de corto periodo en la región de Nuevo Cuyo. *GEOACTA*, 32, 193-206.

64.- Benítez, C., J. Ramírez, J. C. Segura, J. M. Ibáñez, J. Almendros, A. García-Yeguas and Cortés, G. (2007). Continuous HMM-based seismic event classification at Deception Island, Antarctica. *IEEE Transactions On Geoscience And Remote Sensing*, Vol, 44, n, 12, 40-49.

65.- Caselli, A.T., G. Badi, A. L. Bonatto, C. L. Bengoa, M. R. Agosto, A. Bidone y J. Ibáñez (2007). Actividad Sísmica Y Composición Química Fumarólica Anómala Debido A Posible Efecto Sello En El Sistema Volcánico, Isla Decepción (Antártida). *Revista de la Asociación Geológica Argentina* 62 (4): 545-552 (2007) 545.

66.- Valero-Navarro, A., Fernández-Sánchez, J.F., Medina-Castillo, A.L., Fernández-Ibáñez, F., Segura-Carretero, A., Ibáñez, J.M. and Fernandez-Guriérrez, A. (2007). Rapid and sensible screening test of water for Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons: Screening of drinking, waste and Antarctic water samples. *CHEMOSPHERE*, 67, 903-910, doi10.1016.

2008.

67.- Ibáñez, J.M., Del Pezzo, E., Bengoa, C., Caselli, A., Badi, G. and Almendros, J. (2008). Volcanic tremor and local earthquakes at Copahue volcano, Southern Andes, Argentina. *Journ. Vol. Geoth. Res.* 174, 184-294.

68.- Ibáñez, J.M., A. Rietbrock and A. García-Yeguas. Imaging an Active Volcano Edifice at Tenerife Island, Spain. (2008) *EOS, TRANSACTIONS AMERICAN GEOPHYSICAL UNION*, VOL. 89, NO. 32, doi:10.1029/2008EO320001, 289-290. 2008

69.- Zandomenghi, D., Almendros, J., Ibáñez, J.M. and Saccorotti (2008). Seismic Tomography of Central São Miguel, Azores. *Phys. Earth. Planet. Interior*, 167, 8-18.

2009

70.- Badi, G., E. Del Pezzo, J.M. Ibanez, F. Bianco, N. Sabbione, and M. Araujo Depth Dependent Seismic Scattering Attenuation In The Nuevo Cuyo Region (Southern Central Andes). *Geophysical Research Letter*. VOL. 36, L24307, 5 PP., 2009. doi:10.1029/2009GL041081

71.- Barclay, A., Wilcock, W and Ibáñez, J.M. (2009). Bathymetric constraints on the tectonic and volcanic evolution of Deception Island Volcano, South Shetland Islands. *Antarctic Science*, Vol, 21, n, 1, 153-167. doi:10.1017/S0954102008001673 .

72.- Ben-Zvi, T., Wilcock, W.S.D., Barclay A.H., Zandomenghi, D., Ibáñez, J.M. and Almendros J. (2009). The P-wave velocity structure of Deception Island, Antarctica, from two-dimensional seismic tomography. *Journ. Vol. Geotherm. Res.*, 180, 67-80.

73.- Carmona, E., Stich, D., Saccorotti, G., and Ibáñez, J.M. Multiplet focal mechanisms from polarities and relative locations: The Iznajar swarm (S-Spain). *Bull. Seism. Soc. Am.*, 99, doi:10.1785/0120090036.

74.- Cortés, G., Arámbula, R., Gutiérrez, L., Benítez, C., Ibáñez, J., Lesage, P., ... & Garcia, L. (2009). Evaluating robustness of a HMM-based classification system of volcano-seismic events at Colima and Popocatepetl volcanoes. In *Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium, 2009 IEEE International, IGARSS 2009* (Vol. 2, pp. 1012-1015). IEEE. doi: 10.1109/IGARSS.2009.5417428.

75.- Gutiérrez, L., Ibáñez, J., Cortés, G., Ramírez, J., Benítez, C., Tenorio, V., & Alvarez, I. (2009). Volcano-seismic signal detection and classification processing using hidden Markov models. Application to San Cristóbal volcano, Nicaragua. In *Geoscience and*

Remote Sensing Symposium, 2009 IEEE International, IGARSS 2009 (Vol. 4, pp. IV-522). IEEE. doi: 10.1109/IGARSS.2009.5417428.

76.- Ibáñez, J. M., Benítez C., Gutiérrez, L. A., Cortés, G., García-Yeguas A. and Alguacil, G. (2009). Discrimination between different volcanic signals using Hidden Markov Model: an example of Stromboli and Etna volcanoes. *Journ. Vol. Geotherm. Res.*, 187, 218-226. Doi 10.1016/j.jvolgeores. 2009.09.002.

77.- Palo, M., Ibáñez, J.M., Cisneros, M., Bretón, M., Del Pezzo, E., Ocaña, E. and Posadas, A. (2009). Analysis of the wavefield properties of the volcanic explosions at Volcán de Colima, México: insight of the source mechanism. *Geophys. Journ. Int.*, 177, 1383-1398.

78.- Zandomenighi, D., Barclay, A., Almendros, J., Ibáñez, J.M., Wilcock, W.S.D and Ben-Zvi, T. (2009). Crustal Structure of Deception Island Volcano from P-wave Seismic Tomography: Tectonic and Volcanic Implications. *Journ. Geophys. Res* 114, B06310, doi:10.1029/2008JB006119

2010

79.- Carmona, E., Almendros, J., Peña, J.A. and Ibáñez, J.M. (2010). Characterization of fracture systems using precise array locations of earthquake multiplets: An example at Deception Island volcano, Antarctica. *Journ. Geophys. Res.*, 115, 1-20. Doi: 10.1029/2009JB006865, 2010.

2011

80.- García-Yeguas, A., Almendros, J., Abella, R. and Ibáñez, J.M. (2011). Quantitative analysis of seismic wave propagation anomalies in azimuth and apparent slowness at Deception Island volcano (Antarctica) using seismic arrays. *Geophys. Journ. Int.*, Vol. 184, Issue 2, 801–815. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-246X.2010.04864.x

81.- Petrosino, S., Cusano, P., La Rocca, M., Galluzzo, D., Orozco-Rojas, J., Bretón, M., Ibáñez, J.M. and Del Pezzo, E. (2011). Source location of long period and low frequency seismicity at Colima volcano. *Bull. Of Volcanology*, 73, 887-898, DOI: 10.1007/s00445-011-0447-2.

2012

82.- Carmona E., Almendros J., Serrano I., Stich D., Ibáñez J. M. Results from seismic monitoring surveys at Deception Island Volcano (Antarctica) from 1999 to 2011. (2012) *Antarctic Science*. 24, 485-499 doi:10.1017/S0954102012000314.

83.- De Barros L., Martini, F, Bean, C.J, Garcia-Yeguas, A., Ibáñez, J.M. Imaging magma storage below Teide volcano (Tenerife) using scattered seismic wavefields (2012). *Geophys. Journ. Int.*, 191, 695-706, doi: 10.1111/j.1365-246X.2012.05637.x.

84.- De Lauro, E. S. De Martino, M. Palo, and J.M. Ibáñez. Self-sustained oscillations at Volcán de Colima (Mexico) inferred by Independent Component Analysis (2012). *Bull. Of Volcanology*, 74, 279-292. DOI 10.1007/s00445-011-0520-x.

85.- García-Yeguas, A., Kulaikov, I., Ibáñez, J.M., Rietbrock, A. High resolution 3D P wave velocity structure beneath Tenerife Island (Canary Islands, Spain) based on tomographic inversion of active-source data (2012). *Journ. Geophys. Res.*, doi:10.1029/2011JB008970.

86.- Ibáñez, J.M., De Angelis, S., Díaz-Moreno, A., Hernández, P., Alguacil, G., Posadas, A.M. and Pérez, N. (2012), Insights Into The 2011-2012 Submarine Eruption Off The Coast Of El Hierro (Canary Islands, Spain) From Statistical Analyses Of Earthquake Activity. *Geophys. Journ. Int.*, 191, 659-670. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-246X.2012.05629.x.

87.- Lodge, A., S.E.J. Nippress, A. Rietbrock, A. García-Yeguas and J.M. Ibáñez (2012). Evidence for magmatic underplating and magma chambers beneath the Canary Islands derived using teleseismic receiver functions. *Phys. Earth Planet. Int.* 212-213, 44-54.

88.- Mancilla, F., E. Del Pezzo, D. Stich, J. Morales, J. M. Ibañez, and F. Bianco (2012). Q_P and Q_S in the upper mantle beneath the Iberian peninsula from recordings of the very deep Granada earthquake of April 11, 2010. *Geophysical Research Letter*. VOL. 39, L09303, doi:10.1029/2012GL050947

89.- Scarfi, L., Raffaele, R., Badi, G., Ibáñez, J.M. Imposta, S., Araujo, M., and Sabbione, N. (2012) Seismotectonic features from accurate hypocentre locations in Southern Central Andes (Western Argentina). *Tectonophysics* 518-521, 44-54. DOI 10.1016/j.tecto.2011.11.009.

2013.

90.- Prudencio, J., Del Pezzo, E., García-Yeguas, A., Ibáñez, J.M., (2013) Spatial distribution of intrinsic and scattering seismic attenuation in active volcanic islands, I: model and the case of Tenerife Island. *Geophy. Journ. Int.*, VOL, 195, 1942-1956. DOI 10.1093/gji/ggt361.

91.- Prudencio, J., Ibáñez, J.M., García-Yeguas, A., Del Pezzo, E. and A. Posadas, (2013) Spatial distribution of intrinsic and scattering seismic attenuation in active volcanic islands: II Deception island images. *Geophy. Journ. Int.*, VOL 195, 1957-1969. DOI 10.1093/gji/ggt360.

2014.

92.- Carmona, E., Almendros, J., Martín, R., Cortés, G., Alguacil, G, Moreno, J., Martín, J.B., Martos, A., Serrano I., Stich, D. and Ibáñez J.M. (2014). Advances in seismic monitoring at Deception Island volcano (Antarctica) since the International Polar Year. *Annals of Geophysics*, 57, 3, doi:10.4401/ag-6378.

93.- Cortés, G., García, L., Alvarez, I., Benítez, C., De la Torre, A. and Ibáñez, J.M. (2014), Parallel System Architecture (PSA): An efficient approach for Automatic Recognition of Volcano-Seismic Events. *Jour. Vol. Geother. Res. Vol.* 271, 1-10. DOI 10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2013.07.004.

94.- García-Yeguas, A., Ibáñez, J. M., Koulakov I., Jakovlev, A., Romero-Ruiz, M.C. and Prudencio, J. (2014). Seismic tomography model reveals Mantle magma source of recent volcanic activity at El Hierro Island (Canary Islands, Spain). *Geophy. Journ. Int.*, 199, 1739–1750, 10.1093/gji/ggu339.

95.- Ontiveros-Ortega, A., Vidal, F., Giménez, E., and Ibáñez, J.M. (2014). Effect of heavy metals on the surface free energy and zeta potential of volcanic glass: implications on the adhesion and growth of microorganisms. *Journal of Materials Science* 49 (9), 3550-3559. DOI 10.1007/s10853-014-8077-7

96.- Pérez, N., L. Somoza, P. A. Hernández, L. González de Vallejo, R. León, T. Sagiya, A. Biain, F. J. González, T. Medialdea, J. Barrancos, J.M. Ibáñez, H. Sumino, K. Nogami and C. Romero-Ruiz (2014). Evidence from acoustic imaging for submarine volcanic activity in 2012 off the west coast of El Hierro (Canary Islands, Spain). *Bull. of Volcanol.*, 76:882. DOI: 10.1007/s00445-014-0882-y.

2015

97.- Carmona, E., Almendros, J., Alguacil, G., Soto, J.I., Luzón, F. and Ibáñez, J.M. (2015). Identification of T-Waves in the Alboran Sea. *Pure and Applied Geophysics*, 24 (1), 1-10. DOI 10.1007/s00024-014-1018-1.

98.- Díaz-Moreno, A., Ibáñez, J.M., De Angelis, S., García-Yeguas, A., Prudencio, J., Morales, J., Tuvè, T. and García, L. (2015). Seismic hydraulic fracture migration originated by successive deep magma pulses: The 2011–2013 seismic series associated to the volcanic activity of El Hierro Island. *Journal of Geophysical Research*. 120(11), 7749-7770 DOI 10.1002/2015JB012249.

99.- Pérez N.M., Somoza L., Hernández P. A., González de Vallejo L., León R., Sagiya T., Biain A., González F.J., Medialdea T., Barrancos J., Ibáñez J., Sumino H., Nogami K. and Romero C. (2015). Reply to comment from Blanco et al. (2015) on "Evidence from acoustic imaging for submarine volcanic activity in 2012 off the west coast of El Hierro (Canary Islands, Spain)". *Bull. Volcanol.* 77 (7) . DOI 10.1007/s00445-015-0948-5

100.- Prudencio, J., L. De Siena, J.M. Ibáñez, E. Del Pezzo, A. García-Yeguas and A. Díaz-Moreno (2015). The 3D attenuation structure of Deception Island (Antarctica). *Surveys in Geophysics*, 36 (3), 371-390. DOI: 10.1007/s10712-015-9322-6.

101.- Prudencio, J., E. Del Pezzo, J. M. Ibáñez, E. Giampiccolo and D. Patané (2015). Two-dimensional seismic attenuation images of Stromboli Island using active data. *Geoph. Res. Lett.* 42, 1–8, doi:10.1002/2015GL063293.

102.- Prudencio, J., J. M. Ibáñez, E. Del Pezzo, J. Martí, A. García-Yeguas, L. De Siena. (2015). 3D attenuation tomography of the volcanic island of Tenerife (Canary Islands, Spain). *Surveys in Geophysics*, 36, 5, 693-716. DOI 10.1007/s10712-015-9333-3.

2016

103.- Barberi, G., Giampiccolo, E., Musumeci, C., Scarfi, L., Bruno, V., Cocina, O., Díaz-Moreno, A., Sicali, S., Tusa, G., Tuvè, T., Zuccarello, L., Ibáñez J.M., and Patané, D., (2016). Seismic and Volcanic activity during 2014 in the región involved by TOMO-ETNA seismic active experiment. *Annals of Geophysics*, 59, 4 doi:10.4401/ag-7082.

104.- Cavallaro, D., Cocchi, L., Coltelli, M., Muccini, F., Carmisciano, C., Firetto-Carlino, M., Ibáñez, J.M., Patané, D., Filippone, M. and Buttaro, E., (2016). Acquisition procedures, processing methodologies and preliminary results of magnetic and ROV data collected during the TOMO-ETNA experiment. *Annals of Geophysics*, 59, 4, doi:10.4401/ag-7084.

105.- Coltelli, M., Cavallaro, D., Firetto Carlino, M., Cocchi, L., Muccini, F., D'alessandro, A., Claude, M.E, Monaco, C., Ibáñez, J.M.,... and Rapisarda, S. (2016). The marine activities performed within the TOMO-ETNA experiment. *Annals of Geophysics*, 59, 4, doi:10.4401/ag-7081.

106.- Cortés, G., Benítez, M.C., García, L., Alvarez, I. and Ibáñez, J.M. (2016). A Comparative Study of Dimensionality Reduction Algorithms Applied to Volcano-Seismic Signals. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*. Vol 9, nº 1, pp 253-263. DOI. 0.1109/JSTARS.2015.2479300.

107.- Del Pezzo, E., Ibáñez, J.M., Prudencio, J., Bianco, F., De Siena, L. (2016). Absorption and Scattering 2D Volcano Images from Numerically Calculated Space-weighting functions. *Geophys. Journal International*. doi: 10.1093/gji/ggw171.

108.- Díaz-Moreno A., Koulakov I., García-Yeguas A., Jakovlev A., Barberi, G., Cocina O., Zuccarello L., Scarfi, L., Patané, D. , Álvarez I., García L., Benítez C., Prudencio J. , Ibáñez J.M., (2016). PARTOS - Passive and Active Ray TOMography Software:

Description and preliminary analysis using TOMO-ETNA experiment's dataset. *Annals of Geophysics*, 59, 4, doi:10.4401/ag-7088.

109.- Firetto-Carlino, M., Zgur, F., Bruno, P.P., Coltelli, M., Sormani, L., Cavallaro, D., Ibáñez, J.M. and Patané, D., (2016). Acquisition and preliminary analysis of multi-channel seismic reflection data, acquired during the oceanographic cruises of the Tomo-Etna experiment. *Annals of Geophysics*, 59, 4, doi:10.4401/ag-7083.

110.- García, L., Álvarez I., Benítez, C., Titos, M., Bueno, M., Mota, S., De la Torre, A., Segura, J.C., Alguacil, G., Díaz-Moreno, A., Prudencio, J., García-Yeguas, A., Ibáñez, J.M., Zuccarello, L., Cocina, O., and Patané, D. (2016). Advances on the automatic estimation of the P-wave onset time. *Annals of Geophysics*, 59, 4, doi:10.4401/ag-7087.

111.- Ibáñez, J.M., Prudencio, J., Díaz-Moreno, A., Patané, D., Puglisi, G., Luehr, B.G., Carrión, F., Dañobeitia, J.J., Coltelli, M., Bianco, F., Del Pezzo, E., Dahm, T., Willmott, V., and Mazauric, V., (2016). The TOMO-ETNA experiment: an imaging active campaign at Mt. Etna volcano. Context, main objectives, working-plans and involved research projects. *Annals of Geophysics*, 59, 4, S0426, doi:10.4401/ag-7079.

112.- Ibáñez, J.M., Díaz-Moreno, A., Prudencio, J., Patané, D., Zuccarello, L., Cocina, O., Luehr, B., Carrion, F., Coltelli, M., Bruno, P. P., Bianco, F., Hellweg, M. Abreu, R., Alguacil, G., Alvarez, I., Aranda, C., Benítez, C., Buontempo, L., Feriche, M., García, L., Martín, J.B., Morales, J., Serrano, I., Titos, M., Urbano, L., Aiesi, G., Azzaro, R., Barberi, G., Cantarero, M., Cappuccio, P., Cavallaro, D., Contraffatto, D., La Rocca, G., Di Prima, S., Falsaperla, S., Firetto-Carlino, M., Giampiccolo, E., Musumeci, C., Pellegrino, D., Pulvirenti, M., Rapisarda, S., Sassano, M., Scarfi, L., Scuderi, L., Sicali, A., Tusa, G., Tuvè, T., Del Pezzo, E., Fiore, S., Galluzzo, D., La Rocca, M., Longobardi, M., Nocerino, L., Scognamiglio, S., Criscuoli, F., D'Alessandro, A., D'Anna, R., De Gori, P., Fertitta, G., Giovani, L., Passafiume, G., Silvestri, M., Speciale, S., Bottari, C., Cocchi, L., Muccini, F., Salimbeni, S., Dahm, T., García-Yeguas, A., Ontiveros, A., Coello, E., Cordero, M., Guillén, C., Romero, M.C., McCann, H., Bretón, M., Boyd, S., Koulakov, I., Abramenkov, S., (2016). TOMO-ETNA experiment at Etna volcano: activities on land. *Annals of Geophysics*, 59, 4, S0427, doi:10.4401/ag-7080.

113.- Monaco, C., Ibáñez, J.M., Carrión, F. and Tringali, L. M., (2016). Cetacean behavioural responses to noise exposure generated by seismic surveys: how to mitigate better?. *Annals of Geophysics*, 59, 4, doi:10.4401/ag-7089.

2017

114.- García-Yeguas, A., Ledo, J.J., Piña-Varas, P., Prudencio, J., Queralt, P., Marcuello, A., Ibáñez, J.M., Benjumea, B., Sánchez-Alzola, A. and Pérez, N., (2017). A novel 3D joint interpretation of magnetotelluric and seismic tomographic models: the case of the volcanic island of Tenerife. *Computer and Geosciences*, 109, 95–105, doi 10.1016/j.cageo.2017.08.003.

115.- Ibáñez, J.M., Díaz-Moreno, A., Prudencio, J., Zandomenighi, D., Wilcock, W., Barclay, A., Almendros, J., Benítez, C., García-Yeguas, C. and Alguacil, G., (2017). Database of multi-parametric geophysical data from the TOMO-DEC experiment on Deception Island, Antarctica. *Nature Sci. Data* 4:170128, doi: 10.1038/sdata.2017.128.

116.- Prudencio, J., Aoki, Y., Takeo, M., Ibáñez, J.M., Del Pezzo, E., and Song, W., (2017). Separation of scattering and intrinsic attenuation at Asama volcano (Japan): evidence of high volcanic structural contrasts. *Jour. Vol. Geoth. Res.*, 01, 14, doi: 10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2017.01.014.

2018

117.- Bueno, Angel, Manuel Titos, Luz García, Isaac Álvarez, Jesús Ibañez, Carmen Benítez. Classification of Volcano-Seismic Signals with Bayesian Neural Networks. 2018 26th European Signal Processing Conference (EUSIPCO). 2295-2299. 2018/9/3. DOI: 10.23919/EUSIPCO.2018.8553358. Roma, Italy, Italy

118.- Del Pezzo, E., de La Torre, A., Bianco, F., Ibañez, J.M., Gabrielli, S., and De Siena, L. (2018). Numerically Calculated 3-D Space-weighting Functions to Image Earth Structures using coda waves. *Geosciences*, 8, 175, doi:10.3390/geosciences8050175.

119.- Díaz-Moreno, A., Barberi, G., Cocina, O., Koulakov, I., Scarfi, L., Zuccarello, L., Prudencio, J., García-Yeguas, A., Alvarez, I., García, L. and Ibañez, J.M., (2018). New Insights on Mt. Etna's Crust and Relationship with the Regional Tectonic Framework from Joint Active and Passive P-Wave Seismic Tomography. *Surveys in Geophysics*. Vol 39 (1), 57-97. DOI: 10.1007/s10712-017-9425-3.

120.- Garcia-Yeguas, A., Sanchez-Alzola, A., De Siena, L., Prudencio, J., Díaz-Moreno, A., Ibañez, J.M., (2018). Scattering images from autocorrelation functions of P-wave seismic velocity images: the case of Tenerife Island (Canary Islands, Spain). *Bull. of Volcanology*. DOI: 10.1007/s00445-018-1205-5.

121.- Titos, M., Bueno, A., García, L., Benítez, C. Ibañez, J.M., (2018). Detection and Classification of Continuous Volcano-Seismic Signals with Recurrent Neural Networks. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing (TGRS)*. TGRS-2017-01491.R1. DOI: 10.1109/TGRS.2018.2870202

2019

122.- Bueno, A., Díaz-Moreno, A., De Angelis, S., Benítez, C., Ibañez, J.M. (2019). Recursive Entropy Method of Segmentation for Seismic Signals. *Seismo. Res. Letts*. <https://doi.org/10.1785/0220180317>.

123.- Bueno, A., Benítez, C., De Angelis, S., Díaz-Moreno, A., Ibañez, J.M., (2019). Volcano-Seismic Transfer Learning and Uncertainty Quantification with Bayesian Neural Networks. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing (TGRS)*. DOI 10.1109/TGRS.2019.2941494.

124.- Del Pezzo, E., E. Giampiccolo, T. Tuvé, G. Di Grazia, S. Gresta, J.M. Ibañez (2019). Study of the regional pattern of intrinsic and scattering seismic attenuation in Eastern Sicily (Italy) from local earthquakes. *Geophy. Journ. Intern.* 218(2), 1456-1468. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gji/ggz208>.

2020

125.- Del Pezzo, E., and Ibañez, J. M. (2020). Seismic Coda-Waves Imaging Based on Sensitivity Kernels Calculated Using an Heuristic Approach. *Geosciences*, 10(8), 304. <https://doi.org/10.3390/geosciences10080304>

126.- Ibañez, J. M., Castro-Melgar, I., Cocina, O., Zuccarello, L., Branca, S., Del Pezzo, E., & Prudencio, J. (2020). First 2-D intrinsic and scattering attenuation images of Mt Etna volcano and surrounding region from active seismic data. *Geophysical Journal International*, 220(1), 267-277. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gji/ggz450>

2021

127.- Bueno, A., Titos, M., Benítez, C., & Ibañez, J. M. (2021). Continuous active learning for seismo-volcanic monitoring. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, 19, 1-5.

128.- Bueno, A. Benítez, C., Zuccarello, L., De Angelis, S., Ibáñez, J.M. (2021). Bayesian Monitoring of Seismo Volcanic Dynamics. IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing (TGRS). DOI: 10.1109/TGRS.2021.3076012.

129.- Bueno, Á., Balestriero, R., De Angelis, S., Benítez, M. C., Zuccarello, L., Baraniuk, R., ... & Maarten, V. (2021). Recurrent Scattering Network detects metastable behavior in polyphonic seismo-volcanic signals for volcano eruption forecasting. IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing, 60, 1-23.

130.- Castro-Melgar, I., Prudencio, J., Del Pezzo, E., Giampiccolo, E. and Ibáñez, J.M. (2021). Shallow magma storage beneath Mt. Etna: Evidence from new attenuation tomography and existing velocity models. Journ. Geophys. Res. 10.1029/2021JB022094.

131.- Castro Melgar, I., Prudencio Soñora, J., Del Pezzo, E., & Ibáñez Godoy, J. M. (2021). Small-scale volcanic structures of the Aeolian volcanic arc revealed by seismic attenuation. 10.3389/feart.2021.725402

132.- Giampiccolo, E., Del Pezzo E., Tuvé, T., Di Grazia, T.S. and Ibáñez, J.M. (2021). 3-D Q-coda attenuation structure at Mt. Etna. Geophysical Journal International, DOI: 10.1093/gji/ggab235.

133.- Martínez, V.L., Titos, M., Benitez, C., Badi, G., Casas, J.A., Olivera Craig, V.H. & Ibáñez, J.M., (2021). Advanced Signal Recognition Methods applied to seismo-volcanic events from Planchon Peteroa Volcanic Complex: Deep Neural Network classifier. Journal of South American Earth Sciences. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsames.2020.103115>

134.- Posadas, A., Morales, J., Ibáñez, J.M. and Posadas-Garzón, A. (2021). Non-Linear Seismic Processes And The Second Law Of Thermodynamics: A Case Study From Canterbury (New Zealand). Chaos, Solitons and Fractals, 151, 111243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2021.111243>.

2022

135.- Bretón, M., Ibáñez, J. M., León, Z., Plascencia, I., Campos, A., Santiago, H., ... & De Angelis, S. (2022). Historical and morphological evidence for multi-stage growth of El Volcancito, Volcán de Colima. Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research, 421, 107447.

136.- D'Auria, L., Koulakov, I., Prudencio, J., Cabrera-Pérez, I., Ibáñez, J. M., Barrancos, J., ... & Pérez, N. M. (2022). Rapid magma ascent beneath La Palma revealed by seismic tomography. Scientific Reports, 12(1), 17654.

137.- Ibáñez, J. M., (2022). El uso de la Inteligencia Artificial (IA) para producir erupciones volcánicas. La Cueva de Nerja: un laboratorio natural para conocer los cambios climáticos pasados, presentes y futuros 7, 36-46. ISSN 1699-6305. www.pasajealaciencia.es

138.- Ibáñez, J. M., & Bretón, M. (2022). Los volcanes en la historia de la humanidad. La Cueva de Nerja: un laboratorio natural para conocer los cambios climáticos pasados, presentes y futuros 7, 58-83. ISSN 1699-6305. www.pasajealaciencia.es

139.- Ibáñez, J. M., & Prudencio, J. (2022). Radiografías de los volcanes. La Cueva de Nerja: un laboratorio natural para conocer los cambios climáticos pasados, presentes y futuros 7, 47-57. ISSN 1699-6305. www.pasajealaciencia.es

140.- Zuccarello, L., De Angelis, S., Minio, V., Saccorotti, G., Bean, C. J., Paratore, M., & Ibanez, J. M. (2022). Volcanic Tremor Tracks Changes in Multi-Vent Activity at Mt. Etna, Italy: Evidence From Analyses of Seismic Array Data. Geophysical Research Letters, 49(22), e2022GL100056.

2023

- 141.- Cabrera-Pérez, I., D'Auria, L., Soubestre, J., Przeor, M., Barrancos, J., García-Hernández, R., ... & Pérez, N. (2023). Spatio-temporal velocity variations observed during the pre-eruptive episode of La Palma 2021 eruption inferred from ambient noise interferometry. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 12039.
- 142.- Koulakov, I., D'Auria, L., Prudencio, J., Cabrera-Pérez, I., Barrancos, J., Padilla, G. D., ... & Ibáñez, J. M. (2023). Local earthquake seismic tomography reveals the link between crustal structure and volcanism in Tenerife (Canary Islands). *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 128(3), e2022JB025798.
- 143.- Ontiveros-Ortega, A., Plaza, I., Calero, J., Moleon, J. A., & Ibáñez, J. M. (2023). High variability of interaction energy between volcanic particles: implications for deposit stability. *Natural Hazards*, 1-20.
- 144.- Rey-Devesa, P., Prudencio, J., Benítez, C., Bretón, M., Plasencia, I., León, Z., ... & Ibáñez, J. M. (2023). Tracking volcanic explosions using Shannon entropy at Volcán de Colima. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 9807.
- 145.- Rey-Devesa, P., Benítez, C., Prudencio, J., Gutiérrez, L., Cortés-Moreno, G., Titos, M., ... & Ibáñez, J. M. (2023). Volcanic Early Warning Using Shannon Entropy: Multiple Cases of Study. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, e2023JB026684.
- 146.- Titos, M., Gutiérrez, L. A., Benítez, C., Rey Devesa, P., Koulakov, I., & Ibáñez, J. M. (2023). Multi-station volcano-tectonic earthquake monitoring based on transfer learning. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 11, 1204832.

PUBLIC DATA BASES AND SOFTWARE.

- 1.- IBÁÑEZ ET AL. 1994. QNONLIN. THE IASPEI PC SHAREWARE LIBRARY.
- 2.- Ibanez, Jesus M.; Lühr, Birger ; Dahm, Torsten (2014): TOMO-ETNA. GFZ Data Services. Other/Seismic Network. doi:10.14470/6G7569676919. <https://geofon.gfz-potsdam.de/doi/network/1T/2014>
- 3.- Ibanez, J.M. (2017) TOMODEC. High resolution seismic tomography of Deception Island (Antarctica), and modelling of seismo-volcanic sources. Bathymetryc data and derived products., Ver. 1, Australian Antarctic Data Centre - doi:10.4225/15/58e580cfe8c95, https://data.aad.gov.au/metadata/records/TOMODEC_2005_BATHYMETRY-SPAIN
- 4.- Ibanez, J.M. (2017) TOMODEC. High resolution seismic tomography of Deception Island (Antarctica), and modelling of seismo-volcanic sources. GRAVIMETRIC DATA, Ver. 1, Australian Antarctic Data Centre - doi:10.4225/15/58e47c33f2500 https://data.aad.gov.au/metadata/records/TOMODEC_2005_GRAVIMETRY-SPAIN
- 5.- Ibanez, J.M. (2017) TOMODEC. High resolution seismic tomography of Deception Island (Antarctica), and modelling of seismo-volcanic sources. MAGNETIC DATA, Ver. 1, Australian Antarctic Data Centre - doi:10.4225/15/58e47c1be64b8 https://data.aad.gov.au/metadata/records/TOMODEC_2005_MAGNETIC-SPAIN
- 6.- Ibanez, J.M. (2017) TOMODEC. High resolution seismic tomography of Deception Island (Antarctica), and modelling of seismo-volcanic sources. SEISMIC MODELS, Ver. 1, Australian Antarctic Data Centre - doi:10.4225/15/58e47c03e652a https://data.aad.gov.au/metadata/records/TOMODEC_2005_MODELS-SPAIN
- 7.- Ibanez, J.M. (2017) TOMODEC. High resolution seismic tomography of Deception Island (Antarctica), and modelling of seismo-volcanic sources, Ver. 1, Australian Antarctic Data Centre

https://data.aad.gov.au/metadata/records/TOMODEC_2005_PROJECT-SPAIN

8.- Ibanez, J.M. (2017) TOMODEC. High resolution seismic tomography of Deception Island (Antarctica), and modelling of seismo-volcanic sources. SEISMIC DATA, Ver. 1, Australian Antarctic Data Centre - doi:10.4225/15/58e6edfc522cf

https://data.aad.gov.au/metadata/records/TOMODEC_2005_SEISMOLOGY-SPAIN

9.- Ibanez, J.M. (2017) TOMODEC. High resolution seismic tomography of Deception Island (Antarctica), and modelling of seismo-volcanic sources. ADDITIONAL INFORMATION, Ver. 1, Australian Antarctic Data Centre - doi:10.4225/15/58e47be626ee5

https://data.aad.gov.au/metadata/records/TOMODEC_2005_UTM-SPAIN

10.- Zuccarello Luciano, Gutiérrez Ligdamis, Reitano Danilo, Alparone Salvatore, Contrafatto Danilo, Di Prima Sergio, Larocca Graziano, Rapisarda Salvatore, Scuderi Luciano, Sassano Marco, Cappuccio Pasqualino, Rey-Devesa Pablo, Benítez Carmen, Koulakov Ivan, Prudencio Janire, Ibáñez Jesús, & Cocina Ornella. (2022). Seismic dataset. Mt. Etna, November, 2013. (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6849621>

11.- Software. Analysis of Spectral Characteristics System of Seismic Records (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7008075>)

12.- Software. STA/LTA triggering methods for seismic records [OLD Version] (Ver. 1.0) (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7041962>)

13.- Software. STA/LTA triggering methods for seismic records [New Version] - (Ver. 1.1) (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7647707>)

14.- Software. System for plotting 24-hour seismic records in one-hour segments and on one continuous plot (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7714226>)

15.- Software. Converting Seismic Records to Wav sound (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7320318>)

16.- Software. Integrate Seismic Signals. (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7048873>)

17.- Software. System to select, cut and save events since seismic records (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7268903>)

18.- Software. System to select, merge and save events since seismic records (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7318039>)

19.- Software. Download Seismic Records from the FDSN network (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7612237>)

20.- Software. Individual Seismic Data Download from the FDSN network (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7750743>)

21.- Bases de datos. Database of Panama Region to determine intrinsic and scattering attenuation (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7248064>)

22.- Bases de datos. A successful short-term volcanic eruption forecasting using seismic features: datasets and Software (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6821530>)

23.- Bases de datos. Forecasting and Tracking Volcanic Explosions using Shannon Entropy at Volcán de Colima (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7732898>)

24.- Bases de datos. A multi-station volcano-tectonic earthquakes monitoring based on Transfer Learning techniques (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7755506>)

Bases de datos. Seismic dataset. Mt. Etna, November, 2013 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6849621>)

SCIENTIFIC DISSEMINATION ARTICLES AND SPECIFIC REPORTS

1.- Ibáñez, J.M., (1989). Isla Decepción, Antartida. Revista Referencias

- 2.- Ibáñez, J.M., Morales, J., García, A., Ortiz, R., Del Pezzo, E. & Risso, C. (1995). Deception Island. Bulletin of the Global Volcanism Network, 20, 14-15.
- 3.- Caselli, A.T., Bidone, A., Bengoa, C., Rojas Vera, E., Badi, G., Zandomenighi, D., Sánchez; N., Fernández, F. y Ibáñez, J. (2004). Deception Island (Antarctica) High seismicity and stable thermal activity. Bulletin of the Global Volcanism Network (Smithsonian Institution). 28, 6
- 4.- García, A., Abella, R., Ibáñez, J.M., Vidal, F., Almendros, J., Risso, C., Caselli, A., Baraldo, A. & Berrocoso, M. (1996). Deception Island. Bulletin of the Global Volcanism Network, 21, 7.
- 5.- García, A., Astiz, M.M., Villegas, M., Ibáñez, J.M., Morales, J., Carmona, E., Caselli, A., Badi, G. & Baraldo, A. (1997). Deception Island. Bulletin of the Global Volcanism Network, 22, 10.
- 6.- García, A., Ortiz, R., Ibáñez, J.M., Delpezzo, E., Almendros, J., Carmona, E., Saccortti, G. And Peña, J.A. (1999). Deception Island. Bulletin of the Global Volcanism Network, 24, 01.
- 7.- Ibáñez, J.M., Alguacil, G., Morales, J., Peña J.A., Almendros, J., Carmona, E., García, A., Ortiz, R., Del Pezzo, E., Martini, M., Chouet, B., & Saccorotti, G. (1999). Deception Island. Bulletin of the Global Volcanism Network, 24, 05.
- 8.- García, A., Ortiz, R., Ibáñez, J.M., Carmona, E., Martín, J.B., Martínez-Arévalo, C., Pérez-Cuadrado, J.L., Bretón, M. & La Rocca, M. (2001) *Deception Island*. Bulletin of the Global Volcanism Network, 26, 05.
- 9.- Global Volcanism Program, 2003. Report on Deception Island (Antarctica) (Venzke, E., ed.). Bulletin of the Global Volcanism Network, 28:6. Smithsonian Institution. <https://doi.org/10.5479/si.GVP.BGVN200306-390030>
- 10.- Global Volcanism Program, 2003. Report on Deception Island (Antarctica) (Venzke, E., ed.). Bulletin of the Global Volcanism Network, 28:2. Smithsonian Institution. <https://doi.org/10.5479/si.GVP.BGVN200302-390030>
- 11.- Global Volcanism Program, 2004. Report on Deception Island (Antarctica) (Wunderman, R., ed.). Bulletin of the Global Volcanism Network, 29:12. Smithsonian Institution. <https://doi.org/10.5479/si.GVP.BGVN200412-390030>

PRESENTATIONS AT CONFERENCES.

1987

- 1.- IBÁÑEZ, J.M., VIDAL, F. & ALGUACIL, G. (1987). Determinación de la razón de Poisson y profundidad focal de microterremotos con un método independiente del modelo de velocidades. XXI Bienal de Física 4-10 Octubre, Salamanca, pp. 387-388.

1988

- 2.- IBÁÑEZ, J.M., DE MIGUEL, F. & VIDAL, F. (1988). Estimación de velocidades medias, a distintas profundidades, con los métodos de Chapman y Bollinger en la Depresión de Granada. VI Asamblea Nacional de Geofísica y Geodesia, Madrid, 6-10 de Junio.
- 3.- DE MIGUEL, F., VIDAL, F., ALGUACIL, G., IBÁÑEZ, J.M., POSADAS, A.M. & MORALES, J. (1988). La sismicidad del sistema de fracturas Padul-Santa Fe-Pinos Puente. VI Asamblea Nacional de Geofísica y Geodesia, Madrid, 6-10 de Junio.
- 4.- ORTIZ, R., VILA, J. & IBÁÑEZ, J.M., (1988). Sismicidad en la Isla de

Decepción. Antártida. VI Asamblea Nacional de Geofísica y Geodesia, Madrid, 6-10 de Junio.

5.- ORTIZ, R., VILA, J., IBÁÑEZ, J.M. & VIRAMONTE, J.G. (1988). Estudio preliminar del campo magnético en la Isla de Decepción. Antártida. VI Asamblea Nacional de Geofísica y Geodesia, Madrid, 6-10 de Junio.

6.- VIDAL, F., MORALES, J., DE MIGUEL, F., POSADAS, A.M. & IBÁÑEZ, J.M., (1988). Los terremotos de la zona Sur de la Sierra de la Almirante y su correlación con fracturas. VI Asamblea Nacional de Geofísica y Geodesia, Madrid, 6-10 de Junio.

1989

7.- DE MIGUEL, F., IBÁÑEZ, J.M., DE MARTINO, S., DEL PEZZO, E., SORGENTE, A. & GROZZA, B., (1989). Caratteristiche dell'attenuazione sismica in due aree tettonicamente attive del Sud Europa. 8° Convegno Nazionale del Gruppo Nazionale di Geofisica della Terra Solida. Roma, Italia, 7-9 Noviembre.

8.- GARCIA, A., VIRAMONTE, J.G., VILA, J. & IBÁÑEZ, J.M., (1990). Estudio del campo magnético en Port Foster, Isla Decepción. III Simposium Antártico Español. Gredos. Octubre, 1989.

9.- PATANE', D., IBÁÑEZ, J.M. & DEL PEZZO, E., (1989). Studio dell'attenuazione sismica all'Etna mediante parametrizzazione non lineare. 8° Convegno Nazionale del Gruppo Nazionale di Geofisica della Terra Solida. Roma, Italia, 7-9 Noviembre.

1990.

10.- De Miguel, F., Ibáñez, J.M., Alguacil, G., Vidal, F., Morales, J., Peña, J.A. & Canas J.A., (1990). Q_{Lg} in Granada Basin (Southern Spain). XXII General Assembly of the European Seismological Commission, Barcelona.

11.- Ekström, G., Dziewonski, A.M. & Ibáñez, J.M. (1990). Deep earthquakes outside slabs. A. G. U. Fall Meeting, S. Francisco. December 1990

12.- Ibáñez, J.M., Del Pezzo, E., Martini, M., Patané, D., De Miguel, F. & Vidal, F., (1990). Coda-Q dependence on frequency, lapse time, site and data fitting methods. XXII General Assembly of the European Seismological Commission, Barcelona. September 1990

13.- Ibáñez, J.M., De Miguel, F., Del Pezzo, E., Herraiz, M., Morales, J., Alguacil, G., Vidal, F. & Posadas A., (1990). Coda-Q in Granada Basin (Southern Spain). XXII General Assembly of the European Seismological Commission, Barcelona. September 1990

14.- Morales, J., Vidal, F., Burillo, F.J., Peña, J.A., Alguacil, G., Ibáñez, J.M., Posadas, A.M. & De Miguel, F., (1990). Site response features of the Zafarraya basin (SE Spain) from microtremors measurement. XXII General Assembly of the European Seismological Commission, Barcelona. September 1990

15.- Peña, J.A., Vidal, F., Posadas, A.M., Morales, J., Alguacil, G., De Miguel, F., Ibáñez, J.M., Romacho, M.D. & Lopez-Linares A., (1990). Hypocentral clustering properties of Betic Earthquakes. XXII General Assembly of the European Seismological Commission, Barcelona. September 1990

16.- Posadas, A.M., Vidal, F., Morales, J., De Miguel, F., Ibáñez, J.M., Lopez-Linares, A., Alguacil, G., Romacho, M.D. & Garcia, J.M., (1990). Earthquake and microearthquake spatial distribution analysis in the Agron seismic series, December 1988. XXII General

1991.

17.- ALGUACIL, G., MORALES, J., IBÁÑEZ J.M. & LUZON, F. (1991). Ecuación de estaciones sísmicas mediante técnicas de filtrado. VII Asamblea Nacional de Geodesia y Geofísica. 2-5 de Diciembre. San Fernando, Cádiz.

18.- DE MIGUEL, F., IBÁÑEZ, J.M., MORALES, J., POSADAS, A.M., LUZON, F., ROMACHO, M.D. & PEÑA J.A. (1991). Relación entre Q_{Lg} y Q_c en el Sur de España. VII Asamblea Nacional de Geodesia y Geofísica. 2-5 de Diciembre. San Fernando, Cádiz.

19.- Ekström, G., Dziewonski, A.M. & Ibáñez, J.M. (1991). Deep earthquakes outside slabs. XX General Assembly I.U.G.G. Viena. 11-24 August, 1991

20.- IBÁÑEZ, J.M., EKSTRÖM, G. & DZIEWONSKI, A.M. (1991). Terremotos profundos localizados fuera de las superficies de Wadati-Benioff. VII Asamblea Nacional de Geodesia y Geofísica. 2-5 de Diciembre. San Fernando, Cádiz.

21.- IBÁÑEZ, J.M., EKSTRÖM, G. & DZIEWONSKI, A.M. (1991). Complejidad del estado de esfuerzos de la región de subducción de Tonga-Kermadec. VII Asamblea Nacional de Geodesia y Geofísica. 2-5 de Diciembre. San Fernando, Cádiz.

22.- IBÁÑEZ, J.M., DEL PEZZO, E., PATANÉ, D., DE MIGUEL, F., VIDAL, F., MORALES, J. & POSADAS, A.M. (1991). Un método no lineal para estimar Q-coda. VII Asamblea Nacional de Geodesia y Geofísica. 2-5 de Diciembre. San Fernando, Cádiz.

23.- Ibáñez, J.M., De Miguel, F., Del Pezzo, E., Alguacil, G., Morales, J., Vidal, F. & Posadas, A.M. (1991). A guide of the program QNONLIN. XX General Assembly IUGG, Viena. 11-24 August 1991.

24.- MORALES, J., IBÁÑEZ, J.M., VIDAL, F., DE MIGUEL, F., ALGUACIL, G., POSADAS, A.M., DEL PEZZO, E. & PATANE, D. (1991). Amplificación de sitio en la Depresión de Granada a partir de los efectos sobre las codas. VII Asamblea Nacional de Geodesia y Geofísica. 2-5 de Diciembre. San Fernando, Cádiz.

25.- MORALES, J., VIDAL, F., ALGUACIL, G., DE MIGUEL, F., IBÁÑEZ, J.M. & POSADAS, A.M. (1991). Fenómenos de amplificación en la Depresión de Granada mediante razones espectrales de microterremotos. VII Asamblea Nacional de Geodesia y Geofísica. 2-5 de Diciembre. San Fernando, Cádiz.

26.- MORALES, J., SEO, K., SAMANO, T., PEÑA, J.A., IBÁÑEZ, J.M. & VIDAL, F., (1991). Efectos de sitio en la Depresión de Granada a partir de medidas de microterremotos. VII Asamblea Nacional de Geodesia y Geofísica. 2-5 de Diciembre. San Fernando, Cádiz.

27.- PATANE, D., IBÁÑEZ, J.M., DE MIGUEL, F., MORALES, J., DEL PEZZO E. & POSADAS, A.M. (1991). Variación espacial de la razón de Poisson en el Mt. Etna. VII Asamblea Nacional de Geodesia y Geofísica. 2-5 de Diciembre. San Fernando, Cádiz.

28.- POSADAS, A.M., VIDAL, F., LOPEZ-LINARES, A., IBÁÑEZ J.M. & MORALES, J. (1991). Morfodinámica de un sistema de fallas sísmicamente activo mediante análisis de componentes principales. VII Asamblea Nacional de Geodesia y Geofísica. 2-5 de Diciembre. San Fernando, Cádiz.

29.- POSADAS, A.M., VIDAL, F., DE MIGUEL, F., MORALES, J., IBÁÑEZ J.M. & PEÑA J.A. (1991). Aplicación del análisis de componentes principales a la serie sísmica de Antequera (1989). VII Asamblea Nacional de Geodesia y Geofísica. 2-5 de Diciembre. San Fernando, Cádiz.

30.- POSADAS, A.M., VIDAL, F., PEÑA, J.A., ALGUACIL, G., IBÁÑEZ, J., MORALES, J., GARCIA J.M. & ROMACHO, M.D. (1991). Un programa para la aplicación

del análisis de componentes principales. VII Asamblea Nacional de Geodesia y Geofísica. 2-5 de Diciembre. San Fernando, Cádiz.

31.- POSADAS, A.M., VIDAL, F., MORALES, J., IBÁÑEZ, J.M., DE MIGUEL F. & ALGUACIL, G. (1991). Aplicación del método de los tres puntos a la serie sísmica de Loja (1985). VII Asamblea Nacional de Geodesia y Geofísica. 2-5 de Diciembre. San Fernando, Cádiz.

32.- ROMACHO, M.D., IBÁÑEZ, J.M., MORALES, J., POSADAS, A.M., NAVARRO, M., GARCÍA, J.M. & DEL PEZZO, E. (1991). Atenuación sísmica del Sur de Almería. VII Asamblea Nacional de Geodesia y Geofísica. 2-5 de Diciembre. San Fernando, Cádiz.

33.- VIDAL, F., AMELUNG, F., PEÑA, J.A., MORALES, J., POSADAS, A.M., IBÁÑEZ J.M. & ROMACHO, M.D. (1991). Cálculo de mecanismos focales con una red sísmica local. VII Asamblea Nacional de Geodesia y Geofísica. 2-5 de Diciembre. San Fernando, Cádiz.

34.- VIDAL, F., ALGUACIL, G., ROMACHO, M.D., POSADAS, A.M., PEÑA, J.A., DE MIGUEL, F., NAVARRO, M., GARCIA, J.M. MORALES, J., IBÁÑEZ, J.M., GAZQUEZ J.A. & CORCHETE, V. (1991). Monitorización de la actividad sísmica de Almería con una red local de la R.S.A. VII Asamblea Nacional de Geodesia y Geofísica. 2-5 de Diciembre. San Fernando, Cádiz.

1992.

35.- DEL PEZZO, E., DE MARTINO, S., IBÁÑEZ, J.M. & DE MIGUEL, F. (1992). Studio del geometrical spreading. 12o Convegno Nazionale del Gruppo Nazionale di Geofisica della Terra Solida. Roma, Italia.

36.- Morales, J., Ibáñez, J.M., Vidal, F., De Miguel, F., Alguacil, G. And Seo, K., (1992). Site amplification in the Granada Basin (Southern Spain) based on site-dependent coda-Q value. International Symposium on the effects of surface geology on seismic motion. ESG 1992, Odawara, Japan, 25-27 March, 1992., Vol 1, 329-334.

37.- Morales, J., Peña, J.A., Ibáñez, J.M., Vidal, F., Seo, K. & Samano, T., (1992). Site response in the Granada basin (Southern Spain) based on microtremor measurements. Tenth World Conference on Earthquake Engineering, Madrid, Spain 19-24 July, 1992, 1069-1073.

1993.

38.- Ibáñez, J.M., Alguacil, G., De Miguel, F., Morales, J., Vidal, F., Posadas, A.M., Del Pezzo, E., De Martino, S. & Sabaresse C. (1993). Analysis of the geometrical spreading function in the lithosphere for short period S and coda waves. XVIII General Assembly of the European Geophysical Society. Wiesbaden, 3-7 May 1993.

39.- Ibáñez, J.M., Patane, D., Morales, J., Del Pezzo, E., Privitera, E., Alguacil, G. & Posadas, A.M. (1993). Spatial variation of Poisson's ratio in Mt. Etna. Non linear analysis of volcanic tremor. Lanzarote, 24-28, May, 1993.

40.- Ibáñez, J.M., Del Pezzo, E., Morales, J., Martini, M., Patane, D., Alguacil, G. & Posadas, A.M. (1993). Estimates of coda-Q using a non-linear regression in Mt Etna and Campi Flegrei. Non linear analysis of volcanic tremor. Lanzarote, 24-28, May, 1993.

1994.

41.- Del Pezzo E. & Ibáñez, J.M. (1994). Seismic attenuation in volcanic areas: separation of intrinsic and scattering Q. XIX General Assembly of the European Geophysical

Society. Grenoble, 25-29 April 1994.

42.- Del Rey, R., Ortiz, R. & Ibáñez, J.M. (1994). Actual seismicity in Timanfaya (Lanzarote, Canary Islands). XIX General Assembly of the European Geophysical Society. Grenoble, 25-29 April 1994.

43.- Ibáñez, J.M., Akinci, A., Del Pezzo, E., Morales, J. & Ergintav, S. (1994). Separation of scattering and intrinsic attenuation in Southern Spain using multiple lapse-time window analysis. XIX General Assembly of the European Geophysical Society. Grenoble, 25-29 April 1994.

1995.

44.- Ibáñez, J.M., Morales, J., Ortiz, R., Blanco, I. & Del Rey R. (1995). Deep earthquakes recorded at Deception and Livingston Islands (Antarctica). Possible connection with the South Shetland subduction zone. XXI General Assembly IUGG, Boulder. 2-14 July 1995.

45.- Ibáñez, J.M., Morales, J., Alguacil, G., Almendros, J., Ortiz, R., Garcia, A., & Del Pezzo E. (1995). Seismic array studies at Deception Island (Antarctica): earthquakes classification and location. VIII ISAES, Siena, 10-15 September 1995.

46.- Ibáñez, J.M., Morales, J., Alguacil, G., Almendros, J., Ortiz, R., Blanco, I. & Garcia, A. (1995). About the occurrence of intermediate-deep earthquakes under South Shetland islands (Antarctica). VIII ISAES, Siena, 10-15 September 1995.

47.- Morales, J., Ibáñez, J.M., Felpeto, A. & Garcia A. (1995). Analysis of the spectral decay observed in seismic records at Deception Island, South Shetland Islands (Antarctica): a possible path effect. XXI General Assembly IUGG, Boulder. 2-14 July 1995.

1996.

48.- ALGUACIL, G., ORTIZ, R., OLMEDILLAS, J.C., DEL PEZZO, E. & IBÁÑEZ, J.M. (1996). Desarrollo de arrays sísmicos para la monitorización de la actividad tectónica y volcánica en la Antártida. VI Simposium Antártico. Miraflores de la Sierra, 11-14 Septiembre de 1996.

49.- Almendros, J., Ibanez, J., Alguacil, G., Del Pezzo, E., Morales, J., Ortiz, R., Blanco, M.J., Olmedillas, Jc., Lopez, C., La Rocca, M. (1996). Seismic monitoring of Teide Volcano by using two seismic arrays. IAVCEI 2nd Workshop on the European Laboratory Volcanoes, Santorini, Greece, May 2-4 1996.

50.- Del Pezzo E., La Rocca, M. & Ibáñez, J.M. (1996). High frequency coda-waves observations from dense arrays. XXI General Assembly of the European Geophysical Society. The Hague, 6-10 May 1996.

52.- Del Pezzo, E., La Rocca, M., Ibáñez, J. Alguacil, G., Almendros, J., Ortiz,R., Morales, J., Garcia, A.,1977. Observations of volcanic earthquakes and tremor at Desepcion Island-Antartica. European Seismological Commission Workshop on Seismic phenomena associated with volcanic activity, Ercolano, Napoli, Italia, 4-8 nov.1996

53.- Ibáñez, J.M., Ortiz, R., Del Pezzo,E., Blanco, M.J., Morales, J., Alguacil, G., Olmedillas, J.C., López, C., Larocca, M., (1996). Seismic monitoring of Teide Volcano by using two seismic arrays. IAVCEI. 2nd Workshop on the European Laboratory Volcanoes, Santorini, Greece, May 2-4 1996.

54.- Ibáñez, J.M., Del Pezzo E. & Canas, J.A. (1996). A revision of short period seismic attenuation in the Mediterranean basin (Spain, Italy & Greece). XXI General Assembly of the European Geophysical Society. The Hague, 6-10 May 1996.

55.- Ibáñez,J.M., Morales,J., Alguacil,G., Almendros, J., Ortiz,,R., Del Pezzo, E.

(1996). Intermediate focus earthquakes under South Shetland Islands (Antartica). European Seismological Commission Workshop on Seismic phenomena associated with volcanic activity 4-8 nov.1996, Ercolano, Naples, Italy.

56.- IBÁÑEZ, J.M., MORALES, J., ALGUACIL, G., ORTIZ, R., ALMENDROS, J., DEL PEZZO, E., POSADAS, A. & LUZÓN, F. (1996). Actividad sísmica regional alrededor de las islas Livingston y Decepción: terremotos superficiales y profundos. VI Simposium Antártico Español. Miraflores de la Sierra, 11-14 Septiembre de 1996.

57.- IBÁÑEZ, J.M., DEL PEZZO, E., ORTIZ, R., MORALES, J., ALGUACIL, G., ALMENDROS, J., GARCÍA, A. & VIDAL, F. (1996). Dos años de monitorización de la actividad sísmica de la isla Decepción usando "arrays" sísmicos. VI Simposium Antártico Español. Miraflores de la Sierra, 11-14 Septiembre de 1996.

58.- IBÁÑEZ, J.M., ALMENDROS, J., ALGUACIL, G., DEL PEZZO, E. & MORALES, J. (1996). Eventos sísmicos de largo periodo en isla Decepción: evidencias de una zona volcánica activa. VI Simposium Antártico Español. Miraflores de la Sierra, 11-14 Septiembre de 1996.

1997.

59.- Almendros, J., Ibáñez, J.M., Alguacil, G., Del Pezzo, E. & Ortiz, R. (1997). Analisis of the seismic activity in the volcanic area of Deception Island, Antarctica, by using a seismic array. 29th General Assembly of the IASPEI, Thessaloniki (Greece), 18-28 August, 1997.

60.- Ibáñez, J.M., Almendros, J., Alguacil, G., Del Pezzo, E. & Ortiz, R. (1997). Seismic array observations of the volcanic tremor source. 29th General Assembly of the IASPEI, Thessaloniki (Greece), 18-28 August, 1997.

1998.

61.- Almendros, J., Ibáñez, J.M., Alguacil, G. & Del Pezzo, E., (1998). Determinación de la distancia epicentral de señales volcánicas usando técnicas de arrays sísmicos. I Asamblea Hispano Portuguesa de Geodesia y Geofísica. Aguadulce (Almería), 9-13 de Febrero de 1998.

62.- Almendros, J., Ibáñez, J.M., Alguacil, G., Del Pezzo, E., & Ortiz, R. (1998). El tremor volcánico como superposición de eventos más simples. I Asamblea Hispano Portuguesa de Geodesia y Geofísica. Aguadulce (Almería), 9-13 de Febrero de 1998.

63.- Almendros, J., Ibáñez, J.M., Del Pezzo, E., Alguacil, G. & Ortiz, R., (1998). Seguimiento de la fuente sísmica volcánica en la Isla Decepción (Antártida) usando Arrays sísmicos. I Asamblea Hispano Portuguesa de Geodesia y Geofísica. Aguadulce (Almería), 9-13 de Febrero de 1998.

64.- Badi, G. & Ibáñez, J.M. (1998). Estudio preliminar de la atenuación sísmica en los Andes Argentinos. I Asamblea Hispano Portuguesa de Geodesia y Geofísica. Aguadulce (Almería), 9-13 de Febrero de 1998.

65.- Bianco, F., Carmona, E., Castellano, M., Ibáñez, J.M., La Rocca, M., Maresca, R., Petrosino, S. & Saccorotti G. (1998). Wave field analysis of the seismic noise at the Mt. Vesuvius, Italy, applying array techniques. European Geophys. Soc. Nice, April 1998.

66.- Bianco, F., Castellano, M., Del Pezzo, E. & Ibáñez, J.M. (1998). Measurements of intrinsic and scattering attenuation at Mt. Vesuvius. European Geophys. Soc. Nice, April 1998.

67.- Bianco, F., Castellano, M., Del Pezzo, E., Ibáñez, J.M. (1998). Attenuation of the short period seismic waves at Mt. Vesuvius, Italy. 1998 Fall Meeting A.G.U. S. Francisco, 6-

10 December 1998.

68.- Carmona, E., Ibáñez, J.M. & Alguacil, G., (1998). Generación de ondas T para trayectos del mar del Alborán. I Asamblea Hispano Portuguesa de Geodesia y Geofísica. Aguadulce (Almería), 9-13 de Febrero de 1998.

69.- CARMONA, E., IBAÑEZ, J.M.,ALGUACIL, G., MORALES, J. (1998). “ Estudio de ondas T en el Mar de Alborán “.Jornadas Científicas : 100 años de observaciones sismológicas en San Fernando. San Fernando (Cádiz) 17-18 de Septiembre de1998

70.- Del Pezzo, E., Giudicepietro, F., Martini, M., Saccorotti, G., Ibáñez, J., (1998). Volcano monitoring with small-aperture seismic arrays. 1998 Cities on Volcanoes. Rome and Naples, Italy, 28 June-4 July, 1998.

71.- García, A., Abella, R., Astiz, M., Ibáñez, J.M., Morales, J., Vidal, F., Peña, J. & Villegas, M.T. (1998). Seguimiento de la actividad sísmica volcánica de la isla Decepción (Shetland del Sur, Antártida), 1994-1997. I Asamblea Hispano Portuguesa de Geodesia y Geofísica. Aguadulce (Almería), 9-13 de Febrero de 1998

72.- Ibáñez, J.M., Alguacil, G., Almendros, J., Morales, J., Del Pezzo, E. & Ortiz, R. (1998). Terremotos de foco intermedio-profundo en la región de las Shetland del Sur (Antártida). I Asamblea Hispano Portuguesa de Geodesia y Geofísica. Aguadulce (Almería), 9-13 de Febrero de 1998

73.- Ibáñez, J.M., Alguacil, G., Almendros, J., Carmona, E., Abril, M., Del Pezzo, E., La Rocca, M., Simini, M., Petrosino, S., Maritato, L., Grozzea, B., Ortiz, R. & García, A. (1998). Estudio preliminar de la fuente explosiva del volcán Stromboli usando arrays sísmicos. I Asamblea Hispano Portuguesa de Geodesia y Geofísica. Aguadulce (Almería), 9-13 de Febrero de 1998.

74.- La Rocca, M., Petrosino, S., Saccorotti, G., Simini, M., Ibáñez, J.M., Almendros, J. & Del Pezzo, E. (1998). Location of the source and shallow velocity model deduced from the explosion-quakes recorded by two seismic antennas at stromboli volcano. European Geophys. Soc. Nice, April 1998.

75.- Morales, J., Alguacil, G., Luzón, F., Navarro, M., Posadas, A.M. & Ibáñez, J.M. (1998). Primeros datos de una nueva instrumentación de banda-ancha y movimiento fuerte de alta resolución para el Sudeste de España. I Asamblea Hispano Portuguesa de Geodesia y Geofísica. Aguadulce (Almería), 9-13 de Febrero de 1998.

76.- Petrosino, S., Larocca, M., Saccorotti, G., Bianco, F., Carmona, E., Ibáñez, J.M. & Del Pezzo, E. (1998). A seismic array on Mt. Vesuvius. . European Geophys. Soc. Nice, April 1998.

77.- Petrosino, S., Larocca, M., Saccorotti, G., Bianco, F., Carmona, E., Ibáñez, J.M. & Del Pezzo, E. (1998). Un array sísmico al Vesuvio. Convegno del Gruppo Nazionale de Vulcanologia. Catania, April, 1998.

1999.

78.- Abril, M., Morales, J., Mancilla, F., Peña, J.A., Carmona, E., Almendros, J., Alguacil, G., Ibáñez, J. & Saccorotti, G. (1999). New permanent seismic broad band stations at South Shetland Islands: Livingston, Deception and King George. 8th international Symposium on Antarctic Earth Sciences. Wellington (New Zealand), 5-9 July 1999.

79.- Alguacil, G., Ortiz, R., Del Pezzo, E., Ibáñez, J.M., Almendros, J., Morales, J., Saccorotti, G., Carmona, E., Petrosino, S., Abril, M., La Rocca, M., Bianco, F. & Castellano, M. (1999), Use of a portable dense seismic antenna to study very local microearthquakes: application to several volcanic areas. IUGG99, Birmingham,19-30 July.

80.- Almendros, J., Ibáñez, J.M., Alguacil, G., Morales, J., Del Pezzo, E., La Rocca,

M., Ortiz, R., Araña, V., Blanco, M.J. (1999). Evidence of local seismicity and inference from the absence of observable volcanic tremor at Teide Volcano (Canary Islands, Spain).. XXIV General assembly EGS, The Hague, 19-23 April, 1999.

81.- Almendros, J., Alguacil, G., Carmona, E., Ibáñez, J.M., Mancilla, F., Morales, J., Peña, J.A., Del Pezzo, E., Saccorotti, G. & García A. (1999). The seismo-volcanic crisis at Deception island volcano: January-February 1999. 8th international Symposium on Antarctic Earth Sciences. Wellington (New Zealand), 5-9 July 1999.

82.- Almendros, J., Carmona, E., Saccorotti, G., Peña, J.A., Del Pezzo, E., Ibáñez, J.M., & Alguacil, G. (1999). Preliminary results from the 1998-99 double seismic antenna experiment at Deception volcano, South Shetland islands (Antarctica). IUGG99, Birmingham, 19-30 July.

83.- Almendros, J., Ibáñez, J.M., Alguacil, G., Morales, J., Del Pezzo, E., La Rocca, M., Ortiz, R., Araña, V. & Blanco, M.J. (1999). Local seismicity and absence of observable volcanic tremor at Teide volcano (Cnary Islands, Spain). IUGG99, Birmingham, 19-30 July.

84.- Carmona, E., Saccorotti, G., Posadas, A.M., Ibáñez, J.M, Del Pezzo, E., Alguacil, G., Morales, J. (1999). Spatial-temporal analysis of a seismic series in Granada Basin (Spain) by using Bayesian and clustering techniques. XXIV General assembly EGS, The Hague, 19-23 April, 1999.

85.- Carmona, E., Saccorotti, G., Posadas, A.M., Ibáñez, J.M., Del Pezzo, E., Alguacil, G., & Morales, J. (1999). Spatial and temporal analysis, by using bayesian and clustering techniques, of a seismic series in Granada Basin (Spain). IUGG99, Birmingham, 19-30 July.

86.- Del Pezzo, E., Ibáñez, J.M., La Rocca, M., Almendros, J., Saccorotti, G., Petrosino, S., Alguacil, G., Carmona, E., (1999). A twin seismic antenna experiment at Stromboli volcano (Italy). XXIV General assembly EGS, The Hague, 19-23 April, 1999.

87.- Ibáñez, J.M, Almendros, J., Del Pezzo, E., Alguacil, G., La Rocca, M., García, A., Ortiz, R., (1999). Seismo-volcanic source analysis at Deception Island volcano (Antarctica). XXIV General Assembly EGS, The Hague, 19-23 April, 1999.

88.- Ibáñez, J.M, Almendros, J., Alguacil, G., Del Pezzo, E. & La Rocca, M., (1999). Tectonic and seismo-volcanic events recorded at Deception Island (Antarctica) by a seismic antenna: 1994-1997. 8th international Symposium on Antarctic Earth Sciences. Wellington (New Zealand), 5-9 July 1999.

89.- Ibáñez, J.M., Carmona, E., & Alguacil, G. (1999). Observations of T-waves in seismic stations in Southern Spain from earthquakes of the north coast of Marrocco. IUGG99, Birmingham, 19-30 July.

90.- Ibáñez, J.M., Del Pezzo, E., Alguacil, G., Ortiz, R. & Chouet, B. (1999). Preliminar analysis of high frequency earthquakes at Timanfaya volcano (Lanzarote Island, Spain). IUGG99, Birmingham, 19-30 July.

100.- Ibáñez, J.M., Almendros, J., Del Pezzo, E., Alguacil, G., La Rocca, M., García, A. & Ortiz, R. (1999). Deception Island volcano (Antarctica): seismo volcanic source analysis. IUGG99, Birmingham, 19-30 July.

101.- La Rocca, M., Del Pezzo, E., Ibáñez, J.M., Almendros, J., Saccorotti, G., Petrosino, S., Alguacil, G., Carmona, E. (1999). Location of the seismo-volcanic source at Stromboli volcano using two distinct seismic antennas. . IUGG99, Birmingham, 19-30 July.

102.- Petrosino, S., Del Pezzo, E., La Rocca, M., Ibáñez, J.M & Maresca R. (1999). Shallow velocity model for Stromboli volcano from surface waves dispersion. IUGG99, Birmingham, 19-30 July.

2000.

103.- Morales, J., G. Alguacil, J.M. Ibañez, F. Vidal. Source parameters and complexity of the Granada Basin 24 February 1997 earthquake. XXVII General Assembly of the European Seismological Commission (ESC) Lisboa, 10-15 September, 2000.

2001.

104.- Bianco, F., Castellano, M., Del Pezzo, E., Di Luccio, F., Ibanez, J. Intrinsic and scattering attenuation in the southern apennines, Italy. EGS Conference, Nice, 24-29 March 2001

105.- Martinez Arévalo, C., Ibañez, J., Carmona, E., Del Pezzo, E. Short range and high frequency seismic attenuation in Deception Island, Antarctica. EGS Conference, Nice, 24-29 March 2001

106.- Saccorotti, G., Carmona, E., Ibanez, J., del Pezzo, E. Passive seismic Imaging of Caldera walls: two examples from Kilauea and Deception Island volcanoes. EGS Conference, Nice, 24-29 March 2001

2002.

107.- Carmona, E., Almendros, J., Abril, M., Ibañez, J.M., Saccorotti, G., Del Pezzo, E., & Ortiz, R. (2002). A volcano-tectonic earthquake swarm at Deception island, Antarctica. Evidences of an active volcano. Symposium Internacional "Cien años de Sismología en Granada", Granada, 8-11 Octubre 2002.

108.- Carmona, E., Esquivel José A, Estévez G., Ibañez J. M. (2002). An approach to the characterization of the seismic series using nonparametric methods. Symposium Internacional "Cien años de Sismología en Granada", Granada, 8-11 Octubre 2002.

109.- Ferrari, F., Patané, D., Del Pezzo, E., Gresta, S., Ibañez, J.M., Saccorotti, G., & Scarfi, L. (2002). Polarization of tremor wave-field before and during the July-August 2001 Mt. Etna eruption. 27th General Assembly of the E.G.S.. Nice, 26-30 March, 2002.

110.- Havskov, J., Peña, J.A., Ibañez, J.M., Ottemöller, L. & Martínez-Arévalo, C. (2002). Magnitude scales for very local earthquakes. Application for Deception Island volcano (Antarctica). 27th General Assembly of the E.G.S.. Nice, 26-30 March, 2002.

111.- Ibañez, J.M., Carmona, E., Almendros, J., Saccorotti, G., Del Pezzo, E., Abril, M., Ortiz, R. & Martínez-Arévalo, C., (2002). The 1998-1999 seismic series at Deception Island volcano, Antarctica. 27th General Assembly of the E.G.S.. Nice, 26-30 March, 2002.

112.- Ibañez, J.M., Blanco, M.J., Zandomenighi, D., Carmona, E., Almendros, J., Benito, J. & García, A. (2002). The new short period seismic network at Teide volcano. Symposium Internacional "Cien años de Sismología en Granada", Granada, 8-11 Octubre 2002.

113.- Ibañez, J.M. Wallenstein, N., Abril, M., Saccorotti, G, Montalvo, A., & Silva, R. (2002). The Azores experiment, april-july 2003. Symposium Internacional "Cien años de Sismología en Granada", Granada, Octubre 2002.

114.- Ibañez, J. M., Carmona, E., Almendros, J., Saccorotti, G., Del Pezzo, E., Abril, M., Ortiz, R., Martínez Arévalo, C. (2002). La serie sísmica de 1998-99 en la isla Decepción (Antártida). III Asamblea Hispano-Portuguesa de Geofísica y Geodesia, Valencia. 2002

115.- Martínez Arévalo, C., Bianco, F., Ibañez, J. M., Del Pezzo, E., Almendros, J. (2002) Atenuación sísmica superficial y separación de ondas de cizalla en el rango del corto periodo en el volcán Isla Decepción (Antártida). III Asamblea Hispano-Portuguesa de Geofísica y Geodesia. Valencia. 2002

116.- Martínez Arévalo, C., Havskov, J., Peña, J. A., Ibáñez, J. M., Ottemöller, L., Almendros, J. (2002). Escalas de magnitud para terremotos muy locales: aplicación al volcán Isla Decepción (Antártida). III Asamblea Hispano-Portuguesa de Geofísica y Geodesia. Valencia. 2002

117.- Martínez-Arévalo, C., Bianco, F., Ibáñez, J.M. & Del Pezzo, E. (2002). Shallow seismic attenuation and shear waves splitting in the short period range of Deception Island volcano (Antarctica). 27th General Assembly of the E.G.S.. Nice, 26-30 March, 2002.

118.- Martínez-Arévalo C., Bianco F., Ibáñez J.M. & Del Pezzo E. (2002). Seismic attenuation in the short period range at Deception Island volcano (Antarctica). Symposium Internacional "Cien años de Sismología en Granada", Granada, 8-11 Octubre 2002.

119.- Martínez-Arévalo C., Havskov J., Peña J.A., Carmona E., Almendros J., Abril M., Ibáñez J.M., Ottemöller L. (2002). Magnitude scales for very local earthquakes. Application for Deception Island volcano (Antarctica). Symposium Internacional "Cien años de Sismología en Granada", Granada, 8-11 Octubre 2002.

120.- Posadas, A.M., Ibáñez, J.M., Carmona, E. & Luzón, F., (2002). Seismicity in the Deception volcán (Antarctica): determining significant structures in a cloud of earthquakes. 27th General Assembly of the E.G.S.. Nice, 26-30 March, 2002.

121.- Saccoroti, G., Zuccarello, L., Del Pezzo, E., Ibáñez, J.M., Gresta, S. & Privitera, E. (2002). Quantitative analysis of tremor wavefield at Etna volcano, Italy. 27th General Assembly of the E.G.S.. Nice, 26-30 March, 2002.

122.- Tuvè T., Ibáñez J.M., Del Pezzo E. & Bottari A. (2002). Preliminary results of Q_c estimations in the Messina straits area. Symposium Internacional "Cien años de Sismología en Granada", Granada, 8-11 Octubre 2002.

2003.

123.- Almendros, J., Carmona, E., Ibáñez, J.M. Relative propagation parameters and source locations of similar events using seismic antennas. . Fall Meeting of the American Geophysical Union (AGU), San Francisco (USA). 8-12 December. EOS Trans. AGU, 84(46).

124.- Martínez-Arévalo, C., C. Rietbrock, A., Marrero, I., Almendros, J., Patane, D., Ferrari, F., Ibáñez, J. M., (2003). 3-D Attenuation Structure of Mt. Etna Volcano. Fall Meeting of the American Geophysical Union (AGU), San Francisco (USA). 8-12 December. EOS Trans. AGU, 84(46).

125.- Martínez-Arévalo, C. E. Carmona, J. Morales, J. Almendros, J.M. Ibáñez, M. Abril, (2003). Stress drop values for seismo-volcanic events in Deception island (Antarctica). 28th General Assembly of the European Geophysical Society, 7-11 April *Nice (France)*.

126.- J.M. Ibáñez, E. Del Pezzo, J. Almendros, G. Saccoroti, E. Carmona, M. La Rocca and B. Chouet The influence of heterogeneous volcanic structures and complex topography in the propagation of seismic waves. European Seismological Commission SEISMIC PHENOMENA ASSOCIATED WITH VOLCANIC ACTIVITY, Tenerife, Spain, 18-21 September, 2003.

127.- J.M. Ibáñez, J. Almendros, G. Alguacil, J. Morales, E. Del Pezzo, M. La Rocca, R. Ortiz, V. Araña, M.J. and Blanco The study of local seismicity at Teide volcano using seismic antennas. European Seismological Commission SEISMIC PHENOMENA ASSOCIATED WITH VOLCANIC ACTIVITY, Tenerife, Spain, 18-21 September, 2003

128.- J.M. Ibáñez and C. Martínez-Arévalo Near surface seismic attenuation and its influence in the magnitude determination in volcanic environments. A case of Deception Island Volcano (Antarctica). European Seismological Commission SEISMIC PHENOMENA ASSOCIATED WITH VOLCANIC ACTIVITY, Tenerife, Spain, 18-21 September, 2003

129.- Tuvè, T.; Martínez-Arévalo, C.; Ibáñez, J.M.; Teramo, A.; Bottari, A. Crustal attenuation structure in Messina Straits area (Southern Italy). 28 th General Assembly of the European Geophysical Society, 7-11 April. Nice (France).

2004.

130.- Almendros, J., Carmona, E., Ibáñez, J. M.(2004). Estimación relativa del vector lentitud y localización relativa de la fuente utilizando antenas sísmicas. IV Asamblea Hispano-Portuguesa de Geofísica y Geodesia. Figueira da Foz (Portugal). 2004

131.- Caselli, A.T., Bidone, A., Bengoa, C., Rojas Vera, E., Badi, G., Zandomenighi, D., Sánchez; N., Fernández, F. y Ibáñez, J. (2004). Análisis sísmológico y geoquímico comparativo del verano austral 2004 en Isla Decepción, Antártida. Vº Simposio Argentino y Iº Latinoamericano sobre Investigaciones Antárticas, Actas en prensa.

132.- Ibáñez J.M., Almendros, J., Carmona, E., Abril, M., Zandomenighi, D., Alguacil, G., Martínez-Arévalo, M., Carrión, F., Saccorotti, G., Del Pezzo, E., Wallenstein, N., Montalvo, A., Patané, D., Zuccarello, L., Di Prima, S., Blanco, M.J., García, A., Caselli, A. Integral seismic monitoring of active volcanoes. Part I, instrument deployment. European Seismological Commission Workshop, La Palma, Spain, 7-11 September, 2004.

133.- Ibáñez J.M., Almendros, J., Carmona, E., Abril, M., Zandomenighi, D., Alguacil, G., Martínez-Arévalo, M., Carrión, F., Saccorotti, G., Del Pezzo, E., Wallenstein, N., Montalvo, A., Patané, D., Zuccarello, L., Di Prima, S., Blanco, M.J., García, A., Caselli, A. Integral seismic monitoring of active volcanoes. Part II, some results. European Seismological Commission Workshop *Characterizing eruptive phases with seismology*, La Palma, Spain, 7-11 September, 2004.

134.- Saccorotti, G., Galluzzo, D., La Rocca, M., Bonagura, M. T., Damiano, N., Carmona, E., Almendros, J., Abril, M., Carrión, F., Ibáñez, J. M., Blanco, M.J., Zandomenighi, D., García, A., Sánchez, N., Tárraga, M., Ortiz, R., Wallenstein, N., Silva, R. A., Montalvo, A., Quadrio, A., Carrilho, F. (2004). Detailed seismicity observations at Sao Miguel Island, Azores. 32nd International Geological Congress, Firenze 2004.

135.- Saccorotti, G.; Wallenstein, N.; Ibanez, J.; Bonagura, M.T.; Damiano, N.; La Rocca, M.; Quadrio, A.; Silva, R.; Zandomenighi, D. (2004). A seismic field survey at Fogo-Furnas volcanoes, Sao Miguel island, Azores. 1st Genaral Assembly EGU, 17-21 March, Nice 2004.

2005.

136.- Almendros, J.; Zandomenighi, D.; Carmona, E.; Ibáñez, J. M.; Blanco, M. J.; Abella, R. (2005). Array analyses of seismic activity during May 2004 at Teide Volcano, Canary Islands, Spain. [EGU05-A-00222](#) 2nd EGU General Assembly 2005 Vienna 24-29 April 2005.

137.- Almendros, J., Zandomenighi, D., Saccorotti, G., Barclay, A. Ibáñez, J.M. Seismic tomography of Central Sao Miguel, Azores. 2005 AGU, Fall meeting, 5-9 December, San Francisco (USA), December EOS 86(52) S51A-0983, 2005.

138.- Badi G., J.M. Ibáñez, N.C. Sabbione. Estimation of Q in Nuevo Cuyo Region, Argentina, using P, S and Coda waves. IASPEI (International Association of Seismology and Physics of the Earth's Interior) General Assembly. Santiago, Chile, 02 al 08 de octubre de 2005.

139.- Giampiccolo, E.; Tuvé, T.; Bianco, F.; Bottari, A.; Del Pezzo, E.; Gresta, S.; Ibanez, J.M.; Patané, D. Scattering and intrinsic attenuation of seismic energy in eastern Sicily (Italy). 2nd EGU General Assembly 2005 Vienna, Austria, 24 - 29 April 2005

140.- Góngora, E.; Wallenstein, N.; Ibáñez, J.; Carmona, E.; Posadas, A. Principal Component Analysis as a tool to characterise the spatial geometry of the Faial (Azores) seismic series (1998-2002). 2nd EGU General Assembly 2005 Vienna, Austria, 24 - 29 April 2005

141.- Martínez-Arévalo, Carmen, Domenico Patané, Andreas Rietbrock and Jesús M. Ibáñez. The intrusive process leading to the Mt. Etna 2001 flank eruption: constraints from 3D attenuation tomography. 2005 AGU, Fall meeting, 5-9 December, San Francisco (USA), December EOS 86(52) S51A-0983, 2005.

142.- Zandomenighi Daria, Andrew H. Barclay, Tami Ben Zvi, William Wilcock, Jesús M. Ibáñez, Javier Almendros and TOMODEC Working Group. Preliminary Seismic Tomography of Deception Island Volcano, South Shetland Islands. 2005 AGU, Fall meeting, 5-9 December, San Francisco (USA), December EOS 86(52). S41A-0975.

2006.

143.- Ben-Zvi, T., Barclay, A., Wilcock, W., Ibáñez, J.M., Zandomenighi, D., Almendros, J. and TOMODEC WORKING group. Seismic 2-D Tomography of Deception Island, Antarctica. X International Meeting of Colima Volcano, Colima, México, January, 2006.

144.- Bengoa, C., Caselli, A., Ibáñez, J.M., Del Pezzo, E., Badi, G., Bretón, M. Volcanic tremor and local seismicity at Copahue Volcano. X International Meeting of Colima Volcano, Colima, México, January, 2006.

145.- Benítez, C., Ramírez, J., Segura, J.C., Rubio, A., Ibáñez, J.M., García-Yeguas, A., Almendros, J. and Alguacil, G. Continuous HMM-based seismic events classification at Deception Island, Antarctica. X International Meeting of Colima Volcano, Colima, México, January, 2006.

146.- García-Yeguas, A., Ibáñez, J.M., Abella, R., Zandomenighi, D., Almendros, J. and TOMODEC working group. Anomalías de propagación de ondas sísmicas en el volcán Isla Decepción (Antártida) usando disparos registrados en antenas sísmicas. Spanish-Portugese Joint Geophysic and Geodetic Assembly. Seville, January 30th-February 3rd, 2006.

147.- Gutiérrez, L., Ibáñez, J.M., Benítez, C., Ramírez, J., Segura, J.C., Rubio, A., García-Yeguas, A., Almendros, J. and Alguacil, G. Discrimination between different volcanic signals using Hidden Markov Model: an example of Stromboli and Etna Volcanoes. X International Meeting of Colima Volcano, Colima, México, January, 2006.

148.- Ibáñez, J.M., García-Yeguas, A., Almendros, J., Zandomenighi, D., Barclay, A., and TOMODEC working group. Seismic wave propagation anomalies of Deception Island volcano detected by seismic antennas. X International Meeting of Colima Volcano, Colima, México, January, 2006

149.- Ibáñez, J.M., Bretón, M., Del Pezzo, E., Ocaña, E., Almendros, J., García-Yeguas, A., Espejo, T., La Rocca, M., Zandomenighi, D., Bengoa, C., Caselli, A., Ramirez, J.J., Téllez, A. Santiago, H., Orozco, J. & Alatorre, E. Location of explosive signal at Colima

Volcando using seismic antennas and Broad Band Stations. X International Meeting of Colima Volcano, Colima, México, January, 2006.

150.- Ibáñez, J.M. New Trends of volcanic seismology. Invited talk in X International Meeting of Colima Volcano, Colima, México, January, 2006.

151.- Ibáñez, J. M.; Del Pezzo, E.; Bengoa, C.; Almendros, J.; Caselli, A. (2006). *Volcanic tremor associated with the geothermal activity of Copahue volcano, Southern Andes region, Argentina*. EGU General Assembly 2006, Vienna, Austria, 2-7 April 2006.

152.- Martínez-Arévalo, Carmen, Domenico Patané, Andreas Rietbrock and Jesús M. Ibáñez. 3D Shallow P-Wave Attenuation Tomography. X International Meeting of Colima Volcano, Colima, México, January, 2006.

153.- Martínez-Arévalo, C., Almendros, J., Patané, D., Rietbrock, A., Ibáñez, J.M., (2006). Attenuation tomographic images of the July-August, 2001 Mt. Etna eruption. 5th Asamblea Hispano-Portuguesa de Geodesia y Geofísica, Sevilla (Spain).

154.- Martínez-Arevalo, C., D. Patané, A. Rietbrock and J.M. Ibañez, (2006). The intrusive process leading to the Mt. Etna 2001 flank eruption: constraints from 3D Qp model. 31th General Assembly of the European Geophysical Society, *Viena (Austria)*.

155.- Zandomaneghi, D., Barclay, A., Wilcock, W., Almendros, J., Ibáñez, J.M. and TOMODEC working group. A preliminary seismic tomographic image of Deception Island Volcano. X International Meeting of Colima Volcano, Colima, México, January, 2006.

156.- Zandomeneghi, D., Almendros, J., Saccorotti, G., Ibáñez, J.M. (2006). Tomografía Sísmica de la región central de Sao Miguel (Azores). 5th Asamblea Hispano-Portuguesa de Geodesia y Geofísica, Sevilla (Spain).

157.- Zandomeneghi, D., Barclay, A., Wilcock, W., Almendros, J., Ibáñez, J.M. and TOMODEC working group. (2006). Tomografía Sísmica del volcán Isla Decepción (Antártida) usando fuentes activas. 5th Asamblea Hispano-Portuguesa de Geodesia y Geofísica, Sevilla (Spain).

158.- Zandomeneghi, D., Almendros, J., Barclay, A. and Ibáñez, J.M. (2006). A preliminary seismic tomography image of Deception Island Volcano. European Geosciences Union, Viena. Geophysical Research Abstracts, Vol, 8., 05652.

2007.

159.- A. García-Yeguas, R. Abella, J. Almendros, D. Zandomeneghi, M. Palo, J.M. Ibáñez. Utilización de sísmica activa para la detección de heterogeneidades laterales en un medio volcánico (Isla Decepción, Antártida). "XXXI Reunión Bienal de la Real Sociedad Española de Física y 17°. Encuentro Ibérico de la Física". Del 10 al 14 de Septiembre de 2007 en Granada.

159.- Zandomeneghi, D., Barclay, A.H., Almendros, J., Ibáñez, J.M., Ben-Zvi, T., Wilcock, W.S.D. and TOMODEC working group (2007). Three-dimensional P wave tomography of Deception Island Volcan, South Shetland Islands. 10th International Symposium on Antarctic Earth Sciences. University of California, Santa Barbara, August, 26-31. Extended abstract, USGS OF-2007-1047.

160.- T. Ben-Zvi, W. S. D. Wilcock, A. H. Barclay, D. Zandomeneghi, J. M. Ibáñez, J. Almendros, and Tomodec Working Group. The P-wave velocity structure of Deception Island, Antarctica, from twodimensional seismic tomography. 10th International Symposium on Antarctic Earth Sciences. University of California, Santa Barbara, August, 26-31. Extended abstract,.

161.- Carmona, E., F. Martini, J.M. Ibáñez and C.J. Bean. Multiplets and Detection of Seismic Velocity Changes During the 1998-99 Seismic Series at Deception Island Volcano,

Antarctica. AGU, Fall meeting, San Francisco (USA), December, 2007.

162.- Del Pezzo E., M. La Rocca, D. Galluzzo, S. Petrosino, P. Cusano, F. Bianco, M. Breton, J. Orozco-Rojas, J. Ibanez (2007). *Una Campagna di Acquisizione di Dati Sismici al Vulcano Colima (Messico)*. 26° Convegno del Gruppo Nazionale di Geofisica della Terra Solida - Roma, 13-15 Novembre 2007.

2008.

163.- Bianco, F.; Del Pezzo, E.; Badi, G.; Ibanez, J Depth dependent intrinsic and scattering attenuation in the lithospheric structure of the “Nuevo Cuyo” region, Andes, Argentina. 5th General assembly EGU General Assembly – Vienna, 13-18 April 2008

164.- Del Pezzo E., La Rocca M., Galluzzo D., Petrosino S., Cusano P., Bianco F., Breton M., Orozco-Rojas J., Ibanez J., M. Veneruso (2008). *A seismic survey at Colima volcano (Mexico)*. 5th General assembly EGU General Assembly – Vienna, 13-18 April 2008, A-06891.

165.- García-Yeguas, Araceli, Rafael Abella, Javier Almendros, Jesús M. Ibáñez Godoy, Daria Zandomenighi. Anomalies of Deception Island volcano detected by seismic antennas using shoots. IAVCEI 2008. Del 17 al 22 de agosto de 2008. Reykjavik. Islandia.

166.- García-Yeguas, Araceli, Jesús Miguel Ibáñez Godoy, Andreas Rietbrock and TOM-TEIDEVS group. The TOM-TEIDEVS project: An active seismic experiment at Tenerife Island (Canary Islands, Spain) imaging an active volcano edifice IAVCEI 2008. Del 17 al 22 de agosto de 2008. Reykjavik. Islandia.

167.- Garcia-Yeguas, A, Ibáñez, J M, Rietbrock, A and TOM-TEIDEVS working group. An active seismic experiment at Tenerife Island (Canary Island, Spain): Imaging an active volcano edifice. AGU, Fall meeting, San Francisco (USA), December, 2008.

168.- Ibáñez J. M., Del Pezzo E., Bengoa C., García-Yeguas A., Caselli A., Badi G., Almendros J., *Volcanic tremor and local earthquakes at Copahue volcanic complex, Southern Andes, Argentina*. IAVCEI 2008. Del 17 al 22 de agosto de 2008. Reykjavik. Islandia.

169.- Palo, M., Ibáñez, J. M., Cisneros, M., Orozco-Rojas, J., García-Yeguas, A., Bretón, M., Del Pezzo, E., Ocaña, E., *Analysis of the wavefield properties of volcanic explosions at Volcán de Colima, México: insights into the source mechanism*. IAVCEI 2008. Del 17 al 22 de agosto de 2008. Reykjavik. Islandia.

2009.

170.- Bengoa, Cintia L Ernesto Horne, Alberto T. Caselli y Jesús M. Ibáñez Seismic activity of Copahue volcano zone, Copahue, Neuquén, Argentina: High and low frequency events. XI International Meeting of Volcán de Colima. Colima, February 2nd-6th, 2009.

171.- Benítez, C., Cortés, G., Arámbula, R., Ibáñez, J.M., Lesage, P. A successfully application of the automatic signal recognition technique to Mexican volcanoes: Colima and Popocatepetl. XI International Meeting of Volcán de Colima. Colima, February 2nd-6th, 2009.

172.- Bretón-González, M., Orozco, J., Cisneros M., Alatorre, E., Santiago, H, Ibáñez, J.M., Ocaña, E., García-Yeguas, A. The Colima Volcano seismic array: a powerful tool to track the seismic-volcanic activity. XI International Meeting of Volcán de Colima. Colima, February 2nd-6th, 2009.

173.- Caselli, A., Vélez, L., Agosto, M., Bengoa, C., Ibáñez, J.M. and Euillades, P. Variaciones geoquímicas, sismicidad y deformación en el volcán Copahue (Argentina). XI International Meeting of Volcán de Colima. Colima, February 2nd-6th, 2009.

174.- García-Yeguas Araceli, Jesús M. Ibáñez, Valentí Sallarés, Andreas Rietbrock and

TOM-TEIDEVS group .Imaging active volcanoes: 3D Seismic Tomography of Tenerife Island, (Canary Islands, Spain). XI International Meeting of Volcán de Colima. Colima, February 2nd-6th, 2009.

175.- García-Yeguas, A., Ibáñez, J.M., Sallarés, V. and Rietbrock A. High-resolution 3D seismic tomography of Tenerife Island (Spain). "Spain-China Symposium on Geophysical & Geochemical Geosystems (SG3)" Del 22 al 25 de Junio de 2008. Zaragoza (España).

176.- García-Yeguas, A., Ibáñez, J.M. Koulakov I. and Sallarès, V. "First high resolution 3d velocity structure of the volcanic Tenerife Island (Canary Islands, Spain)". "American Geophysical Union Fall 2009". Del 14 al 18 de Diciembre de 2009.San Francisco (EEUU).

177.- Gutiérrez, L., Ibañez, J, Ramírez, J., Benítez, C. Tenorio, V. Volcano-seismic signal detection and classification processing using Hidden Markov Models. Application to Telica and San Cristóbal volcanoes, Nicaragua. XI International Meeting of Volcán de Colima. Colima, February 2nd-6th, 2009.

178.- Ibáñez, J.M. Tomography of active volcanoes. Invited Talk. XI International Meeting of Volcán de Colima. Colima, February 2nd-6th, 2009.

179.- Ibáñez, Jesús M. Carmen Benítez, Javier Ramírez, Ligdamis A. Gutiérrez, Guillermo Cortés and Araceli García-Yeguas. Automatic discrimination of seismic signals using Hidden Markov Models using data of Stromboli and Etna volcanoes. XI International Meeting of Volcán de Colima. Colima, February 2nd-6th, 2009.

180.- Ibáñez, J.M., Rietbrock, A., García-Yeguas, A. and TOM-TEIDEVS working group. An active seismic experiment at Tenerife Island (Canary Islands, Spain) imaging an active volcano edifice. The TOM-TEIDEVS project. XI International Meeting of Volcán de Colima. Colima, February 2nd-6th, 2009.

181.- Ontiveros-Ortega A; Ibáñez J., Espinosa-Jiménez M., Vidal-Sánchez F., Ocaña E., Jiménez-Martin, E. Surface properties of eruptive material of Deception Island. XI International Meeting of Volcán de Colima. Colima, February 2nd-6th, 2009.

182.- Orozco-Rojas, J., Esteban-Parra, M.J., Ibañez, J., Navarro-Ochoa, C., Bretón-González, M., and Reyes-Dávila, G. Multi-variable analysis of volcanic explosions and degassing processes at Volcán de Fuego de Colima from 2004 to 2006. XI International Meeting of Volcán de Colima. Colima, February 2nd-6th, 2009.

183.- Cortés, Guillermo, Raúl Arámbula, Ligdamis A. Gutiérrez, Carmen Benítez, Jesús Ibáñez, Philippe Lesage, Isaac Alvarez and Luz García. Evaluating Robustness Of A Hmm-Based Classification System Of Volcano-Seismic Events At Colima And Popocatepetl Volcanoes. 2009 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium (IGARSS 2009) July 12–17, 2009 • Cape Town, South Africa.

184.- Gutiérrez, Ligdamis, Ibañez, Jesús, Cortés, Guillermo, Ramírez, Javier, Benítez, Carmen, Tenorio, Virginia and Álvarez Isaac. Volcano-seismic signal detection and classification processing using Hidden Markov Models. Application to San Cristóbal volcano, Nicaragua. 2009 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium (IGARSS 2009) July 12–17, 2009 • Cape Town, South Africa.

2010.

185.- Alvarez, Isaac, García, L., Cortés, G., Benitez, C., De la Torre, A., Ibáñez, J.M. and Mora, M., Comparison of volcano-seismic signals from different volcanoes: Characterization of different sources of events and strategies for the evaluation of automatic recognizers of volcano seismic events. Cities on Volcanoes 6. IAVCEI. Puerto de la Cruz. Tenerife, 31 May-4 June 2010.

- 186.- Bengoa, C., Caselli, A., Ibáñez, J.M., Volcano seismology studies at Copahue volcano, Argentina. Cities on Volcanoes 6. IAVCEI. Puerto de la Cruz. Tenerife, 31 May-4 June 2010.
- 187.- Bretón, M., Caselli, A., Coello-Bravo, J.J., Forjaz, V., Gonçalves, A.A., González, E., Ibáñez, J.M., Miranda, R., Muñoz, A., Ordóñez, S., Pérez, N. and Romero, C., IBEROAMERICAN Volcanological network: a new challenge for reducing volcanic risk in the Iberoamerican Community. Cities on Volcanoes 6. IAVCEI. Puerto de la Cruz. Tenerife, 31 May-4 June 2010.
- 188.- Buontempo, L., Ibáñez, J.M. and Morales, J., Preliminary results from shear wave splitting analysis in Canary Islands. Cities on Volcanoes 6. IAVCEI. Puerto de la Cruz. Tenerife, 31 May-4 June 2010.
- 189.- Cortés, G., Benítez, C., Ibáñez, J.M., González, E., Arámbula, R., Lesage, P. and Orozco, J. Towards an unsupervised HMM-based automatic classification system: application to a joint data base built from Colima, Popocatepetl and Deception seismo-volcanic events. Cities on Volcanoes 6. IAVCEI. Puerto de la Cruz. Tenerife, 31 May-4 June 2010.
- 190.- Cortés, G., García, I., Alvarez, I., González, E., De la Torre, A. and Ibáñez, J.M., Automatic and semi-automatic tools for segmentation and labelling of large databases of volcano-seismic signals. Cities on Volcanoes 6. IAVCEI. Puerto de la Cruz. Tenerife, 31 May-4 June 2010.
- 191.- García-Yeguas, A., Ibáñez, J.M. Koulakov I. and Sallarès, V. "First high resolution 3D velocity structure of the volcanic Tenerife Island (Canary Islands, Spain)". "European Geophysical Union". Del 2 al 7 de Mayo de 2010. Viena (Austria).
- 192.- García-Yeguas, A., Koulakov, I. and Ibáñez, J.M., First high resolution seismic tomography, P wave velocity structure beneath Tenerife Island (Canary Islands, Spain). Cities on Volcanoes 6. IAVCEI. Puerto de la Cruz. Tenerife, 31 May-4 June 2010.
- 193.- Ibáñez, J.M. High definition seismic tomography of active volcanic island using active and passive experiments. Keynote lecture. Cities on Volcanoes 6. IAVCEI. Puerto de la Cruz. Tenerife, 31 May-4 June 2010.
- 194.- Martín, J.J., García-Cacho, L., Rodríguez, R., Eff-Darwich, A., Ibáñez, J.M., Trujillo, A., Reñasco, J., Serra Llopert, J., Raja, F., Bancora, C., Calvo, D., Mass media and Volcanic risk in the Canary islands. Cities on Volcanoes 6. IAVCEI. Puerto de la Cruz. Tenerife, 31 May-4 June 2010.
- 195.- Orozco-Rojas, J., Almendros, J., Ibáñez, J.M. and Bretón, M. Location of low frequency signals associated to volcanic explosions of Volcán de Fuego de Colima using broad band Semblance Analysis. Cities on Volcanoes 6. IAVCEI. Puerto de la Cruz. Tenerife, 31 May-4 June 2010.
- 196.- Orozco-Rojas, J., Ibáñez, J.M., Esteban-Parra, M.J., Zobin, V. and Bretón, M., Statistical analysis of along continuous time series of volcanic explosions of Volcán de Fuego de Colima, México. Cities on Volcanoes 6. IAVCEI. Puerto de la Cruz. Tenerife, 31 May-4 June 2010.
- 197.- Orozco-Rojas, J., Bretón, M., Cortés, G., Santiago, H. and Ibáñez, J.M., Seismic characterization of seismicity recorded by seismic array at Volcán de Colima, México. Cities on Volcanoes 6. IAVCEI. Puerto de la Cruz. Tenerife, 31 May-4 June 2010.
- 198.- Prudencio, J., García-Yeguas, A., Ibáñez, J.M. and Alguacil, G., Initial results of seismic attenuation for P-waves on Tenerife island (Canary Islands, Spain). Cities on Volcanoes 6. IAVCEI. Puerto de la Cruz. Tenerife, 31 May-4 June 2010.

199.- Raffaele, R., Scarfi, L., Badi, G., Ibáñez, J.M., Imposta, S., Sub-horizontal subduction in Western Argentina, between 29°S and 34°S, as viewed from a local seismic network. Cities on Volcanoes 6. IAVCEI. Puerto de la Cruz. Tenerife, 31 May-4 June 2010.

200.- Romero-Ruiz, C., Ibáñez, J.M., Carrión, F., and Luis, V., Seismic series accompanies the 1704-1705 eruption of Sietefuentes-Fasnia-Arafo and their effects. Volcanological and seismological implications. Cities on Volcanoes 6. IAVCEI. Puerto de la Cruz. Tenerife, 31 May-4 June 2010.

201.- Romero-Ruiz, C., Luis, V., Ibáñez, J.M. and Carrión, F., Local site amplification in Tenerife island. The example of some historical seismic series accompanies volcanic eruption and the implications on the seismic risk evaluation. Cities on Volcanoes 6. IAVCEI. Puerto de la Cruz. Tenerife, 31 May-4 June 2010.

2011

202.- De Barros, L. F. Martini, C. J. Bean, A. García-Yeguas and J.M. Ibáñez. Magmatic storage below Teide volcano from reflected and scattered seismic waves. European Geophysical Union. 3 al 8 de Abril de 2011. Viena (Austria).

203.- Del Pezzo, Edoardo Jose Morales, Jesus Ibanez, Daniel Stich, and Francesca Bianco Attenuation for P and S waves in the upper mantle beneath Iberian peninsula in the frequency range 0.2 - 8 Hz from Broad-Band recordings of the (600 km) deep earthquake of April 11, 2010. EGU2011- General Assembly, Vienna 3-8 April, 2011.

204.- Prudencio, J., E. Del Pezzo, A. García-Yeguas and J. Ibáñez. Intrinsic and scattering attenuation image of Teide volcanic complex from an active seismic experiment. European Geophysical Union. 3 al 8 de Abril de 2011. Viena (Austria).

2012

205.- Carmona, E., Almendros, J., Martin, R., Cortés, G., Alguacil, G., Moreno, J., Martín, B., Martos, A., Serrano, I., Stich, D. and Ibáñez, J., 2012, Seismic monitoring at Deception Island volcano (Antarctica): Recent advances. EGU General Assembly, 22–27 April 2012, Vienna (Austria). EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts 14, 12717.

206.- Boué A., Lesage P., Cortés G., Benítez C., Ibáñez J., Álvarez I., Del La Torre A., Gutiérrez L., Arámbula R., González-Amézcuca M., Reyes-Dávila G. 2012. Improving the Material Failure Forecast Method (FFM) for eruption prediction by automatic classification of volcano-seismic signals. Cities on Volcanoes 7. Colima, Mexico.

207.- García-Yeguas A., Koulakov I., Jakolev A., Ibáñez J.M. 2012. From 3D to 4D seismic tomography at EL Hierro Island (Canary Islands, Spain). Geophysical Research Abstracts. EGU General Assembly 2012. 14. EGU2012-5563. EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts 14, 5563.

208.- García-Yeguas A., Koulakov I., Ibáñez J., Jakolev A., Romero C. 2012. 3D and 4D Seismic Tomography at El Hierro (Canary Islands, Spain). Oral Communication. MAKAVOL 2012 EL HIERRO: International Meeting on Island Volcano Risk Management. International.

209.- Prudencio, J., Ibáñez, J., García-Yeguas, A. and Del Pezzo, E., 2012, 2D intrinsic and scattering attenuation tomography of Tenerife and Deception Island (Antarctica) from active seismic experiments, MAKAVOL 2012 EL HIERRO, 10-15 October, El Hierro (Canary Islands, Spain).

210.- Carrión, F., Díaz-Moreno, A., Martin, J.B., Moreno, J., Prudencio, J., García-Yeguas, A., Ibáñez, J., Barrancos, J., Pérez, N., Barros, I., Bandomo, Z. and Gonçalves, A.,

2012, The New seismic network for seismo-volcanic monitoring of Fogo Island (Cape Verde): Evidences of seismically active volcano, MAKAVOL 2012 EL HIERRO, 10-15 October, El Hierro (Canary Islands, Spain).

2013

211.- Prudencio, J., Ibáñez, J., De Siena, L. and Del Pezzo, E., 2013, 3D attenuation structure of Deception Island (Antarctica), EGU General Assembly 2013, 5 - 12 April, Vienna (Austria).

212.- Prudencio, J., Del Pezzo, E., De Siena, L. and Ibáñez, J., 2013, 3D attenuation structure at Tenerife Island (Canary Islands, Spain), EGU General Assembly 2013, 5 - 12 April, Vienna (Austria). EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts 15, 1953.

213.- Prudencio, J., Ibáñez, J., García-Yeguas, A. and Del Pezzo, E., 2013, 2D Intrinsic And Scattering Attenuation Tomography Of Tenerife And Deception Island (Antarctica) From Active Seismic Experiments, EGU General Assembly 2013, 5 - 12 April, Vienna (Austria). EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts 15, 1955

214.- Prudencio, J., De Siena, L., Ibáñez, J. and Del Pezzo, E., 2013, From 2D to 3D attenuation tomography in Deception Island (Antarctica), AGU Fall Meeting 2013, 9-13 December, San Francisco (USA). AGU Fall Meeting Abstracts 1, 2459

215.- García-Yeguas, A., Granados, M.C., García, L., Benítez, C., De la Torre, A., Álvarez, I., Díaz-Moreno, A., Ibáñez, J. Application of a cross correlation-based picking algorithm to active seismic signals from experiments in Tenerife Island (Canary Islands, Spain). Poster. American Geophysical Union (AGU) Meeting 2013. AGU Fall Meeting Abstracts 1, 2293

216.- Pérez, N., Luis Somoza, Luis González de Vallejo, Takeshi Sagiya, Ricardo León, Pedro A Hernández, Ander Biain, Francisco J González, Teresa Medialdea, Daniel Gonzalez-Aller, José Luis Sánchez de La Madrid, José Barrancos, Jesús M Ibáñez, Hirochika Sumino. Precursory geophysical, geodetic and geochemical signatures of a new 2012 submarine eruption off the northwestern coast of El Hierro, Canary Islands, Spain. EGU General Assembly 2013, 5 - 12 April, Vienna (Austria). EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts 15, 12169

2014

217.- Cocina, O., Zuccarello, L., Díaz-Moreno, A., Prudencio, J., Cavallaro, D., Firetto M., Coltelli, M., Carrión, F., Carmisciano, C., D'Anna, G., Lhur, B., Ibáñez, J., Patané, D. and TOMO-ETNA working group, 2014. TOMO-ETNA: an active seismic experiment at Etna volcano. Conferenza A. Rittman, 29-31 October, Nicolosi (Italy)

218.- Del Pezzo, E., Bianco, F., Prudencio, J. and Ibáñez, J., 2014. Separate intrinsic- and scattering-Q images of volcanoes using scattered waves. A new method applied to Deception Island volcano. 33^o Convegno GNGTS, 25-27 November, Bologna (Italy).

219.- Díaz-Moreno, A., García-Yeguas, A., De Angelis, S., Prudencio, J., Ibáñez, J., Morales, J. and Koulakov, I., 2014, Relative and probabilistic non linear relocation of the seismicity of El Hierro (Canary Islands, Spain): Implications for the 2011-2012 eruption, EGU Meeting 2014, 27 April – 2 May, Vienna (Austria). EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts 16, 5261.

220.- García-Yeguas, A., Del Pezzo, E., Prudencio, J., Ibáñez, J. and De Siena, L., 2014, P-wave scattering attenuation images of Tenerife island using Autocorrelation

Functions from velocity seismic tomography fluctuations, EGU Meeting 2014, 27 April – 2 May, Vienna (Austria). EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts 16, 4386

221.- Ibáñez, J., Patané, D., Carrión, F., Zuccarello, L., Prudencio, J., Cocina, O., Díaz-Moreno, A., Coltelli, M., Urbano, L., Scarfi, L., Bianco, F., García-Yeguas, A., Lhür, B., Cavallaro, D. and Carlino, M., 2014. TOMO-ETNA MED-SUV. ISES an Active Seismic and Passive Seismic Experiment at Mt. Etna Volcano. An Integrated Marine and On-Land Geophysical Survey. MED-SUV 1th year Meeting, 7-9 July, Nicolosi (Italy).

222.- Ibáñez, J., Patané, D., Coltelli, M., Carrión, F., Bruno, P., Cocina, O., Zuccarello, L., Díaz-Moreno, A., Prudencio, J., Bianco, F., Cavallaro, D., Firetto-Carlino, M., Carmisciano, C., Cocchi, L., D'Anna, G.D., Lhür, B. and TOMO-ETNA working group, 2014. TOMO-ETNA: an active seismic experiment at Etna volcano. 33° Convegno GNGTS, 25-27 November, Bologna (Italy).

223.- Ibáñez, J., Patané, D., Puglisi, G., Zuccarello, L., Bianco, F., Luehr, B., Díaz-Moreno, A., Prudencio, J., Koulakov, I., Del Pezzo, E., Cocina, O., Coltelli, M., Scarfi, L., De Gori, P. and Carrión, F., 2014, TOMO-ETNA MED-SUV. ISES an active seismic and passive seismic experiment at Mt. Etna volcano. An integrated marine and onland geophysical survey, EGU Meeting 2014, 27 April – 2 May, Vienna (Austria). EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts 16, 5534

224.- Ledo, J., García-Yeguas, A., Piña-Varas, P., Ibáñez, J., Queralt, P., Marcuello, A., Prudencio, J. and Díaz-Moreno, A., 2014. 3D MT and seismic velocity models: Tenerife Island (Spain). 22nd EM Induction Workshop, 24-30 August, Weimar (Germany).

225.- Prudencio, J., Taira, T., De Siena, L., Onizawa, S., Ibáñez, J., Hellweg, M., Del Pezzo, E., Aoyama, H., García-Yeguas, A., Oshima, H. and Díaz-Moreno, A., 2014, First attenuation study at Usu volcano (Hokkaido, Japan), EGU Meeting 2014, 27 April – 2 May, Vienna (Austria). EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts 16, 6902

226.- Urbano, L., Prudencio, J., Ibáñez, J. and Vilchéz-González, J.M., 2014. Raising volcanic risk awareness among children at school. MED-SUV 1th year Meeting, 7-9 July, Nicolosi (Italy).

227.- Vilchéz-González, J.M., Prudencio, J., Urbano, L., Ibáñez, J. and Carrillo Rosúa, F.J., 2014. Los Volcanes y sus peligros. Proyecto educativo para Educación Primaria, II Congreso Internacional de Ciencias de la Educación y del Desarrollo, 25-27 junio, Granada (España).

228.- Vilchéz-González, J.M., Prudencio, J., Urbano, L., Ibáñez, J. and Carrillo Rosúa, F.J., 2014. El conocimiento sobre volcanes en Educación Primaria, II Congreso Internacional de investigación e innovación en Educación Infantil y Educación Primaria, 14-16 mayo, Murcia (España).

2015

229.- Delgado-Ramos, Fernando, Jesús M. Ibáñez, Gerardo Alguacil, Francisco José Calvo Solana, Susana Tortosa Molina, Alfonso Sánchez Salvador, Juan Carlos Gómez Vargas. ACTIVIDAD SÍSMICA REGISTRADA EN LAS PRESAS DE BÉZNAR Y RULES, CUENCA DEL GUADALFE: CONCLUSIONES Y PROPUESTAS DE MEJORA DEL SISTEMA. X Jornadas Españolas de Presas. Organizado por el Comoté Nacional Español de Grandes Presas. Sevilla, 18-20 Febrero. 2015

230.- Nunn, C.; Julian, B. R.; Foulger, G. R.; Patané, D.; Ibáñez, J. M.; Briole, P.; Mhanna, N. Mount Etna: 3-D and 4-D structure using seismic tomography. American Geophysical Union, Fall Meeting 2015, abstract id. S23D-2779

231.- Volk, Friderike Meike; Bean, Christopher; Lokmer, Ivan; Pérez, Nemesio; Ibáñez, Jesús. Identifying apparent velocity changes in cross correlated microseism noise data. EGU General Assembly 2015, held 12-17 April, 2015 in Vienna, Austria. id.12176.

232.- Volk, M. F.; Bean, C. J.; Lokmer, I.; Perez, N. M.; Ibanez, J. M. Tracking velocity changes from ambient noise and repeating airgun shots in Tenerife. American Geophysical Union, Fall Meeting 2015, abstract id. S41B-2750

2016

233.- Birger-G. Luehr, Jesus M. Ibáñez, Alejandro Díaz-Moreno, Janire Prudencio, Domenico Patane, Ivan Koulakov, Dirk Roessler, Ornella Cocina, Luciano Zuccarello, Toni Zieger, Torsten Dahm. The TOMO-ETNA Experiment resolving the crust around Etna volcano, Sicily, with active and passive seismic investigations. CoV9 2016 conference in Puerto Varas, Chile, November 20-25, 2016.

2017

234.- Bueno Rodriguez, A.; Titos Luzón, M.; Garcia Martinez, L.; Benitez, C.; Ibáñez, J. M. Automatic Seismic-Event Classification with Convolutional Neural Networks. American Geophysical Union, Fall Meeting 2017, abstract #S21E-03

235.- Titos Luzón, M.; Bueno Rodriguez, A.; Garcia Martinez, L.; Benitez, C.; Ibáñez, J. M. Automatic Classification of volcano-seismic events based on Deep Neural Networks. American Geophysical Union, Fall Meeting 2017, abstract #S41D-01

2018

236.- Bean, Chris; Volk, Meike; Perez, Nemesio; Ibanez, Jesus; Mollhoff, Martin. Quantifying the stress sensitivity of a volcanic edifice using an active time-lapse seismic experiment. 20th EGU General Assembly, EGU2018, Proceedings from the conference held 4-13 April, 2018 in Vienna, Austria, p.17782

237.- Bueno Rodriguez, Angel; Titos Luzon, Manuel; Garcia Martinez, Luz; Benitez Ortuzar, Carmen; Diaz Moreno, Alejandro; De Angelis, Silvio; Ibañez Godoy, Jesus. A Bayesian Neural Network approach for the classification of volcano-seismic events. 20th EGU General Assembly, EGU2018, Proceedings from the conference held 4-13 April, 2018 in Vienna, Austria, p.9526.

238.- Bueno, Angel, Manuel Titos, Luz García, Isaac Álvarez, Jesús Ibáñez, Carmen Benítez. Classification of Volcano-Seismic Signals with Bayesian Neural Networks. 2018 26th European Signal Processing Conference (EUSIPCO). 2295-2299. 2018/9/3. DOI: 10.23919/EUSIPCO.2018.8553358. Roma, Italy, Italy

239.- Ledo, Juanjo; García-Yeguas, Araceli; Piña-Varas, Perla; Prudencio, Janire; Queralt, Pilar; Marcuello, Alex; Ibáñez, Jesús M.; Benjumea, Beatriz; Sánchez-Alzola, Alberto; Pérez, Nemesio. Imaging Tenerife volcanic island from fuzzy logic clustering of electrical resistivity and seismic velocity 3D models. 20th EGU General Assembly, EGU2018, Proceedings from the conference held 4-13 April, 2018 in Vienna, Austria, p.4404

240.- Titos, M., Bueno, A., García, L., Benítez, M. C., & Ibáñez, J. (2018). Detection and classification of continuous volcano-seismic signals with recurrent neural networks. IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing, 57(4), 1936-1948.

2019

241.- Cocina, O., Ibanez, J., Zuccarello, L., Del Pezzo, E., Castro-Melgar, I., & Prudencio, J. (2019, January). 2D and 3D attenuation tomographies at Mt. Etna (Italy). In Geophysical Research Abstracts (Vol. 21).

242.- Diaz Moreno, A., Bueno Rodriguez, A., Zuccarello, L., Woolam, J., Titos Luzón, M., Benitez, C., ... & Ibáñez, J. M. (2019, December). PICOSS: Python interface for the classification of seismic signals. In AGU Fall Meeting Abstracts (Vol. 2019, pp. NG21B-0954).

243.- García, L., Zucarello, L., Álvarez, I., Benítez, C., Cuius, A., Titos, M., ... & Ibáñez, J. (2019, January). Automatic detection and characterization of low frequency seismicity: Long Period events detection and clusterization into families. An example case for Mt. Etna. In Geophysical Research Abstracts (Vol. 21).

244.- Titos, M., Bueno, Á., García, L., Zuccarello, L., Álvarez, I., Ibañez, J., & Benítez, C. (2019, January). Using RNN for automatic detection and classification of volcano seismic signals at Deception Island Volcano. In Geophysical Research Abstracts (Vol. 21).

245.- Yeguas, A. G., García, L., Benítez, C., Mota, S., & Ibáñez, J. M. (2019, January). Can citizens train Artificial Intelligence algorithms to process volcano-seismic signals?. In Geophysical Research Abstracts (Vol. 21).

246.- Yeguas, A. G., Martínez, L. G., Fernández, S. M., Prudencio, J., Zuccarello, L., Vílchez, M. V., ... & Ibáñez, J. M. (2019, January). How do volcanoes communicate? PIISA Project: approaching research in volcanoes to Secondary School Science Education. In Geophysical Research Abstracts (Vol. 21).

247.- Zuccarello, L., Martínez, L. G., Alvarez, I., Benitez, M. C., Titos, M., Bueno, A., ... & Ibanez, J. (2019, January). Characterization of low frequency seismicity at Etna Volcano during 2010 eruption, using advanced automatic analysis algorithms. In Geophysical Research Abstracts (Vol. 21).

2020

248.- EGU General Assembly Conference , 2020. Poster. Cabrera, I., Soubestre, J., D'Auria, L., Del Pezzo, E., Barrancos, J., Padilla, G. D., Ibáñez, J.M. ... & Pérez, N. M. Velocity and attenuation models of Tenerife and La Palma (Canary Islands, Spain) through Ambient Noise Tomography (No. EGU2020-318). Copernicus Meetings.

249.- Melgar, I. C., Prudencio, J., Taira, T. A., Gritto, R., & Ibanez, J. (2020, December). Seismic Attenuation Imaging of The Geysers Geothermal Field, USA. In AGU Fall Meeting 2020: Online Everywhere.

250.- Prudencio, J., Castro-Melgar, I., Taira, T., Gritto, R., & Ibáñez, J. M. (2020, December). Seismic Attenuation Imaging of The Geysers Geothermal Field, USA. In AGU Fall Meeting Abstracts (Vol. 2020, pp. S061-0015).

2021

251.- Castro-Melgar, I., Prudencio, J., Ibáñez, J.M., Gatsios, T., & Parcharidis, I. (2021, November). Operational Monitoring of a Volcano Before Entering in Unrest Phase Using Sentinel 1 DINSAR and MTINSAR: the Case of La Palma Volcanic Island. In Safe Greece International Conference 2021

2022

252.- Pérez, I. C., D'Auria, L., Soubestre, J., Przeor, M., Koulakov, I., van Dorth, D. M., Prudencio, J. Ibáñez, J.M. ... & Pérez, N. (2022). Spatio-temporal velocity variations

observed during the pre-eruptive episode of La Palma eruption inferred from ambient noise interferometry (No. EGU22-5133). Copernicus Meetings.

253.- D'Auria, L., Koulakov, I., Prudencio, J., Cabrera-Pérez, I., Ibáñez, J. M., Barrancos, J., ... & Pérez, N. M. (2022, May). Tomographic imaging of the magmatic system feeding the 2021 Cumbre Vieja eruption (La Palma, Canary Islands). In EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts (pp. EGU22-4591).

254.- Iván Cabrera Pérez, Luca D'Auria, Jean Soubestre, Monika Przeor, Ivan Koulakov, David Martínez van Dorth, Jesús M Ibáñez, Víctor Ortega, José Barrancos, Germán D Padilla, Rubén García-Hernández, Nemesio Pérez (2022). Spatio-temporal velocity variations observed during the pre-eruptive episode of La Palma eruption inferred from ambient noise interferometry. In EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts (pp. EGU22-5133)

255.- Ignacio Castro-Melgar, Theodoros Gatsios, Janire Prudencio, Jesus Ibanez, Issaak Parcharidis (2022) Operational use of Sentinel 1 data and interferometric methods to detect precursors for volcanic hazard warning system: the case of La Palma volcanic complex last eruption. Conference: ESA Living Planet Symposium 2022. Country/TerritoryGermany. CityBonn.Period 23/05/22 → 27/05/22

256.- Castro-Melgar, I., Gatsios, T., Prudencio, J., Ibanez, J., & Parcharidis, I. (2022, September). Monitoreo de la deformación del complejo volcánico de Santorini aplicando interferometría PSDS SAR (2015-2021) usando imágenes Sentinel 1 SAR. In XIX Congreso de Tecnologías de la Información Geográfica-TIG al servicio de los ODS.

2023

Experience in organizing R&D activities
Organization of scientific-technological conferences, seminars, conferences, etc.

- Organizer of the Spanish-Japanese Joint Symposium on Seismic Ground Motion in Sedimentary Basins. Granada, July 27-29, 1992.
- Secretary-Organizer of the V Conference on Instrumentation and Data Processing in Earth Sciences. Ibero-American Meeting. Granada March 29-31, 1993.
- Member of the organizing committee of the international Congress “Centennial of the Cartuja Observatory”, Granada, 2002.
- Moderator in the session on Detection and treatment of seismic signals of the I Hispano-Portuguese Assembly of Geodesy and Geophysics.
- Member of the organizing committee of the Congress “VII Spanish Symposium on Polar Studies”, Granada. September 18-20, 2009.
- Member of the organizing committee of the international Congress “Antarctica Climate evolution”. Granada September 7-11, 2009.
- Member of the organizing committee of the international Congress “Cities of Volcanoes 6th”. Puerto de la Cruz, May 31-June 4, 2010.